

CATHOLIC DIOCESAN SCHOOLS' ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION- MAKING PRACTICES AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE SCHOOLS' ETHICAL CLIMATE AND EMPLOYEES' MORALE

REV. FR. VICTOR BRIAN L. CATALBAS, EMD, *Author*
MS. ROSALINDA C. BALORIA, EMD, *Co-author*
MR. JOSE CALASANZ JULYSESSES D. TABIA, EMD, *Co-author*

Post-Graduate School Department, Saint Vincent's College, Dipolog City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443691>

ABSTRACT

This research delved into the ethical decision-making practices among administrators in Catholic diocesan schools and their profound impact on the school's ethical climate and the morale of employees in the province of Zamboanga del Norte, encompassing the cities of Dipolog and Dapitan. Employing a descriptive method and correlational research design, this study systematically portrayed the characteristics and pertinent details of leaders and employees across five Catholic schools within the Diocese of Dipolog with factual precision. The findings revealed that the prevailing ethical decision-making practices among administrators predominantly revolved around benevolence and principled actions, fostering a caring ethical environment conducive to nurturing a confident and enthusiastic workforce. These ethical practices exerted a moderate influence on the school's ethical climate, providing substantial support for career development and other opportunities for employees. Conclusions drawn from this study underscored the pivotal role of administrators' ethical decision-making in shaping a positive ethical climate within schools. Consequently, recommendations were proposed for administrators to embrace optimal ethical decision-making practices. These recommendations aimed to cultivate a moral atmosphere within the work environment, enhancing the ethical standards practiced within schools, and ultimately fostering a more productive and contented workforce.

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a moral issue. Leaders make decisions every day that impact the lives of others (Vogel, 2012). By stepping into educational leadership roles, school and district administrators accept responsibility for the “broader community welfare” of the students, teachers, and parents that schools serve (Marion, 2005). In creating and maintaining a community conducive to academic, emotional, and social learning, all school personnel look up to their administrator as the primary architect and promoter of the values and standards ensuring everything and everyone in the school building function according to the highest ethical standard possible.

Top managers are primarily responsible for setting ethical standards, for communicating them formally or informally through their own behavior and decisions and the strategies implemented, and their appropriation by the members of the company (Ambrose and Schminke, 2003). Why so? Because, in addition, leaders ought to be a crucial source of ethical guidance for employees and should at the same time be responsible for the moral development in an organization (Mihelic, Lipicknik and Tekavcic, 2010). In short, leaders are a moral compass in the formation of an ethical climate for a better work environment. The more the leader “walks the talk” the higher the level of trust and respect he generates from followers (Mihelic, et.al., 2010). Stated differently, the more the chief executive demonstrates the standards and the example for people to follow the more morally healthy the organization is (Kelly, 1990). Thus, one can only see that leaders are responsible in creating a positive and healthy corporate culture which dramatically improves people’s lives.

However, the absence of an ethical culture in the organization that is supposed to be initiated and exemplified by a leader would lead to organizational disaster and decay. The biggest scandal in business happened in 2001 when Enron, an American Energy company and its accounting firm Arthur Anderson willfully presented inaccurate information about the companies’ financial statement and its auditor. As a result, both companies were out of business, Enron’s shareholders lost \$25 billion while the accounting firm closed. The latter’s closure resulted in 85,000 jobs lost. And who is to blame for the biggest scandal in the business world? According to the National Business Ethics Survey of 2013, managers are to blame for workplace misconduct (www.floridaonline.tech.com). The failure of any leader to manifest moral ascendancy or to develop an ethical behavior would result to organizational meltdown.

In a national level, last 2014, former president of one of the state universities in the Philippines was dismissed for utilizing the universities’ resources for his home improvements. He was charged with grave misconduct, malversation, indirect bribery, and violations of Republic Act No. 3019, or the Anti-Graft and Corrupt Practices Act. He was also penalized with cancellation of eligibility, perpetual disqualification from holding public office, and forfeiture of retirement benefits (www.news.abs-cbn.com).

In a local level, few years ago, in one of the elementary schools of Zamboanga del Norte, bribery was being tolerated by a high ranking official in a school district. The school leader receives money or items of great value in exchange for a teaching position. This is a sad reality in an organization that is tasked to form the hearts and minds of individuals to become ethical

beings. As a result, teachers developed Barnard's "zone of indifference" where they follow orders because the leader is superior but not because he has moral ascendancy.

The moral lapses or corporate crimes done by leaders are just few of the many examples of unethical practices in the realm of business that is either initiated by the leader or the leaders' lack of moral courage to develop an ethical working environment. To avoid unethical behaviors that may possibly result to questioning leadership legitimacy and integrity (Fulmer, 2005), business educators forced the business world to review its business ethics to be ethically conscious. Managers and researchers have turned their attention to ethics management (Trevino & Brown, 2005). The primary concern now is to create a common perception of employees of what is correct behavior that would serve as a moral code of the organization. This shared perception, which is initiated by the leader, is related to what is considered as ethically correct behavior which collectively referred to as the ethical climate of the organization. The preservation and success of the organization depend upon leaders who developed ethical climate through their ethical decision-making practices.

The ethical or moral development of leaders play an important role in ethical decision-making practices. Individual ethical values influence the moral reasoning of individuals as they consider what constitutes right or wrong behavior (Ambrose, Arnaud, Schminke, 2008). The most popular model of cognitive moral development (CMD) was proposed by Lawrence Kohlberg (1984) in his book *Essays on Moral Development: The Psychology of Moral Development*.

Kohlberg developed three levels of moral standards from which individuals based their ethical decisions. These are *preconventional*, *conventional* and *postconventional* moralities (Kohlberg, p. 172). The first level is *preconventional morality* in which actions are evaluated in terms of whether they avoid punishment or lead to rewards. In this level, individuals react to ethical problems from an egoistic perspective, evaluating moral choices primarily in terms of personal consequences, needs, and exchanges of favors. Correct actions are those that lead to personal rewards and those that allow one to avoid punishment (Ambrose et al, 2008). The second level is *conventional morality* in which actions are evaluated in terms of maintaining a good image in the eyes of other people. In this level, correct behavior is defined by the expectations of others and what helps others. What is right is determined by the laws, rules, and obligations of society and what is needed to maintain social order (Ambrose, et. al., 2008). According to Kohlberg, many individuals never progress beyond level II. The third level is *postconventional morality* in which actions are products of formulating abstract ethical principles and upholding them to avoid self-condemnation. Individuals here are guided by self-chosen ethical principles, justice, and the rights of human beings. Kohlberg's theory of cognitive moral development is instrumental in the formulation of Victor and Cullen's (1987, 1988) three ethical criteria namely *egoism*, *benevolence*, and *principle*.

Egoism criterion. This refers to a behavioral tendency that is essentially self-interested in seeking pleasure and escaping pain. In a largely egoistic climate, self-interest might be the dominant consideration (Victor and Cullen, 1988). It is a theory that states that an individual should follow the greatest benefit for oneself (Upchurch, 1998).

Benevolence criterion. It is associated with concerns to satisfy the interests of as many people as possible. In an organization characterized primarily by benevolent climate, a teleological consideration of the well-being of others may be dominant reasoning used by employees to identify and solve ethical problems (Victor and Cullen, 1988). The theory of justice (i.e., benevolence) represents acting in a fair and impartial basis, maximizes the good, and follows impartial distribution of rules (Upchurch, 1998).

Principle criterion. It relates to internalization of universal standards and beliefs by the members of the organization. With a largely principled climate, the application and interpretation of rules or law might be the dominant form of reasoning (Victor and Cullen, 1988). This means that an individual keeps the rule if the outcome of keeping the rule is greater than the outcome of rejecting the rule (Upchurch, 1998).

These three criteria will be used in this study as the basis for leaders' ethical reasoning.

Leaders are basically moral managers. As moral managers, ethical leaders use leadership tools such as rewards, discipline, communication, and decision-making to communicate the importance of ethics, set standards, and hold employees accountable to those standards (Treviño et al., 2000, 2003). Managers who engage in ethical leadership behavior act as virtuous agents in promoting an ethical climate (Flynn, 2008). Leadership research has shown that business leaders are primarily responsible for creating and managing the culture and climate of the firm (Schein, 1985). Leaders have a significant influence on employee's ethical climate evaluation (Mulki, Jaramillo, Locander, 2009). There are even many studies support the idea that ethical leaders should have a positive effect on ethical climate (Mayer, Kuenzi, Greenbaum, 2010). Thus, leaders really influence the kind of ethical climate the organization has.

Ethical climate is an organizational construct that has been studied and analyzed from Homans in 1950 until Theiring in 2016. But the most widely used study is from Victor and Cullen in 1988. Victor and Cullen (1988) defined ethical climate as shared perception of what ethically correct behavior is and how ethical issues should be handled in the organization. Ethical climate help workers solve ethical issues by giving them answers to "what should I do?" when faced with a moral dilemma (Homans, 1950). For example, in a hiring decision, expectations about whose interests should be considered and/or what codes or laws should be applied? Or, how people in an organization typically decide whether it is right or wrong to pay kickbacks. These are subjects for ethical deliberations in the organizations.

Victor and Cullen (1987, 1988) established a framework that categorizes ethical working climate and provides an understanding of what constitutes ethical behavior in an organization based on the ethical criteria and locus of control that exist in the firm (Victor & Cullen). Victor and Cullen (1988) developed a typology made up of five dimensions of ethical working climate that can be found in an organization, namely, instrumental, caring, independence, rules and law, *and code* climates. A description of the five climates is presented below, with examples of the typical items associated with the respective types.

Instrumental climate. Individuals employed in an organization demonstrating an instrumental climate look out for their own self-interest ("In this organization, people protect their own interest above all else"). Individuals in an instrumental climate tend to exhibit behaviors consistent with guarding themselves to ensure that their interests are protected and are expected to engage in behaviors, ethical or otherwise, to enhance the success of the organization, regardless of the outcomes (Victor & Cullen, 1988).

Caring climate. An organization with a caring climate encourages a moral judgment approach geared towards behaving in a manner that benefits the greater good. Individuals employed in this type of climate tend to place importance on the well-being of others in the organization, as well as the organization and society in general ("What is best for everyone in the organization is a major consideration here"). This climate focuses on the greater good and, subsequently, encourages behavior that ensures the greater good for everyone in the

organization and the organization as a whole. Individuals are expected to always behave in a manner that is efficient, and which leads to the best possible outcome for the customers and public (Victor and Cullen, 1988).

Independence, rules, laws and codes climate. Organizations with this kind of climate have established a strict adherence to rules, policies, and procedures that outline the norms and expectations of the organization (“It is very important to follow the organization’s rules and procedures here”). Thus, one’s success is tied to an individual’s ability to follow such rules, leaving little room for one’s own decision to deviate (Victor & Cullen, 1988).

Educational institution is one of the most important social institutions in the society that sculpts behavior of individuals. It is the seedbed of future leaders and ethical citizens. Schools, through their leaders, should have well-defined ethical climate so that all the members of the organization will have a common ethical standard or norms that guide their decisions, and thus creating a school culture and identity. It is necessary in every school to identify its dominant ethical climate from among the five types of ethical climate of Victor and Cullen (1988) so that the members of the organization will have the same moral perceptual lens in resolving organizational issues. So, it is imperative for school administrators to initiate and maintain an ethical climate through his/her ethical decision-making practices not only to set an example of what ethically correct behavior is in a particular school but also to increase the morale of the employees.

Leaders who make ethical decision improve the morale of the employee. By morale, it means “homefulness” (Beardsley Ruml) or the degree to which an employee feels good about his or her work and work environment (Mcknight, Ahmad, Schroeder, 2001). Ethical leadership is strongly associated with a subordinate’s satisfaction with his/her leaders, with his/her exerting extra effort and with his/her willingness to report problems (Brown, Trevino, & Harrison, 2005). High morale is the result of job-satisfaction which is again the result of motivational attitude of the management (www. ebrary.net). From an Aristotelian perspective, a culture supportive of ethics allows for virtuous actions reflective of the potential for human excellence (Ciulla 2004; Guillén 2006). Thus, when moral virtuousness is experienced in human relationships, employees likely feel more appreciated, loved, and well treated (Argandoña 2011), which is positive for both their emotional state and job outcomes (Cameron et al. 2004; Rego et al. 2010). Since ethics is so intimately linked to excellence and perfection in human action (Argandoña 201 1; Melé 2009), the theoretical basis for expecting a relationship between ethical culture and positive employee emotions and attitudes is a strong one. In this way, good leadership is conceptualized as connected to ethical practices in the workplace, on the grounds that across the ethical dimensions, leadership has a potential to improve the leader–employee relationship, bringing about an assortment of positive job results for the workers (Ruiz-Palomino, 2013) while the lack of ethical behavior in organizational practice is likely to cause harm to the morale of employees (Alshammari, Almutairi & Thuwaini, 2015).

The decision-making process of the five (5) diocesan schools of the Diocese of Dipolog relies so much on the executive vice-president since the president must prioritize his ecclesiastical functions of two dioceses over school management as Local Ordinary of the Diocese of Dipolog and as apostolic administrator of the diocese of Iligan. In the absence of the president, the executive vice president must assist the former and perform all the duties and functions of the president for the five (5) diocesan schools when so designated or in the latter’s absence. In other words, the Executive Vice President must plan and execute the plans for the five (5) diocesan schools. In coordination with the president or the executive vice-president, the administrator of each school manages the day-to-day activities of the school, lays out an

optimistic vision for the future of the school, and provides ethical decisions in times of crisis. However, in every organization, there are always management issues and problems that need to be identified and hopefully solved. While not discounting that there are best practices unique to the schools' identity because of the management's efforts, there are also organizational issues that need to be properly addressed through research, not to judge or criticize ethical management practices, but to assess the ethical quality of school management based on scientific findings. Ethics Based on the researcher's empirical observation as former faculty member in one of the five (5) diocesan schools', organizational problems like organizational politics, breakdown of communication, lack of proper documentation of reports and meetings, gossips, and lack of proper implementation of policies and procedures are the issues that need to be addressed for the improvement of the organization. While issues may vary from one school to another organizational issues need to be checked and resolved by determining the ethical decision-making practices of leaders for the organization to retain its integrity and to avoid organizational meltdown.

The researcher strongly feels that there is a need to determine the ethical decision-making practices of administrators and find out if it made a significant influence in the formation of ethical climate in every school and in the employees' morale.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to determine the Catholic diocesan schools' administrators' ethical decision-making practices and its impact to the school's ethical climate and employees' morale in the province of Zamboanga del Norte and the cities of Dipolog and Dapitan.

Specifically, it will attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 sex,
 - 1.3 length of service,
 - 1.4 educational attainment, and
 - 1.5 seminars/trainings attended on ethical decision making?
2. What is the profile of employees in terms of:
 - 2.1 age,
 - 2.2 sex,
 - 2.3 length of service, and
 - 2.4 educational attainment?
3. What is the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along:
 - 3.1 egoism,
 - 3.2 benevolence, and
 - 3.3 principle?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices when grouped according to profile?
5. What is the level of schools' ethical climate along:
 - 5.1 caring,
 - 5.2 instrumental,
 - 5.3 independence, rules and laws and codes
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of administrators' ethical decision making practices and the level of schools' ethical climate?

7. What is the level of employees' morale?
 8. Is there a significant difference in the level of employees' morale when grouped according to profile?
 9. Is there a significant relationship between the level of administrators' ethical decision making practices and the level of employees' morale?
-

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive method, correlational research design. This research described systematically the information and prominent attributes of the leaders and employees of the five (5) Catholic schools in the Diocese of Dipolog, factually and accurately. The researcher also utilized the census survey form of descriptive research since it is necessary that information is gathered from every member of the population as it is readily accessible. The study investigated possible differences in the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices when grouped according to profile and the level of employees' morale when grouped according to profile.

In this design, the researcher studied the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. This study thus aimed at investigating the existence and the degree of relationship between the leaders' ethical decision-making practices and school's ethical climate and employees' morale. It was again used to determine the strength of association when there is statistical significance.

Setting of the Study

The study was conducted in the five (5) Catholic schools in the Diocese of Dipolog as mentioned in Chapter one.

Respondents of the Study

The population of the study were the two hundred and forty-two (242) leaders and employees of the five (5) Catholic schools in the Diocese of Dipolog. The statistic characterizing the population consists of sex, length of service, educational attainment, and seminars/trainings attended on ethical decision making. This shows that representative sample covers responses of administrators and employees of diverse demographical and professional characteristics so that the perception towards administrators' ethical decision practices, school's ethical climate and employees' morale can be evaluated effectively across different dimensions.

Sampling Technique

Since the researcher included all the administrators and employees of the five schools of the diocese, the purposive sampling was used in collecting the data.

Research Instrument

This research made use of the following instrument and techniques:

Questionnaire. The major tool in the gathering of data is the questionnaire which is designed according to the specific problems of the study. Additional information was obtained using unstructured interviews.

The questionnaire is divided into three parts.

Part I aimed at gathering information on the profile of the school administrators in terms of sex, length of service, educational attainment; and seminars/trainings attended on ethical decision making.

Part II aimed at assessing the school administrators' ethical decision-making practices. The questionnaire consisted of Forsyth's (1980, 2002) Ethics Position Questionnaire (EPQ). The EPQ was derived from Forsyth (1980) developed the EPQ to a shorter more general instrument to measure ethical judgments regarding psychological research.

Part III measured the schools' ethical climate using the Ethical Climate Questionnaire (ECQ) by Victor and Cullen (1987). These climates can be perceived within the school by individuals.

Part IV measured the employees' morale using the Employee Moral Questionnaire (EMQ) by Terri Levine.

Interview. This technique was utilized to get a better grasp of the present situation, aside from confirming and verifying the data inputs collected from the questionnaire. This study used the questionnaire as the interview guide.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the superintendent of the schools of the diocese and from the school leaders of each of the diocesan schools to conduct the study. The researcher, himself, personally administered the distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaires.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools and techniques were used to ensure the valid and systematic presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data: frequency and percentage, arithmetic mean, t-test for independent samples, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Regression analysis.

The frequency and percentage distribution table were used to describe the profile of school administrators. The percentage is computed using the formula:

$$P = \frac{\sum f}{n} \times 100$$

where

P = Percentage

f = frequency

n = total number of respondents

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices, school's ethical climate, and employees' morale. The weighted mean is computed using the formula:

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{\sum wx}{\sum w}$$

where

Weighted Mean = average level

Σ = symbol used to indicate the sum

x = scale value

w = weight

The following statistical continuum was used to interpret the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practice:

Statistical Continuum	Scale	Description
1.000 – 1.874	Completely Disagree	Never Practiced (N)
1.875 – 2.749	Largely Disagree	Very Rarely Practiced (V)
2.750 – 3.624	Moderately Disagree	Rarely Practiced (R)
3.625 – 4.499	Slightly Disagree	Sometimes Practiced (S)
4.500 – 5.374	Slightly Agree	Often Practiced (O)
5.375 – 6.249	Moderately Agree	Usually Practiced (U)
6.250 – 7.124	Largely Agree	Almost Always Practiced (AA)
7.125 – 8.000	Completely Agree	Always Practiced (A)

To describe the school's ethical climate, the researcher used the "moral continuum" as proposed by Cohen (1995). She states that it is helpful to think of moral climate as a continuum. At one end of the continuum is the positive moral climate, or ethical climate, in which organizational norms always facilitate agent behavior that merits the trust of organizational stakeholders. At the other end is the negative moral climate, or unethical climate, which, conversely, is never conducive to such behavior. The climate types will then be classified as unethical climate, moderately ethical climate, and highly ethical climate.

The following statistical continuum was used to interpret the level of ethical climate:

Statistical Continuum	Scale	Description
0.00 – 0.83	Completely False	Not at all Ethical (N)
0.84 – 1.66	Mostly False	Very Slightly Ethical (VS)
1.67 – 2.49	Somewhat False	Slightly Ethical (S)
2.50 – 3.32	Somewhat True	Moderately Ethical (M)
3.33 – 4.15	Mostly True	Highly Ethical (H)
4.16 – 5.00	Completely True	Very Highly Ethical (VH)

The following statistical continuum was used to interpret the level of employees' morale:

Statistical Continuum	Scale	Description
1.00 – 1.79	Never	Very Low
1.80 – 2.59	Rarely	Low
2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes but not very often	Moderate
3.40 – 4.19	Often but not always	High
4.20 – 5.00	Always	Very High

To determine whether there is a significant difference in the administrators' ethical decision practices when grouped according to profile Analysis of Variance was used. To determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of employees' morale when grouped according to profile Analysis of Variance was also used. The One Way ANOVA is computed using the formula:

$$F = \frac{MS_B}{MS_W} \qquad MS_B = \frac{SS_B}{df_B} \qquad MS_W = \frac{SS_W}{df_W}$$

Sum of Squares

$$SS_T = \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} \sum_{j=1}^C (x_{ij} - \bar{x})^2$$

$$SS_B = \sum_{j=1}^C n_j (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x})^2$$

$$SS_W = \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} \sum_{j=1}^C (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)^2$$

$$df_B = C - 1$$

$$df_W = N - C$$

$$df_T = N - 1$$

where

i = a particular member of a treatment level

j = a treatment level

C = number of treatment levels

n_j = number of observations in each treatment level

$\bar{x}$ = grand mean

$\bar{x}_j$ = column mean

x_{ij} = individual value

and

$$SS_T = SS_B + SS_W$$

where

SS_T = total sum of squares

SS_B = sum of squares between groups

To determine whether there is significant relationship between the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the level of schools' ethical climate Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was used. To determine whether there is significant relationship between the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the level of employees' morale Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was also used. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) is computed using the formula:

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \cdot \sum y}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

where:

n = number of pairs of scores

$\sum xy$ = sum of the products of paired scores

$\sum x$ = sum of x scores

$\sum y$ = sum of y scores

$\sum x^2$ = sum of squared x scores

$\sum y^2$ = sum of squared y scores

The guide for interpreting the correlation coefficient as presented by Punsalan and Uriarte (2000) were as follows:

± 1.00 to ± 0.90 Very High correlation; Very Significant relationship

± 0.89 to ± 0.60 High correlation; Significant relationship

± 0.59 to ± 0.40 Moderate correlation; Average relationship

± 0.39 to ± 0.20 Low correlation; Small relationship

± 0.19 and below Negligible; Almost no relationship

r has a t distribution with $n - 2$ degrees of freedom, and the test statistic is given by: $t =$

$$r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

RESULTS

TABLE 1
THE ADMINISTRATORS' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 1

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	26 – 30 years old	1	12.5	12.5
	31 – 35 years old	0	0.0	12.5
	36 – 40 years old	3	37.5	50.0
	41 – 45 years old	1	12.5	62.5
	46 – 50 years old	1	12.5	75.0
	51 – 55 years old	1	12.5	87.5
	56 – 60 years old	0	0.0	87.5
	61 years old or over	1	12.5	100.00
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
SEX	Male	1	12.5	12.5
	Female	7	87.5	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	2	25.0	28.6
	3 – 7 years	1	12.5	37.5
	8 – 12 years	1	12.5	50.0
	13 – 17 years	1	12.5	62.5
	18 – 22 years	1	12.5	75.0
	23 – 27 years	1	12.5	87.5
	28 years or over	1	12.5	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	1	12.5	12.5
	with Master's degree units	2	25.0	37.5
	with Master' degree	2	25.0	62.5
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	1	12.5	75.0
	with Doctorate degree	2	25.0	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
Seminars/Trainings Attended on Ethical Decision Making	Not Attended	3	37.5	37.5
	Attended	5	62.5	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	

Table 1 presents the administrators' profile of School 1. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

One (1), or 12.5% of the administrators is between 26 – 30 years old, no administrator is between 31 – 35 years old, three (3), or 37.5% of the administrators are between 36 – 40 years old, one (1) or 12.5% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 51 – 55 years old,

no administrator is between 56 – 60 years old, and one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is 61 years old or over.

One (1), or 12.5%, of the administrator is a male, and seven (7), or 87.5%, are females.

Two (2), or 25.0% of the administrators have less than 3 years of service, one (1), or 12.5% has between 3 – 7 years of service, one (1), or 12.5% has between 8 – 12 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 13 – 17 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and one (1) or 12.5% has 28 or over years of service.

One (1), or 12.5% of the administrators is a college graduate, two (2), or 25.0% of them have master’s degree units, two (2), or 25.0% have master’s degree, one (1) or 12.5% has doctorate units, and two (2) or 25.0% have a doctorate degree.

Three (3), or 42.9% of the administrators, have not attended seminars on ethical decision making, and four (4), or 57.1%, have attended seminars on ethical decision-making. This means that in Colegio de San Francisco Javier of Rizal Incorporated most administrators are females. Majority of them belong to the age group 36-40 who are middle aged adults. There is only one teacher who earned a doctoral degree. This implies that more women take part in ethical decision-making practices in the institution. The practice that more women are into public and private learning institutions is supported by Karadag & Bektas (2014) who found out that more female teachers work on private schools. They also show administrative skills.

TABLE 2
THE ADMINISTRATORS’ PROFILE OF SCHOOL 2

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	26 – 30 years old	0	0.0	0.0
	31 – 35 years old	1	12.5	12.5
	36 – 40 years old	1	12.5	25.0
	41 – 45 years old	0	0.0	25.0
	46 – 50 years old	2	25.0	50.0
	51 – 55 years old	1	12.5	62.5
	56 – 60 years old	0	0.0	62.5
	61 years old or over	3	37.5	100.00
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
SEX	Male	3	37.5	37.5
	Female	5	62.5	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	1	12.5	12.5
	3 – 7 years	1	12.5	25.0
	8 – 12 years	1	12.5	37.5
	13 – 17 years	0	0.0	37.5
	18 – 22 years	1	12.5	50.0
	23 – 27 years	1	12.5	62.5
	28 years or over	3	37.5	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
	College Graduate	2	25.0	25.0

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	with Master's degree units	3	37.5	62.5
	with Master' degree	3	37.5	100.0
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	0	0.0	100.0
	with Doctorate degree	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	
Seminars/Trainings Attended on Ethical Decision Making	Not Attended	6	75.0	75.0
	Attended	2	25.0	100.0
	TOTAL	8	100.0	

Table 2 presents the administrators' profile of School 2. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

No administrator is between 26 – 30 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 31 – 35 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 36 – 40 years old, no administrator is between 41 – 45 years old, two (2) or 25.0% of the administrators is between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 51 – 55 years old, no administrator is between 56 – 60 years old, and three (3) or 37.5% of the administrators are 61 years old or over.

Three (3), or 37.5% of the administrators are males, and five (5), or 62.5%, are females.

One (1) or 12.5% of the administrators has less than 3 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrator has between 3 – 7 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% of has between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator has between 13 – 17 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and three (3) or 37.5% have 28 or over years of service.

Two (2), or 25.0% of the administrators are college graduates; three (3), or 37.5% of them have master's degree units; three (3), or 37.5% have master's degree, no administrator has doctorate units, and no administrator has doctorate degree.

Six (6), or 75.0% of the administrators have not attended seminars on ethical decision making and two (2) or 25.0% have attended seminars on ethical decision-making.

Most administrators in Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan, Incorporated are females. Because of meager salaries and unattractive professional development program, administrators are not motivated to pursue postgraduate studies. Most of the administrators are not exposed to ethical decision-making seminar/conferences. The study of Murphy, Cross and Mcquire (2006) entitled, "*The motivation of nurses to participate in continuing professional education in Ireland*" highlighted lack of financial support and lack of recognition from employers are two professional barriers in the continuing professional education.

TABLE 3
THE ADMINISTRATORS' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 3

PROFILE	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
26 – 30 years old	0	0.0	0.0

AGE	31 – 35 years old	1	20.0	20.0
	36 – 40 years old	2	40.0	60.0
	41 – 45 years old	1	20.0	80.0
	46 – 50 years old	1	20.0	100.0
	51 – 55 years old	0	0.0	100.0
	56 – 60 years old	0	0.0	100.0
	61 years old or over	0	0.0	100.00
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
SEX	Male	3	60.0	60.0
	Female	2	40.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	0	0.0	0.0
	3 – 7 years	0	0.0	0.0
	8 – 12 years	3	60.0	60.0
	13 – 17 years	0	0.0	60.0
	18 – 22 years	0	0.0	60.0
	23 – 27 years	2	40.0	100.0
	28 years or over	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	0	0.0	0.0
	with Master's degree units	2	40.0	40.0
	with Master' degree	2	40.0	80.0
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	1	20.0	100.0
	with Doctorate degree	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
Seminars/Trainings Attended on Ethical Decision Making	Not Attended	4	80.0	80.0
	Attended	1	20.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	

Table 5 presents the administrators' profile of School 3. . The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

No administrator is below 31, one (1) or 20.0% of the administrator is between 31 - 35 years old, two (2) or 40.0% is between 36 – 40 years old and one (1) or 20.0% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 20.0% is between 46 – 50 years old and no administrator is above 50 years old.

Three (3), or 60.0% of the administrators are males and two (2) or 40.0% of are females.

Of the five administrators, three (3), or 60.0%, have between 8 – 12 years of service, and two (2), or 40.0%, have between 23 – 27 years of service.

No administrator is confined solely to the college graduate level, two (2) or 40.0% have master's degree units, two (2) or 40.0% have master's degree, one (1) or 20.0% has doctorate units, and no administrator has a doctorate degree.

Of the two administrators, four (4) or 80.0% have not attended seminars on ethical decision-making and one (1) or 20.0% has attended seminars on ethical decision-making. This means that even if the school has a small population, all respondents of San Estanislao Kostka,

Incorporated have earned units on postgraduate studies. This implies that the school head is very supportive to continuing professional development (CPD) to everyone (see Table 63).

TABLE 4
THE ADMINISTRATORS' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 4

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	26 – 30 years old	0	0.0	0.0
	31 – 35 years old	0	0.0	0.0
	36 – 40 years old	1	20.0	20.0
	41 – 45 years old	1	20.0	40.0
	46 – 50 years old	1	20.0	60.0
	51 – 55 years old	1	20.0	80.0
	56 – 60 years old	1	20.0	100.0
	61 years old or over	0	0.0	100.00
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
SEX	Male	5	100.0	100.0
	Female	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	0	0.0	0.0
	3 – 7 years	0	0.0	0.0
	8 – 12 years	2	40.0	40.0
	13 – 17 years	2	40.0	80.0
	18 – 22 years	0	0.0	80.0
	23 – 27 years	1	20.0	100.0
	28 years or over	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	0	0.0	0.0
	with Master's degree units	0	0.0	0.0
	with Master' degree	3	60.0	60.0
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	0	0.0	60.0
	with Doctorate degree	2	40.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	
Seminars/Trainings Attended on Ethical Decision Making	Not Attended	5	100.0	100.0
	Attended	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	5	100.0	

Table 5 presents the administrators' profile of School 4. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

No administrator is below 36 years old, one (1) or 20.0% of them is 36 – 40 years old, one (1) or 20% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 20.0% is between 46 – 50 years old and

one (1) or 20.0% is between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 20.0% is between 56 – 60 years old, and no administrator is 61 years old or above.

All administrators are males.

No administrator has less than 8 years of service, two (2) or 40.0% has between 8 – 12 years of service, two (2) or 40.0% has between 13 – 17 years of service, no administrator has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 20.0% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and no administrator has 28 or above years of service.

Three (3) or 60.0% of the administrators have a master’s degree, and two (2) or 40.0% have a doctorate degree.

No administrator has attended seminars on ethical decision making.

All respondents are men who have postgraduate degrees. They are not also exposed to seminars and conferences on ethical decision-making. There are few female administrators who were also absent when the questionnaire of this study was field. This means that majority of women do want to take leadership roles in most organizations. Janice Tucker (2013) supported this view in her article, “*Graduate Programs in Education: Impact on Teachers’ Careers*” stressing the fact that fewer women are in administrative positions. While not underestimating the leadership skills of women, the implication of this is that most of women think that leadership or administrative work is for men.

TABLE 5
THE ADMINISTRATORS’ PROFILE OF SCHOOL 5

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	26 – 30 years old	0	0.0	0.0
	31 – 35 years old	0	0.0	0.0
	36 – 40 years old	0	0.0	0.0
	41 – 45 years old	2	20.0	20.0
	46 – 50 years old	2	20.0	40.0
	51 – 55 years old	1	10.0	50.0
	56 – 60 years old	1	10.0	60.0
	61 years old or over	4	40.0	100.00
	TOTAL	10	100.0	
SEX	Male	7	70.0	70.0
	Female	3	30.0	100.0
	TOTAL	10	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	1	10.0	10.0
	3 – 7 years	2	20.0	30.0
	8 – 12 years	0	0.0	30.0
	13 – 17 years	0	0.0	30.0
	18 – 22 years	0	0.0	30.0
	23 – 27 years	1	10.0	40.0
	28 years or over	6	60.0	100.0
	TOTAL	10	100.0	
	College Graduate	0	0.0	0.0
	with Master’s degree units	1	10.0	10.0
	with Master’ degree	3	30.0	40.0

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	4	40.0	80.0
	with Doctorate degree	2	20.0	100.0
	TOTAL	10	100.0	
Seminars/Trainings Attended on Ethical Decision Making	Not Attended	4	40.0	40.0
	Attended	6	60.0	100.0
	TOTAL	10	100.0	

Table 5 presents the administrators' profile of School 5. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

No administrator is between 26 – 30 years old, no administrator is between 31 – 35 years old, no administrator is between 36 – 40 years old, two (2) or 20.0% of the administrators are between 41 – 45 years old, two (2) or 20.0% of them are between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 10.0% is between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 10.0% is between 56 – 60 years old, and four (4) or 40.0% are 61 years old or over.

Seven (7) or 70.0% of the administrators are males and three (3) or 30.0% of them are females.

One (1) or 10.0% of the administrators has less than 3 years of service, two (2) or 20.0% of the administrator have between 3 – 7 years of service, no administrator has between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator has between 13 – 17 years of service, no administrator has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 10.0% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and six (6) or 60.0% have 28 or over years of service.

No administrator is a college graduate, one (1) or 10.0% of them has master's degree units, three (3) or 30.0% have master's degree, four (4) or 40.0% of the administrators have doctorate units, and two (2) or 20.0% of the administrators have doctorate degree.

Four (4) or 40.0% of the administrators have not attended seminars on ethical decision making and six (6) or 60.0% have attended seminars on ethical decision making. This means that all administrators have postgraduate degrees and majority of them are exposed to seminars and conferences on ethical decision making. Notice that most administrators are employed more than 28 years in service. It only goes to show that there is job satisfaction and good working environment. This is supported by the study of Flowers & Hughes (1973) that when asked, "Why do employees stay?" There are two reasons. First, because of job satisfaction, which includes achievement, recognition, responsibility, growth, and second, the company environment or the degree of comfort an individual employee feels within it. The latter includes work rules, facilities, benefits and wages.

TABLE 6
THE EMPLOYEES' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 1

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	21 – 25 years old	5	25.0	25.0
	26 – 30 years old	7	35.0	60.0
	31 – 35 years old	3	15.0	75.0
	36 – 40 years old	2	10.0	85.0
	41 – 45 years old	1	5.0	90.0

	46 – 50 years old	1	5.0	95.0
	51 – 55 years old	0	0.0	95.0
	56 – 60 years old	1	5.0	100.0
	61 years old or over	0	0.0	100.00
	TOTAL	20	100.0	
SEX	Male	6	30.0	30.0
	Female	14	70.0	100.0
	TOTAL	20	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	5	25.0	25.0
	3 – 7 years	11	55.0	80.0
	8 – 12 years	1	5.0	85.0
	13 – 17 years	2	10.0	95.0
	18 – 22 years	1	5.0	100.0
	23 – 27 years	0	0.0	100.0
	28 years or over	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	20	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	13	65.0	65.0
	with Master’s degree units	6	30.0	95.0
	with Master’ degree	1	5.0	100.0
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	0	0.0	100.0
	with Doctorate degree	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	20	100.0	

Table 6 presents the employees’ profile of School 1. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

Five (5) or 25.0% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, seven (7) or 37.5% are between 26 – 30 years old, three (3) or 15.0% are between 31 – 35 years old, two (2) or 10.0% are between 36 – 40 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 46 – 50 years old, no employee is between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 56 – 60 years old, and no employee is 61 years old or over.

Six (6) or 30.0% of the employees are males and fourteen (14) or 70.0% are females.

Five (5) or 25.0% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, eleven (11) or 55.0% have between 3 – 7 years of service, one (1) or 5.0% has between 8 – 12 years of service, two (2) or 10.0% have between 13 – 17 years of service, one (1) or 5.0% has between 18 – 22 years of service, no employee has between 23 – 27 years of service, and no employee has 28 or over years of service.

Thirteen (13) or 65.0% of the employees are college graduate, six (6) or 30.0% of them have master’s degree units, one (1) or 5.0% has master’s degree, no employee has doctorate units, and no employee has a doctorate degree. With regard to the length of service, majority of the employees will stay in the organization not more than seven years due to the fact that the compensation of the school is smaller compared to teachers employed in public schools. Remember, there is the “grass is greener syndrome” where most people opt to find an organization that gives enough compensation. David Witt (2012), in his online article entitled, “*Top five reasons why employees join and stay with organizations*” found out that number the one reason why employees remain in the organization is base pay / salary (www.leaderchat.org).

In Dana Wilkie (2018) supported this claim by saying that salary is the biggest reason why employees change jobs (www.shrm.org).

TABLE 7
THE EMPLOYEES' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 2

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	21 – 25 years old	11	31.4	31.4
	26 – 30 years old	6	17.1	48.6
	31 – 35 years old	4	11.4	60.0
	36 – 40 years old	2	5.7	65.7
	41 – 45 years old	2	5.7	71.4
	46 – 50 years old	1	2.9	74.3
	51 – 55 years old	6	17.1	91.4
	56 – 60 years old	2	5.7	97.1
	61 years old or over	1	2.9	100.00
	TOTAL	35	100.0	
SEX	Male	15	42.9	42.9
	Female	20	57.1	100.0
	TOTAL	35	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	14	40.0	40.0
	3 – 7 years	7	20.0	60.0
	8 – 12 years	3	8.6	68.6
	13 – 17 years	4	11.4	80.0
	18 – 22 years	2	5.7	85.7
	23 – 27 years	5	14.3	100.0
	28 years or over	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	35	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	24	68.6	68.6
	with Master's degree units	9	25.7	94.3
	with Master' degree	1	2.9	97.1
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	0	0.0	97.1
	with Doctorate degree	1	2.9	100.0
	TOTAL	35	100.0	

Table 7 presents the employees' profile of School 2. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

Eleven (11) or 31.4% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, six (6) or 17.1% are between 26 – 30 years old, four (4) or 11.4% are between 31 – 35 years old, two (2) or 5.7% are between 36 – 40 years old, two (2) or 5.7% are between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 46 – 50 years old, six (6) or 17.1% are between 51 – 55 years old, two (2) or 5.7% are between 56 – 60 years old, and one (1) or 2.9% is 61 years old or over.

Fifteen (15) or 42.9% of the employees are males and twenty (20) or 57.1% are females.

Fourteen (14) or 40.0% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, seven (7) or 20.0% have between 3 – 7 years of service, three (3) or 8.6% have between 8 – 12 years of service, four (4) or 11.4% have between 13 – 17 years of service, two (2) or 5.7% have between 18 – 22 years of service, five (5) or 14.3% are between 23 – 27 years of service, and no employee has 28 or over years of service.

Twenty-four (24) or 68.6% of the employees are college graduate, nine (9) or 25.7% of them have master’s degree units, one (1) or 2.9% has master’s degree, no employee has doctorate units, and one (1) or 2.9% has a doctorate degree.

This means that most of the employees are female and young professionals who are employed less than three years. While one employee has earned doctoral units, the individual was not given administrative functions in the organization. This is because it is non-sequitur that just because one has postdoctoral degree, he/she will automatically be given administrative functions. There are those who pursue postgraduate studies for purely love of learning or to increase their salary. The study of Thomson (2009) found teachers undertake graduate programs for different reasons, primarily to become a better educator and to receive a salary increase. He added that those who acquire the qualifications needed for leadership positions may not choose to advance into available positions.

TABLE 8
THE EMPLOYEES’ PROFILE OF SCHOOL 3

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	21 – 25 years old	6	26.1	26.1
	26 – 30 years old	3	13.0	39.1
	31 – 35 years old	1	4.3	43.5
	36 – 40 years old	5	21.7	65.2
	41 – 45 years old	4	17.4	82.6
	46 – 50 years old	0	0.0	82.6
	51 – 55 years old	1	4.3	87.0
	56 – 60 years old	1	4.3	91.3
	61 years old or over	2	8.7	100.00
TOTAL		23	100.0	
SEX	Male	8	34.8	34.8
	Female	15	65.2	100.0
	TOTAL		23	100.0
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	6	26.1	26.1
	3 – 7 years	11	47.8	73.9
	8 – 12 years	4	17.4	91.3
	13 – 17 years	0	0.0	91.3
	18 – 22 years	0	0.0	91.3
	23 – 27 years	2	8.7	100.0
	28 years or over	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL		23	100.0
	College Graduate	12	52.2	52.2
	with Master’s degree units	7	30.4	82.6

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	with Master' degree	4	17.4	100.0
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	0	0.0	100.0
	with Doctorate degree	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	23	100.0	

Table 8 presents the employees' profile of School 3. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

Six (6) or 26.1% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, three (3) or 13.0% are between 26 – 30 years old, one (1) or 4.3% are between 31 – 35 years old, five (5) or 21.7% are between 36 – 40 years old, four (4) or 17.4% are between 41 – 45 years old, no administrator is between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 4.3% are between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 4.3% are between 56 – 60 years old, and two (2) or 8.7% is 61 years old or over.

Eight (8) or 34.8% of the employees are males and fifteen (15) or 65.2% are females.

Six (6) or 26.1% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, eleven (11) or 47.8% have between 3 – 7 years of service, four (4) or 17.4% have between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator is between 13 – 22 years of service, two (2) or 8.7% are between 23 – 27 years of service, and no employee has 28 or over years of service.

Twelve (12) or 52.2% of the employees are college graduate, seven (7) or 30.4% of them have master's degree units, four (4) or 17.4% has master's degree, no employee has doctorate units, and no employee has a doctorate degree.

This means that majority of the respondents are college graduates and are employed not more than seven years. This is because of the "the grass is greener syndrome" where people will choose to stay to an organization who can give them greater benefits and compensation. Most employees will transfer to public because of sufficient compensation and good security benefits. This claim is supported by Alex Gray (2017) who found that employees nearly always moved to an employer with better ratings in six measures of company culture: overall rating; career opportunities; compensation and benefits; culture and values; work-life balance; and quality of senior management.

TABLE 9
THE EMPLOYEES' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 4

PROFILE		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
AGE	21 – 25 years old	15	44.1	44.1
	26 – 30 years old	10	29.4	73.5
	31 – 35 years old	2	5.9	79.4
	36 – 40 years old	2	5.9	85.3
	41 – 45 years old	3	8.8	94.1
	46 – 50 years old	2	5.9	100.00
	51 – 55 years old	0	0.0	100.00
	56 – 60 years old	0	0.0	100.00
	61 years old or over	0	0.0	100.00
TOTAL		34	100.0	
SEX	Male	11	32.4	32.4
	Female	23	67.6	100.0

	TOTAL	34	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	11	32.4	32.4
	3 – 7 years	17	50.0	82.4
	8 – 12 years	3	8.8	91.2
	13 – 17 years	0	0.0	91.2
	18 – 22 years	3	8.8	100.0
	23 – 27 years	0	0.0	100.0
	28 years or over	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	34	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	11	32.4	32.4
	with Master's degree units	13	38.2	70.6
	with Master' degree	9	26.5	97.1
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	1	2.9	100.0
	with Doctorate degree	0	0.0	100.0
	TOTAL	34	100.0	

Table 9 shows the employees' profile of School 4. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

Fifteen (15), or 44.1% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, ten (10) or 29.4% are between 26 – 30 years old, two (2) or 5.9% are between 31 – 35 years old, two (2) or 5.9% are between 36 – 40 years old, three (3) or 8.8% are between 41 – 45 years old, two (2) or 5.9% are between 46 – 50 years old, and no administrator has 51 years old or over.

Eleven (11), or 32.4% of the employees are males and twenty-three (23) or 67.6% are females.

Eleven (11) or 32.4% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, seventeen (17) or 50.0% have between 3 – 7 years of service, three (3) or 8.8% have between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator have between 13 – 17 years of service, three (3) or 8.8% have between 18 – 22 years of service, and no employee has 23 or over years of service.

Eleven (11) or 32.4% of the employees are college graduate, thirteen (13) or 38.2% of them have master's degree units, nine (9) or 26.5% has master's degree, one (1) or 2.9% has employee has doctorate units, and no employee has a doctorate degree.

Female employees outnumber the male employees due to fact the women love teaching more than men. Carolyn Basten (2006) considered teaching as a 'feminised profession' because of the remarkable number of female educators in Germany. Most respondents are into postgraduate studies. It implies two things, one, that the administrators motivate their teachers for further studies; second, the school has good professional development program.

TABLE 10
THE EMPLOYEES' PROFILE OF SCHOOL 5

PROFILE	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
21 – 25 years old	27	28.7	28.7
26 – 30 years old	14	14.9	43.6
31 – 35 years old	7	7.4	51.1

AGE	36 – 40 years old	7	7.4	58.5
	41 – 45 years old	11	11.7	70.2
	46 – 50 years old	12	12.8	83.0
	51 – 55 years old	7	7.4	90.4
	56 – 60 years old	5	5.3	95.7
	61 years old or over	4	4.3	100.00
	TOTAL	94	100.0	
SEX	Male	38	40.4	40.4
	Female	56	59.6	100.0
	TOTAL	94	100.0	
LENGTH OF SERVICE	Less than 3 years	25	26.6	26.6
	3 – 7 years	25	26.6	53.2
	8 – 12 years	15	16.0	69.1
	13 – 17 years	4	4.3	73.4
	18 – 22 years	9	9.6	83.0
	23 – 27 years	6	6.4	89.4
	28 years or over	10	10.6	100.0
	TOTAL	94	100.0	
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	College Graduate	27	28.7	28.7
	with Master's degree units	24	25.5	54.3
	with Master' degree	37	39.4	93.6
	with Ph. D or any Doctorate units	5	5.3	98.9
	with Doctorate degree	1	1.1	100.0
	TOTAL	94	100.0	

Table 10 presents the administrators' profile of School 5. The table shows the profile, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage.

Twenty seven (27) or 28.7% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, fourteen (14) or 14.9% are between 26 – 30 years old, seven (7) or 7.4% are between 31 – 35 years old, seven (7) or 7.4% are between 36 – 40 years old, eleven (11) or 11.7% are between 41 – 45 years old, twelve (12) or 12.8% are between 46 – 50 years old, seven (7) or 7.4% are between 51 – 55 years old, five (5) or 5.3% are between 56 – 60 years old, and four (4) or 4.3% is 61 years old or over.

Thirty-eight (38) or 40.4% of the employees are males and fifty-six (56) or 59.6% are females.

Twenty five (25) or 26.6% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, twenty five (25) or 26.6% have between 3 – 7 years of service, fifteen (15) or 16.0% have between 8 – 12 years of service, four (4) or 4.3% have between 13 – 17 years of service, nine (9) or 9.6% have between 18 – 22 years of service, six (6) or 6.4% are between 23 – 27 years of service, and ten (10) or 10.6% have 28 or over years of service.

Twenty-seven (27) or 28.7% of the employees are college graduate, twenty-four (24) or 25.5% of them have master's degree units, thirty-seven (37) or 39.4% have master's degree, five (5) or 5.3% have doctorate units, and one (1) or 1.1% has a doctorate degree.

The school has many employees who belong to different age brackets. It implies that employees choose to stay because they are comfortable with the culture, compensation, and the administration of the organization. Gareis & Strong (2003) explained that school leaders

should develop teacher compensation packages that demonstrate that they are valued. Based on data on the area of educational attainment majority of the employees have postgraduate degrees because of the supportive administrators and the organizations' reasonable financial support to continuing professional development (CPD) program. Bubb and Earley (2009) found that when staff (or teachers) felt valued by encouraging for professional growth, they went the extra mile as a result.

TABLE 11
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG
EGOISM OF SCHOOL 1

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. People should protect their own interest above other considerations.	Moderately Agree	6.14	U
2. People should do well in the organization for rewards.	Slightly Agree	4.71	O
3. All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits.	Slightly Agree	4.61	O
4. Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company.	Slightly Agree	4.96	S
5. People should not perform any act that would result to punishments.	Largely Agree	6.93	AA
6. People should work for the success of the company.	Largely Agree	7.04	AA
Grand Weighted Mean	Moderately Agree	5.73	U

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AA)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (A)

Table 11 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced the ethical position that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits". The administrators sometimes practiced that "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". In some organizations, Jenkins & Delbridge (2017) believe that 'strategic deception' is acceptable in the organization. There is also what we call 'constructive lying' which is inevitable feature required to sustain the social order (Goffman, 1957). However, the administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments" and "People should work for the success of the company". While punishment is considered as disciplinary action to erring employees, it will also have negative effect to the organization. Iheanacho, Edema & Ekpe (2016) support this view who found that the more

punishment is meted on workers, the less they tend to perform on their assignment in the organization. Joe, Richard & Sanford (2011) who conducted a study on the organization of discipline found out that punishment relates negatively with performance. Marquis de Sade (1814) said that penalty is more motivating than rewards.

The grand weighted mean of 5.73 tells us that the administrators of Colegio de San Francisco Javier of Rizal, Incorporated usually practiced getting the people in the organization to consider company interest or success over self-interest. It means that, as part of their ethical decision-making practices, administrators or heads of offices motivate their teachers and staffs in achieving organization goals. Ontolan and Redondo (2015) found that when workers are motivated in an organization, their productivity raises and therefore the organization realizes various advantages associated with the rise in labor productivity.

TABLE 12
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG BENEVOLENCE OF SCHOOL 1.

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization.	Largely Agree	6.43	AAP
2. One should never psychologically or physically harm another person.	Largely Agree	6.82	AAP
3. One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual.	Moderately Agree	5.86	U
4. People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all.	Moderately Agree	5.82	U
5. You help others without seeking a reward or recognition.	Largely Agree	6.82	AAP
6. One considers people in their decision-making practices.	Moderately Agree	6.00	U
Grand Weighted Mean	Moderately Agree	6.29	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 12 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along benevolence of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators almost always practiced that “The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization”, “One should never psychologically or physically harm another person”, and “to help others without seeking a reward or recognition.”

The administrators usually practiced that “One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual,” “People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all”, and “One considers people in their decision-making practices.”

The grand weighted mean of 6.29 tells us that the administrators of Colegio de San Francisco Javier of Rizal Incorporated almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. Ghosh (2013) found that people holding leadership positions in the top and senior management team are expected to exhibit adequate proclivity towards ethics, quality of life, compassion, fellow feeling, and community welfare for people inside and outside the organization. In a benevolent atmosphere, individuals perceive that decisions are and should be based on an overarching concern for the well-being of others (Martin & Cullen, 2006). Koo & Boo (2004) found that when top management proactively focuses on these variables, they can “enhance job satisfaction and organizational commitment... by promoting and developing a more benevolent ethical climate.”

TABLE 13
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG PRINCIPLE OF SCHOOL 1

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community.	Largely Agree	6.64	AAP
2. Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization.	Largely Agree	7.04	AAP
3. In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness.	Moderately Agree	5.79	U
4. Employees should strictly obey company policies.	Largely Agree	6.79	AAP
5. Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules.	Largely Agree	6.82	AAP
6. Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization.	Largely Agree	6.89	AAP
7. Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees.	Largely Agree	6.64	AAP
8. Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines.	Largely Agree	6.71	AAP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.67	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 13 presents the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices along principle of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that “In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness”. The administrators almost always practiced that “Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community”, “Employees should strictly obey company policies”, “Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules”, “Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization”, “Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees”, and “Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines”. The highest among them is which 7.04 weighted mean is “Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization.” An administrator who is familiar to the policies of the organization works efficiently. Robert L. Katz (2009) believed that a good administrator should possess conceptual skill that includes recognizing how the various functions of the organization depend on one another, and how changes in any one part affect all the others. If the administrator knows the organizational policies, then his/her employees will be encouraged to do the same. It is called role modelling. Brown & Treviño (2014) supported the idea that role modeling is related to ethical leaders. So, when administrators are faithful in the implementation of organizational policies and guidelines, employees will be challenged to familiarize organizational policies.

The grand weighted mean of 6.67 tells us that the administrators of School 1 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

TABLE 14
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 1

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
EGOISM	5.73	Usually Practiced
BENEVOLENCE.	6.29	Almost Always Practiced
PRINCIPLE	6.67	Almost Always Practiced
Average Grand Weighted Mean	6.23	Usually Practiced

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 14 presents the summary of the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 1. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators of School 1 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.73 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.29 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.67 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 1 is principle. This means that the administrators of this school follow processes and procedures in their decision-making.

The average grand weighted mean 6.23 tells us that level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 1 is "usually practiced".

The implication of this is that administrators are bureaucratic, that is, going by the book, with regard to the day-to-day operations of the school. According to Crystal Lombardo, principle ethical climate or bureaucratic style of management, "makes it easy for new leaders to fit right into the company structure because they will be just following organizational policies and guidelines. Team members can identify their roles and meet expectations right away." She added that when there is familiarity, there is confidence, and that can lead toward higher productivity levels. According to Victor & Cullen (1988) with a largely principled climate, the application and interpretation of rules or law might be the dominant form of reasoning.

TABLE 15
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG
EGOISM OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. People should protect their own interest above other considerations.	Slightly Agree	5.09	O
2. People should do well in the organization for rewards.	Slightly Agree	4.84	O
3. All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits.	Moderately Agree	5.40	U
4. Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company.	Slightly Agree	4.60	O
5. People should not perform any act that would result to punishments.	Largely Agree	6.49	AAP
6. People should work for the success of the company.	Largely Agree	7.12	AAP
Grand Weighted Mean	Moderately Agree	5.59	U

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 15 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators often practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations", "People should do well in the organization for rewards", and "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators usually practiced that "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits." However, the administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments" and People should work for the success of the company" which has the highest weighted mean of 7.12.

The grand weighted mean of 5.59 tells us that the administrators of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan, Incorporated usually practiced getting the people in the organization to work for the company interest. This finding is supported by the article entitled, “*Importance of Employee Performance in Business Organizations*” by Kimberly Leonard (2019) who stressed that business owners need employees that can get the job done, because employee performance is critical to the overall success of the company. Thus, administrators must be decisive in hiring employees that are goal-oriented. Kohlberg (1817) considered this ethical criterion in the pre-conventional level that is the morality of instrumental egoism and simple exchange; let's make a deal.

TABLE 16
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG BENEVOLENCE OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization.	Largely Agree	6.51	AAP
2. One should never psychologically or physically harm another person.	Largely Agree	6.51	AAP
3. One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual.	Moderately Agree	5.95	U
4. People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all.	Largely Agree	6.30	AAP
5. You help others without seeking a reward or recognition.	Completely Agree	7.05	AAP
6. One considers people in their decision-making practices.	Completely Agree	6.95	AAP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.54	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 16 presents the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices along benevolence of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators almost always practiced that “The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization”, “One should never psychologically or physically harm another person”, “People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all”, “to help others without seeking a reward or recognition”, and “One considers people in their decision-making practices.”

The administrators usually practiced that “One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual”.

The grand weighted mean of 6.54 tells us that the administrators of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. This finding is supported by the study entitled, “*The Organizational Bases of Ethical Work Climates in Lodging Operations as Perceived by General Managers*” by Upchurch & Ruhland (1996) who found that among the three ethical criteria used in lodging houses, benevolence is the predominant ethical climate type utilized in applying ethical decisions as perceived by property general managers. Kohlberg (1817) considered this ethical criterion in the conventional level where it focuses on the morality of concordance; be considerate, nice, and kind; you’ll make friends.

TABLE 17
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG PRINCIPLE OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community.	Largely Agree	7.09	AAP
2. Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization.	Largely Agree	6.98	AAP
3. In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness.	Moderately Agree	6.16	U
4. Employees should strictly obey company policies.	Largely Agree	6.88	AAP
5. Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules.	Largely Agree	6.79	AAP
6. Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization.	Completely Agree	7.33	AP
7. Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees.	Largely Agree	7.12	AAP
8. Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines.	Completely Agree	7.14	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.94	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 17 presents the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices along principle of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that “In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness”. The administrators almost always practiced that “Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community,” “Everyone

should familiarize all the policies of the organization,” “Employees should strictly obey company policies”, “Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules”, and “Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees”. The administrators always practiced that “Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization”, and “Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines”.

The grand weighted mean of 6.94 tells us that the administrators of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle. Principle ethical criterion centers on administrators as good rule-followers who lead by example. This finding is supported by an article entitled, “*Principals Need to be Good Followers*,” by Richard Smith (1991) who found that, in the case of principals, to be an effective leader, the principal must also be an effective follower. He writes, “it makes sense that the degree to which principals are effective followers influences the effectiveness of their leaders.” Thus, there is efficient and smooth school operation if administrators are consistent in following organizational policies and procedures. Kohlberg (1981) considered this ethical criterion on the post-conventional level where the morality of consensus-building procedures is emphasized.

TABLE 18
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 2

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
EGOISM	5.59	Usually Practiced
BENEVOLENCE.	6.54	Almost Always Practiced
PRINCIPLE	6.94	Almost Always Practiced
Average Grand Weighted Mean	6.36	Almost Always Practiced

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N) | 4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O) |
| 1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V) | 5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U) |
| 2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R) | 6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP) |
| 3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S) | 7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP) |

Table 18 summarizes the administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 2. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators of School 2 used mixed practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.59, meaning they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.54, meaning they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.94, meaning they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated administrators is principle. This finding is supported by the study entitled “The Effects of Ethical Climates on Organizational Commitment: A Two-Study Analysis” by Cullen, Parboteeah & Victor (2003), who established that the decision-makers generally resort to principles that are based on adherence to rules and codes.

The average grand weighted mean 6.36 tells us that level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 2 is "almost always practiced".

TABLE 19
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG
EGOISM OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. People should protect their own interest above other considerations.	Moderately Agree	5.40	U
2. People should do well in the organization for rewards.	Slightly Agree	4.92	O
3. All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits.	Slightly Agree	4.52	O
4. Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company.	Slightly Disagree	4.36	S
5. People should not perform any act that would result to punishments.	Largely Agree	7.00	AAP
6. People should work for the success of the company.	Completely Agree	7.48	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Moderately Agree	5.61	U

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 19 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits." The administrators sometimes practiced that "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments". The administrators also always practiced that "People should work for the success of the company".

The grand weighted mean of 5.61 tells us that the administrators of San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the company. This finding is supported by the study entitled, "Are Your Employees Putting the Company's Interests First?" by Neubaum, Thomas & Dibrell (2017) who asserted that leaders should put the interests of their firms above their own—such is a tenant of "stewardship theory. In the study entitled, "Importance of Employee

Performance in Business Organizations” by Kimberly Leonard (2019) stated that one of the most important factors in employee performance is to achieve goals.

TABLE 20
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG BENEVOLENCE OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization.	Completely Agree	7.44	AP
2. One should never psychologically or physically harm another person.	Largely Agree	6.96	AAP
3. One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual.	Largely Agree	6.32	AAP
4. People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all.	Largely Agree	6.44	AAP
5. You help others without seeking a reward or recognition.	Completely Agree	7.60	AP
6. One considers people in their decision-making practices.	Completely Agree	7.16	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.99	AAP

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N) | 4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O) |
| 1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V) | 5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U) |
| 2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R) | 6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP) |
| 3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S) | 7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP) |

Table 20 presents the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices along benevolence of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators almost always practiced that “One should never psychologically or physically harm another person”, “People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all”, and “One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual”.

The administrators always practiced that “The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization”, “to help others without seeking a reward or recognition”, and “One considers people in their decision-making practices.”

The grand weighted mean of 6.99 tells us that the administrators of Saint Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence

TABLE 21
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG
PRINCIPLE OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community.	Completely Agree	7.36	AP
2. Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization.	Completely Agree	7.44	AP
3. In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness.	Moderately Agree	5.40	U
4. Employees should strictly obey company policies.	Largely Agree	6.60	AAP
5. Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules.	Largely Agree	6.40	AAP
6. Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization.	Largely Agree	7.00	AAP
7. Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees.	Completely Agree	7.24	AP
8. Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines.	Completely Agree	7.16	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.82	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 21 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along principle of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that "In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness". The administrators almost always practiced that "Employees should strictly obey company policies", "Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules", and "Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization". The administrators always practiced that "Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community", "Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization", "Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees", and "Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines".

The grand weighted mean of 6.82 tells us that the administrators of School 3 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

TABLE 22
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 3

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
EGOISM	5.61	Usually Practiced
BENEVOLENCE.	6.99	Almost Always Practiced
PRINCIPLE	6.82	Almost Always Practiced
Average Grand Weighted Mean	6.47	Almost Always Practiced

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 22 presents the summary of the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 3. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators of School 3 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.61 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.99 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.82 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.47 tells us that level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 3 is "almost always practiced".

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 3 is benevolence. In a benevolent climate, leaders always consider the good of the employees in their ethical decision-making. When one is valued and given importance, he/she will be more committed to the organization he/she is working for. Meyer and Allen (1991) found that "the perception of being valued and cared about by their managers may encourage employees' positive identification and membership with the organization, which in turn strengthens their affective commitment to the organization." In his study on what ethical climate is frequently perceived in lodging houses, Randall Upchurch (1998) found that "benevolence was the most frequently perceived ethical precept present in lodging properties." This implies that the administrators valued their employees, that even if the financial compensation that the latter is receiving is less compared to public school teachers, they choose to remain in the organization.

TABLE 23**THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG EGOISM OF SCHOOL 4**

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. People should protect their own interest above other considerations.	Moderately Agree	5.49	U
2. People should do well in the organization for rewards.	Slightly Agree	5.08	O
3. All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits.	Slightly Agree	4.95	O
4. Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company.	Slightly Disagree	4.19	S
5. People should not perform any act that would result to punishments.	Largely Agree	7.00	AAP
6. People should work for the success of the company.	Completely Agree	7.46	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Moderately Agree	5.70	U

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 23 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits." The administrators sometimes practiced that "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments". The administrators also always practiced that "People should work for the success of the company has 7.46 weighted mean, the highest in the scale level." This means that the administrators are consistent in encouraging and inspiring their employees to work for the success of the company. This finding is supported by the study of Stogdill (1974) who showed that "leaders have a strong drive for responsibility and task completion, usually are vigorous and persistent in the pursuit of goals."

The grand weighted mean of 5.70 tells us that the administrators of School 4 usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the school. This finding explains the motivation of administrators to their employees to contribute for the good of the organization even if it stresses going an extra mile.

TABLE 24**THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG BENEVOLENCE OF SCHOOL 4**

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization.	Completely Agree	7.27	AP
2. One should never psychologically or physically harm another person.	Completely Agree	7.30	AP
3. One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual.	Largely Agree	6.97	AAP
4. People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all.	Moderately Agree	6.16	U
5. You help others without seeking a reward or recognition.	Completely Agree	7.35	AP
6. One considers people in their decision-making practices.	Largely Agree	7.11	AAP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	7.03	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 24 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along benevolence of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators always practiced that "The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization", "One should never psychologically or physically harm another person", and "to help others without seeking a reward or recognition".

The administrators almost always practiced that "One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual". The administrators also usually practiced "People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all".

The grand weighted mean of 7.03 tells us that the administrators of School 4 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. This finding is supported by Erkutlu and Chafra (2016) who found that "employees' well-being and satisfaction, service quality and customer satisfaction, and high quality hospitality experiences are relevant constructs, all of them related to the understanding of the role leaders are to perform in competitive organizations." When employees felt valued and cared properly by the organizations they will also respond positively.

TABLE 25
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG
PRINCIPLE OF SCHOOL 4

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community.	Completely Agree	7.16	AP
2. Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization.	Completely Agree	7.38	AP
3. In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness.	Moderately Agree	5.86	U
4. Employees should strictly obey company policies.	Largely Agree	7.00	AAP
5. Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules.	Largely Agree	6.62	AAP
6. Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization.	Largely Agree	7.03	AAP
7. Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees.	Largely Agree	6.68	AAP
8. Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines.	Completely Agree	7.27	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.88	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 25 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along principle of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that "In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness". The administrators almost always practiced that "Employees should strictly obey company policies", "Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules", "Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization", and "Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees". The administrators always practiced that "Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community", "Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization", and "Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines".

The grand weighted mean of 6.88 tells us that the administrators of School 4 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

TABLE 26
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 4

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
EGOISM	5.70	Usually Practiced
BENEVOLENCE.	7.03	Almost Always Practiced
PRINCIPLE	6.88	Almost Always Practiced
Average Grand Weighted Mean	6.54	Almost Always Practiced

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 26 presents the summary of the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 4. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators of School 4 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.70 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 7.03 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.88 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.54 tells us that level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 4 is "almost always practiced".

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 4 is benevolence. Administrators of any religious institutions are expected to live out the values of Jesus Christ especially his 'others-centered' attitude or benevolence. So it only goes to show that the school administrators are faithful to the school's identity as a Christian educational institution. Moreover, when employees observe benevolent leadership behaviors at work, they become more inclined toward replicating these behaviors, such as spending extra effort to help colleagues or contribute to the common good (Cameron, Bright & Caza, 2004). Simha and Cullen (2012) supports the finding as the put it, "organizations with somewhat humanistic mission will be likely to harbor benevolent climates."

TABLE 27**THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG EGOISM OF SCHOOL 5**

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. People should protect their own interest above other considerations.	Moderately Agree	5.52	U
2. People should do well in the organization for rewards.	Slightly Agree	4.94	O
3. All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits.	Slightly Agree	4.73	O
4. Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company.	Slightly Agree	4.71	O
5. People should not perform any act that would result to punishments.	Largely Agree	6.91	AAP
6. People should work for the success of the company.	Completely Agree	7.57	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Moderately Agree	5.73	U

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 27 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits", and "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments". The administrators also always practiced that "People should work for the success of the company" since it has the highest level in the table. This means that the administrators are consistent in inspiring their employees, teachers and staff about dedication to work for the success of the organization.

The grand weighted mean of 5.73 tells us that the administrators of St. Vincent's College Incorporated usually egoism, which is beneficial to the organization. While administrators focused on company profit or success of the organization, Victor and Cullen (1987, 1988) clarified that egoism could also mean encouraging individuals to be motivated by personal gains. Egoistic climate is very applicable to countries who favor individualism just like the U.S. Mostly, organizations in countries that are high on individualism are more likely to exhibit egoistic ethical climate, because the latter reflects the ultimate concern for the self (Parboteeh, Cullen, Victor & Sakano, 2005).

TABLE 28**THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG BENEVOLENCE OF SCHOOL 5**

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization.	Largely Agree	7.03	AAP
2. One should never psychologically or physically harm another person.	Completely Agree	7.29	AP
3. One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual.	Largely Agree	6.75	AAP
4. People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all.	Largely Agree	6.42	AAP
5. You help others without seeking a reward or recognition.	Completely Agree	7.26	AP
6. One considers people in their decision-making practices.	Largely Agree	7.08	AAP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	6.97	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 28 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along benevolence of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators almost always practiced that "The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization", "One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual", "People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all", and "One considers people in their decision-making practices". The administrators always practiced that "One should never psychologically or physically harm another person", and "to help others without seeking a reward or recognition".

The grand weighted mean of 6.97 tells us that the administrators of School 5 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. Administrators of religious institutions should have competence and Christian character possessing the values of Jesus Christ which is to care for others' benefit. The finding of the study supports the mandate of the sacred congregation for Catholic education that states, "Lay Catholic educators in schools, whether teachers, directors, administrators, or auxiliary staff are entrusted with the task of gradually bringing about an integration of temporal reality with the Gospel, so that the Gospel can thus reach into the lives of all men and women" (Sacred Congregation for Catholic Education, par. 81).

TABLE 29
THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES ALONG
PRINCIPLE OF SCHOOL 5

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community.	Completely Agree	7.23	AP
2. Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization.	Completely Agree	7.40	AP
3. In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness.	Moderately Agree	6.15	O
4. Employees should strictly obey company policies.	Completely Agree	7.32	AP
5. Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules.	Largely Agree	6.86	AAP
6. Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization.	Completely Agree	7.40	AP
7. Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees.	Completely Agree	7.13	AP
8. Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines.	Completely Agree	7.35	AP
Grand Weighted Mean	Largely Agree	7.10	AAP

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)

1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)

2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)

3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)

4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)

5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)

6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)

7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 29 presents the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices along principle of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators often practiced that "In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness." The administrators almost always practiced that "Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules." The administrators always practiced that "Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community," "Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization," "Employees should strictly obey company policies," "Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization," "Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees," and "Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines."

The grand weighted mean of 7.10 tells us that the administrators of St. Vincent's College Incorporated almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle. The two highest scale levels emphasize organizational policies, that administrators are familiar with the policies and their ethical decision-making is based on the policies and guidelines set by the organization. But Martin and Cullen (2006) found that organizations needing to adhere to a visible code of conduct and rules (such as engineering, accounting, and law firms) are more likely to have principled climates (either rules or law and code).

TABLE 30
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 5

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
EGOISM	5.73	Usually Practiced
BENEVOLENCE.	6.97	Almost Always Practiced
PRINCIPLE	7.10	Almost Always Practiced
Average Grand Weighted Mean	6.60	Almost Always Practiced

1.000 – 1.874 Never Practiced (N)	4.500 – 5.374 Often Practiced (O)
1.875 – 2.749 Very Rarely Practiced (V)	5.375 – 6.249 Usually Practiced (U)
2.750 – 3.624 Rarely Practiced (R)	6.250 – 7.124 Almost Always Practiced (AAP)
3.625 – 4.499 Sometimes Practiced (S)	7.125 – 8.000 Always Practiced (AP)

Table 30 presents the summary of the level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 5. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The administrators of School 5 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.73 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.97 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 7.10 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.60 tells us that level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 5 is "almost always practiced".

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 5 is principle. In this climate organizational decisions are perceived as being guided by a strong and pervasive set of local rules or standards, such as codes of conduct (Appelbaum, Deguire, & Lay, 2005; Aquino & Becker, 2005; Liu, Fellows, & Ng, 2004; Martin & Cullen, 2006). This finding is supported by the study of Upchurch and Ruhland (1996) who found that even in lodging operations that were thought to be a benevolent climate, it is still of value to foster ethical decision-making based on the foundations of the principle ethical climate for rules, regulations, policies, and procedures are a critical part of the lodging operations. About the source of following rules of the organization, a study by Tyler and Blader (2005) found that "one promising way to bring the behavior of employees into line with corporate codes of conduct is to tap into their social values."

TABLE 31

THE DIFFERENCE IN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 1 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(5, 2)	0.099	19.296	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 6)	87.417	5.987	Significant
Length of Service	(6, 1)	9.019	233.986	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(4, 3)	0.746	9.117	Not Significant
Seminars/Training Attended	(1, 6)	0.052	5.987	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 31 presents the difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 1 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed F value 0.099 for "Age" is not significant against the critical F value 19.296 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of age. The computed F value 87.417 for "Sex" is significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 9.019 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 233.986 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of length of service. The computed F value 0.746 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 9.117 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of educational attainment. The computed F value 0.052 for "Seminars/ Training Attended" is not significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of seminars/training attended.

Of the five profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Sex" has to do with the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated. That is, their ethical decision-making practices vary as to their sex. This finding is supported by the study of Valentine and Rittenburg (2007) entitled, "*The Ethical Decision Making of Men and Women Executives in International Business Situations*" who found that women had marginally higher ethical judgments and significantly higher ethical intentions than did the men. They added that women are likely to act more ethically than men when faced with an ethical dilemma (Valentine & Rittenburg, 2007). It only goes to show that women administrators are more courageous to face ethical problems in the organization.

TABLE 32

**THE DIFFERENCE IN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES
OF SCHOOL 2 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE**

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(1, 6)	0.425	9.117	Not Significant
Sex	(4, 3)	0.734	5.987	Not Significant
Length of Service	(5, 2)	0.360	19.296	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(2, 5)	0.307	5.786	Not Significant
Seminars/Training Attended	(1, 6)	9.311	5.987	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 32 presents the difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 2 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed F value 0.425 for "Age" is not significant against the critical F value 9.117 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of age. The computed F value 0.734 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of sex. The computed F value 0.360 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 19.296 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of length of service. The computed F value 0.307 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 5.786 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of educational attainment. The computed F value 9.311 for "Seminars/ Training Attended" is significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty.

Of the five profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Seminars/Training Attended" has to do with the ethical decision-making practices of the School 2 administrators. Their approach to problems or situations is influenced by the seminars/training on ethical decision-making they have attended. Seminars and conferences are designed to update (educational) administrators. The finding is supported by the study entitled "The Ethical Reasoning of School Administrators: The Principled Principal" by Kirby, Paradise & Protti (1990), who recommended that administrators need training in ethical reasoning. Similarly, Sharma (1969) found that the need for competent administrators specifically trained to fill peculiarly difficult positions emphasizes the need for clear-cut modes of entering this field as a career.

Choauib & Zadem (2013) found that providing ethical training for managers showing selfish attitudes could effectively increase their sensitivity and "ethical competence," especially in organizations characterized by an egoistic climate. Since administrators belong to the top management, who plan and evaluate everything in the organization, they should be updated with seminars and conferences. In a similar vein, in his article entitled "*Ethics in Administration*," Karakose (2009) concluded that for ethical school governance it is necessary that we need qualified school principals who have special training related to ethical decision-making. He writes that schools and universities should provide this necessary training and support for administrators cooperatively. No university can afford to remain static in its efforts to function in

an ever more complex world (Sharma, 1969). Thus, seminars and conferences contribute to administrators in ethical decision-making.

TABLE 33
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 3 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(3,1)	0.224	215.707	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 3)	1.883	12.128	Not Significant
Length of Service	(1, 3)	1.883	12.128	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(2, 2)	2.671	19.000	Not Significant
Seminars/Training Attended	(1, 3)	0.900	12.128	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 33 presents the difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 3 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value 0.224 for "Age" is not significant against the critical *F* value 215.707 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of age. The computed *F* value 1.883 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical *F* value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of sex. The computed *F* value 1.883 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical *F* value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of length of service. The computed *F* value 2.671 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical *F* value 19.000 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of educational attainment. The computed *F* value 0.900 for "Seminars/ Training Attended" is not significant against the critical *F* value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in ethical decision-making practice in terms of seminars/training attended.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 3 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, and seminars/ training attended in ethical decision making do not influence the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 3. Their approach to problems or situations is likely the same regardless of age, sex, length of service, educational attainment and seminars / training attended.

TABLE 34

THE DIFFERENCE IN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 4 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(3,1)	2.217	215.707	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 3)	0.486	12.128	Not Significant
Length of Service	(2, 2)	5.800	19.000	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(1, 3)	2.536	12.128	Not Significant
Seminars/Training Attended	-	-	-	-

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 34 presents the difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 4 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value 2.217 for "Age" is not significant against the critical *F* value 215.707 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of age. The computed *F* value 0.486 for "Age" is not significant against the critical *F* value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of sex. The computed *F* value 5.800 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical *F* value 19.000 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of length of service. The computed *F* value 2.536 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical *F* value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of educational attainment. No *F* statistic can be computed for the difference in ethical decision-making practices in terms of seminars/ training attended since all administrators have not attended that kind of seminar or training.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 4 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment does not influence the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 4. Their approach to problems or situations is likely the same regardless of age, sex, length of service, educational attainment and seminars / training attended. Empirical studies do not support that finding that there is no significant difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices when grouped according to profile. The findings of this study are supported by the study of Linda Lange (1983) who found, that of the 18 men and women administrators in northeastern Ohio who were asked if they felt that these characteristics of women were accurate, none felt they were entirely true. All remarked that the individual person's characteristics are more important than the sex of the person. It is also supported by the study of Badawy (1978) who found that in one study of 100 female managers and supervisors, differences in managerial potential between males and females, though existing, were not perceived to be significant. Thus, the empirical studies clarify that sex is not a significant factor for ethical decision making on men and women.

However, the study of Perryer & Leighton (2002) does not support the findings of the study who found that age and sex are significant predictors of ethical beliefs. Even Gilligan (1982) believed that while men are more likely to consider rules, rights and fairness, women are more likely to be concerned with relationships, compassion and caring. Gilligan believed that the reason for this gender socialization during their childhood.

TABLE 35
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL 5 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(4, 5)	0.568	5.192	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 8)	1.177	5.318	Not Significant
Length of Service	(3, 6)	14.070	4.757	Significant
Educational Attainment	(3, 6)	1.971	4.757	Not Significant
Seminars/Training Attended	(1, 8)	2.715	5.318	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 35 presents the difference in the administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 5 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value 0.568 for "Age" is not significant against the critical *F* value 5.192 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of age. The computed *F* value 1.177 for "Sex" is significant against the critical *F* value 5.318 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of sex. The computed *F* value 14.070 for "Length of Service" is significant against the critical *F* value 4.757 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed *F* value 1.971 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical *F* value 4.757 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of educational attainment. The computed *F* value 2.715 for "Seminars/ Training Attended" is not significant against the critical *F* value 5.318 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of ethical decision-making practice in terms of seminars/training attended.

Of the five profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Length of Service" has to do with the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of St. Vincent's College Incorporated. That is, their ethical decision-making practices vary according to their length of service. The more seminars/training attended by an administrator in the organization the wiser he/she becomes when it comes ethical decision making because the person is familiar with the culture and practices of the organization. Even Elkhonon Goldberg (2014), a neuroscientist in New York and author of "The Wisdom Paradox," supported these findings by saying that "cognitive templates" develop in the older brain based on pattern recognition, and that these can form the basis for wise behavior and decisions (www.nyt.com) But there is a study that does not support the statement the older, the wiser. The study of Staudinger (1999) found that using the

Berlin wisdom paradigm, it seems fair to say that after about age 20, growing older is certainly not enough to become wiser.

The finding could mean the length of service of the administrator in the organization the more he/she considerate to people and organization. So length of service plays a significant role in ethical decision-making.

TABLE 36
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG CARING OF SCHOOL 1

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people look out for each other's good.	Mostly True	3.39	H
2. The most important concern is the good of all the people in the company.	Mostly True	3.61	H
3. In this company, the major concern is always what is best for the other person.	Mostly True	3.46	H
4. The most efficient way is always the right way, in this company.	Mostly True	3.89	H
5. Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company.	Mostly True	3.86	H
6. In this company, each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently.	Mostly True	4.07	H
7. It is expected that you will always do what is right for the customer and public.	Completely True	4.39	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.81	H

1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Caring (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Caring (M)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Caring (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Caring (H)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Caring (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Caring (VH)

Table 36 presents the level of ethical climate along caring of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 1, it is mostly true that: people look out for each other's good; the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the major concern is always what is best for the other person, the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company; and each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.81 tells us that the ethical climate of School 1 along **caring** is highly caring. An organization that is dominated by women is more likely to create a caring environment. In her classic book *In a Different Voice*, Gilligan (1982) introduced the ethic of care. She discovered that women and girls frequently turned to another voice, that of care, concern, and connection, in finding answers to their moral dilemmas. It is also supported by the study of Marilyn Ferguson (1980) who found that female leadership is characterized by a "caring form of power." Though not absolute most organization that are dominated by women tend to be caring.

TABLE 37
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INSTRUMENTAL OF SCHOOL 1

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are mostly out for themselves.	Somewhat False	2.25	S
2. The major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first.	Mostly True	3.71	H
3. People are expected to do anything to further the company's interests.	Somewhat True	3.25	M
4. There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company.	Mostly True	3.39	H
5. Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests.	Somewhat True	2.54	M
6. In this company, people protect their own interest above other considerations.	Somewhat True	2.89	M
7. People are concerned with the company's interests.	Somewhat True	3.32	M
Grand Weighted Mean	Somewhat True	3.05	M

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School's Interest (N)
- 0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School's Interest (VS)
- 1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School's Interest (S)
- 2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School's Interest (M)
- 3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School's Interest (H)
- 4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School's Interest (VH)

Table 37 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 1, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. It is somewhat true in this school that the people are expected to do anything to further the company's interests; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests, and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first and there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.05 tells us that the ethical climate of School 1 along **instrumental** is moderately concerned with the school's interest. The finding means that administrators are less concerned with school interests than they give importance to caring. A religious institution is encouraged to be more caring, that is, to work for the common good of the people than to work for the self or company profit.

TABLE 38

THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW AND CODE OF SCHOOL 1

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs.	Somewhat False	2.29	S
2. It is very important to follow strictly the company's rules and procedures here.	Mostly True	3.93	H
3. Each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong.	Somewhat True	3.00	M
4. The most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong.	Somewhat True	3.25	M
5. The first consideration is whether a decision violates any law.	Mostly True	3.39	H
6. People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations.	Mostly True	3.46	H
7. Everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures.	Mostly True	3.75	H
8. Successful people in this company go by the book.	Somewhat True	2.75	M
9. In this company, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards.	Mostly True	3.89	H
10. In this company, people are guided by their own personal ethics.	Somewhat True	2.64	M
11. Successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies.	Mostly True	3.75	H
12. In this company, the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration.	Mostly True	3.75	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Somewhat True	3.32	M

1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School Rules (N)

0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School Rules (VS)

1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School Rules (S)

2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School Rules (M)

3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School Rules (H)

4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School Rules (VH)

Table 38 presents the level of ethical climate along independence, rules, law and code of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 1, it is somewhat false that people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs in this school. This would mean that administrators follow the ethical standard

what feminist scholars Shapiro and Stefkovich (2011) call an ethic of care. They believed that the ethic of justice, which comprises rules, policies, standard operating procedures, and information systems, was normally the training of educational leaders in the past. They recommend the need for ethics of care, requiring leaders to consider multiple voices in the decision-making process. Thus, the ethic of care is important to educational leaders in resolving ethical issues.

TABLE 40
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG CARING OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people look out for each other's good.	Mostly True	3.74	H
2. The most important concern is the good of all the people in the company.	Completely True	4.26	VH
3. In this company, the major concern is always what is best for the other person.	Mostly True	3.49	H
4. The most efficient way is always the right way, in this company.	Mostly True	3.47	H
5. Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company.	Mostly True	3.98	H
6. In this company, each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently.	Completely True	4.44	VH
7. It is expected that you will always do what is right for the customer and public.	Completely True	4.37	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.96	H

1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Caring (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Caring (M)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Caring (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Caring (H)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Caring (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Caring (VH)

Table 40 presents the level of ethical climate along caring of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 2 it is mostly true that: people look out for each other's good; the major concern is always what is best for the other person; the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is true that the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; above all, each person is expected to work efficiently, and the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.81 tells us that the ethical climate of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated, along with caring, is highly caring. A highly caring ethical climate since most administrators are women. Educational researchers like Gross and Trask (1976) found that women offer " leadership that can revitalize instructional programs, motivate teachers, and create an effective learning environment. Caring, as an ethical climate, is often

associated with women administrators. Thus, women administrators develop a caring ethical culture.

TABLE 41
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INSTRUMENTAL OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are mostly out for themselves.	Somewhat True	2.91	S
2. The major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first.	Mostly True	3.79	H
3. People are expected to do anything to further the company's interests.	Mostly True	3.35	H
4. There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company.	Somewhat True	2.93	M
5. Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests.	Somewhat True	2.79	M
6. In this company, people protect their own interest above other considerations.	Somewhat True	2.93	M
7. People are concerned with the company's interests.	Somewhat True	3.00	M
Grand Weighted Mean	Somewhat True	3.10	M

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School's Interest (N)
- 0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School's Interest (VS)
- 1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School's Interest (S)
- 2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School's Interest (M)
- 3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School's Interest (H)
- 4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School's Interest (VH)

Table 41 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 2, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. It is somewhat true in this school that: there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests; people protect their own interest above other considerations; and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first and the people are expected to do anything to further the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.05 tells us that the ethical climate of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated along **instrumental** is moderately concerned with the school's interest. The findings that along instrumental climate it is moderately concerned with the school interest because institution is highly caring. Too much focus on company profit or school interest at the expense of employee welfare would become too egoistic. In their study Chouaib & Zaddem (2013) found that an egoistic climate raises mistrust among the members of the

company. So, this implies that the administrators balance employee welfare and company interest.

TABLE 42
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW AND CODE OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs.	Somewhat True	3.21	M
2. It is very important to follow strictly the company's rules and procedures here.	Mostly True	4.07	H
3. Each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong.	Mostly True	3.58	H
4. The most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong.	Mostly True	3.58	H
5. The first consideration is whether a decision violates any law.	Mostly True	3.72	H
6. People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations.	Mostly True	3.84	H
7. Everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures.	Mostly True	4.09	H
8. Successful people in this company go by the book.	Mostly True	3.35	H
9. In this company, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards.	Mostly True	4.00	H
10. In this company, people are guided by their own personal ethics.	Mostly True	3.49	H
11. Successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies.	Mostly True	3.84	H
12. In this company, the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration.	Mostly True	3.88	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.72	H

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School Rules (N)
- 0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School Rules (VS)
- 1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School Rules (S)
- 2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School Rules (M)
- 3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School Rules (H)
- 4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School Rules (VH)

Table 42 presents the level of ethical climate along independence, rules, law and code of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 2, it is somewhat true that in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; successful people in this company go by the book; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.72 tells us that the ethical climate of School 2 along **independence, rules, law and code** is highly concerned with the company rules and procedures. Brown, Trevino & Harrison (2005) found that ethical leaders' conduct serves as role-modelling behavior for followers as their behavior is accepted as appropriate. The findings reveal about how things are being done in the organization. So, since the it is highly concerned with company rules and procedures, it means that administrators serve as models in directing and guiding employees to embrace company rules and procedures.

TABLE 43
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 2

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
CARING	3.96	H
INSTRUMENTAL	3.10	M
INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW and CODE	3.72	H
Average Grand Weighted Mean	3.59	H

0.00 – 0.83 Not at all Ethical (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Ethical (M)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Ethical (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Ethical (H)
1.67 – 2.49 Slightly Ethical (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Ethical (VH)

Table 42 presents the summary of the level of ethical climate of School 2. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The perceptions of employees of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for **caaring** is 3.96 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for **instrumental** is 3.10 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for **independence, rules, law and code** is 3.72 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.59 tells us that the level of ethical climate of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated is "highly ethical."

However, the most dominant ethical climate of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated as perceived by the employees is **caring**. This finding is supported by the study of Victor and Cullen (1988) who found that “caring climate was the most preferred by the workers and instrumentalism was both the least dominant and the least preferred climate dimension.”

TABLE 44
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG CARING OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people look out for each other’s good.	Somewhat True	3.32	M
2. The most important concern is the good of all the people in the company.	Mostly True	3.72	H
3. In this company, the major concern is always what is best for the other person.	Mostly True	3.44	H
4. The most efficient way is always the right way, in this company.	Mostly True	3.32	H
5. Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company.	Mostly True	4.00	H
6. In this company, each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently.	Mostly True	3.96	H
7. It is expected that you will always do what is right for the customer and public.	Completely True	4.44	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.74	H

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Caring (N) | 2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Caring (M) |
| 0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Caring (VS) | 3.33 – 4.15 Highly Caring (H) |
| 1.67 – 2.49 Slight Caring (S) | 4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Caring (VH) |

Table 44 presents the level of ethical climate along caring of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 3, it is somewhat true that people look out for each other’s good. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion. It is mostly true that: the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the major concern is always what is best for the other person; the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company; and each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. It means that the organization is valued their clients so much as they say, “costumer is always right.” A concrete example is the Walmart company who succeeded because of its caring environment towards costumers. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.74 tells us that the ethical climate of School 3 along **caring** is highly caring. Developing a caring environment for employees, students and stakeholders is being promoting human development. Milton Mayeroff is his seminal work *On Caring* suggested that a chief goal of caring is human growth and development. He writes "To care for another

person, in the most significant sense, is to help him grow and actualize himself" (p.1) Human beings are basically relational. A caring culture is strengthening the relational of individuals. It is in relation that human beings become whole. In his article entitled Building an Ethical School: A Theory for Practice in Educational Leadership, Starratt (1991) writes that an ethic of caring requires fidelity to persons, a willingness to acknowledge their right to be who they are, an openness to encountering them in their authentic individuality, a loyalty to the relationship. Thus, a highly caring institution targets employees, students, and stakeholders to become more concern of the needy members of the community.

TABLE 45
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INSTRUMENTAL OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are mostly out for themselves.	Somewhat False	2.44	S
2. The major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first.	Mostly True	3.40	H
3. People are expected to do anything to further the company's interests.	Somewhat True	3.16	M
4. There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company.	Somewhat False	2.48	S
5. Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests.	Somewhat True	2.80	M
6. In this company, people protect their own interest above other considerations.	Somewhat True	2.92	M
7. People are concerned with the company's interests.	Mostly True	3.36	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Somewhat True	2.94	M

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School's Interest (N)
- 0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School's Interest (VS)
- 1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School's Interest (S)
- 2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School's Interest (M)
- 3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School's Interest (H)
- 4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School's Interest (VH)

Table 45 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 3, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves and there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. It is somewhat true in this school that the people are expected to do anything to further the company's interests; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests, and people protect their own interests above other considerations. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first, and people are concerned

with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 2.94 tells us that the ethical climate of School 3 along **instrumental** is moderately concerned with the school's interest. This means that the administrators do not focus more on the company interest than the best interest of the students. The purpose the learning institutions is for the best interest of the students. This rationale always guides the ethical decision-making of administrators. Moreover, religious institutions like Catholic schools are non-stock and non-profit organizations that give importance not only to company interest but also to the formation of holistic individuals that are globally competitive. In his study entitled "*Do Catholic Schools Make a Difference? Evidence from Australia,*" Vella (1999) found that individuals from Catholic schools are more likely to find employment and are paid higher wages in addition to the effects operating through the higher levels of achieved education. He writes that the evidence is suggestive that the labor market values education from Catholic schools more highly than education from government. Frisch & Huppenbauer (2014) found that the whole business strategy must be guided by an ethical business approach which allows leaders to focus not exclusively on short-term maximization of financial profit but to seriously care for the wellbeing of another stakeholder. So, it is reasonable that the instrumental climate is not so high since religious institutions basically concerned with the best interest of the students than company profit.

TABLE 46

THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW AND CODE OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs.	Somewhat True	3.08	M
2. It is very important to follow strictly the company's rules and procedures here.	Mostly True	3.64	H
3. Each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong.	Mostly True	3.36	H
4. The most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong.	Mostly True	3.56	H
5. The first consideration is whether a decision violates any law.	Somewhat True	3.28	M
6. People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations.	Mostly True	3.60	H
7. Everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures.	Mostly True	3.52	H
8. Successful people in this company go by the book.	Somewhat True	2.72	M
9. In this company, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards.	Mostly True	3.60	H
10. In this company, people are guided by their own personal ethics.	Mostly True	3.72	H

11. Successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies.	Mostly True	3.88	H
12. In this company, the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration.	Mostly True	3.56	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.46	H

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School Rules (N)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School Rules (VS)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School Rules (S)
2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School Rules (M)
3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School Rules (H)
4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School Rules (VH)

Table 46 presents the level of ethical climate along independence, rules, law and code of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 3, it is somewhat true that: in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; successful people in this company go by the book. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person’s sense of right and wrong; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.46 tells us that the ethical climate of School 3 along **independence, rules, law and code** is highly concerned with the school rules. *Successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies* is 3.88. This means that administrators act as role models in following company rules and policies since it is an acceptable fact that leaders are the frame of reference especially in following company rules and policies. In his study entitled, “*Principals Need to be Good Followers*”, Smith (1991) found that for the principal to be an effective leader, the principal must also be an effective follower. This finding is supported by Ferrell, Weaver, Taylor & Jones (1978) who found that top management must assume at least part of the responsibility for the ethical conduct of marketers within the organization. They write, by establishing and enforcing policy, the frame of reference for ethical behavior could be improved (Ferrell *et al*, p. 73).

TABLE 47
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 3

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
CARING	3.74	H
INSTRUMENTAL	2.94	M

INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW and CODE	3.46	H
Average Grand Weighted Mean	3.38	H
0.00 – 0.83 Not at all Ethical (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Ethical (M)	
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Ethical (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Ethical (H)	
1.67 – 2.49 Slightly Ethical (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Ethical (VH)	

Table 47 summarizes the level of ethical climate of School 3. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The perceptions of employees of School 3 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for **caring** is 3.74, meaning employees' perceptions of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for **instrumental** is 2.94 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for **independence, rules, law and code** is 3.46 which means that employees' perceptions of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.38 tells us that the level of ethical climate of School 3 is "highly ethical."

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 3 as perceived by the employees is **caring**. Educational institutions are tasked to form the hearts and minds of students. For this to be realized administrators and teachers should possess a caring attitude towards the students. After all, education is for the best interest of the students. This finding is supported by the study of Lynn Beck (1992) entitled, "*A Caring Ethic in Educational Administration*" who considered critique, justice, and caring as equally important guides to moral action but places caring at the top of the values hierarchy. He proposed that a number of ethics have a place in educational leadership but that each needs to be informed and guided by caring (Beck, p. 488). In religious institutions like School 3 the formation of a caring culture is expected and needed as model Christians for students.

TABLE 48
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG CARING OF SCHOOL 4

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people look out for each other's good.	Mostly True	3.54	H
2. The most important concern is the good of all the people in the company.	Mostly True	4.00	H
3. In this company, the major concern is always what is best for the other person.	Mostly True	3.54	H
4. The most efficient way is always the right way, in this company.	Mostly True	3.78	H
5. Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company.	Mostly True	3.92	H
6. In this company, each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently.	Completely True	4.22	VH
7. It is expected that you will always do what is right for the customer and public.	Completely True	4.41	VH

Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.92	H
1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Caring (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Caring (M)		
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Caring (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Caring (H)		
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Caring (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Caring (VH)		

Table 48 presents the level of ethical climate along caring of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 4, it is mostly true that: people look out for each other's good; the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the major concern is always what is best for the other person; the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently and the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.92 tells us that the ethical climate of School 4 along **caring** is highly caring. This means that administrators are faithful to the rationale of all religious institutions, that is, evangelization. Evangelization is making Christ's attitudes visible in the leaders' lives as true witnesses of the gospel. Archbishop Miller (2006) explained that the Catholic school would betray its purpose if it failed to found itself on the person of Christ and his teaching. This finding is supported by the study of Vogel (2012), who found, that among the 20 doctoral students who were asked to identify the kind of ethics that they need to make the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) program successful in elementary and high school, all hold values consistent with the ethic of care. In a similar vein, Nel Noddings (2012), in her article entitled "A Caring Relation to Teaching," proposed that creating a caring climate where caring relations can flourish should be a goal for all teachers and educational policymakers. He writes caring is essential to good teaching. Sernak (1998) explained that caring is a moral act, and that balancing and meeting the needs of the community with "care" is a political tightrope that school leaders must walk. Thus, administrators in religious institutions must maintain a caring attitude toward all the members of the organization.

TABLE 49
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INSTRUMENTAL OF SCHOOL 4

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are mostly out for themselves.	Somewhat False	2.49	S
2. The major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first.	Mostly True	3.81	H
3. People are expected to do anything to further the company's interests.	Mostly True	3.49	H
4. There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company.	Somewhat True	3.05	M
5. Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests.	Somewhat True	2.89	M

6. In this company, people protect their own interest above other considerations.	Somewhat True	2.54	M
7. People are concerned with the company's interests.	Mostly True	3.51	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Somewhat True	3.11	M

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School's Interest (N)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School's Interest (VS)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School's Interest (S)
2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School's Interest (M)
3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School's Interest (H)
4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School's Interest (VH)

Table 49 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 4, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. It is somewhat true in this school that: there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests; and people protect their own interest above other considerations. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first; and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.11 tells us that the ethical climate of School 4 along **instrumental** is moderately concerned with the school's interest. This means that religious school administrators do not prioritize company interest, which is egoistic. Rather, they are more effective in developing a caring climate, which is others-centered. Instrumental climate is thought to be more prevalent in an organization with a market form of governance like stores where promotion and recognition of employees will be based on sales. But this statement is put into question by the study of Wimbush, Shepard & Markam (1997) who found that store employees even chose service ethical climate over instrumental climate. If there is a study that does not support the claim that instrumental climate is expected to be dominant in stores where it is expected to establish, it is much safer to say that it will not flourish in a service-oriented organization like learning institution.

TABLE 50

THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW AND CODE OF SCHOOL 4

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs.	Somewhat True	2.95	M
2. It is very important to follow strictly the company's rules and procedures here.	Mostly True	3.84	H

3. Each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong.	Somewhat True	2.92	M
4. The most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong.	Somewhat True	3.22	M
5. The first consideration is whether a decision violates any law.	Mostly True	3.65	H
6. People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations.	Mostly True	3.76	H
7. Everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures.	Mostly True	3.89	H
8. Successful people in this company go by the book.	Somewhat True	2.51	M
9. In this company, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards.	Mostly True	4.08	H
10. In this company, people are guided by their own personal ethics.	Mostly True	3.38	H
11. Successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies.	Mostly True	3.81	H
12. In this company, the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration.	Mostly True	3.86	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.49	H

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School Rules (N)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School Rules (VS)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School Rules (S)
2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School Rules (M)
3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School Rules (H)
4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School Rules (VH)

Table 50 presents the level of ethical climate along independence, rules, law and code of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 4, it is somewhat true that: in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong; and successful people in this company go by the book. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 4, as perceived by the employees, is **caring**. Caring is one of the marks of Catholic schools that shows the proper attitude of Christian leaders towards people entrusted to them. This finding is supported by the study of Vogel (2012) entitled, *“Values and Ethics in Educational Administration”* who found that responses that related to the ethic of care also included the nurturing of family relationships, listening to others, seeking diverse input on decisions, collaboration, and building strong relationships with all participants in the educational process. As one female school administrator explained, *“As a principal, I have been able to touch the lives of other human beings by caring about them and helping them see themselves grow—helping them to see how they are special and helping them to grow into their human potential.”*

Even in rule-breaking scenario, administrator should be prudent in the giving disciplinary actions towards its members. In his study, entitled, *“A Qualitative Research on Administration Ethics at School,”* Gungor & Ozkara (2017) suggested that before giving punishment to rule-breakers, the first thing to do is to show the behaviors such as understanding the cause, warning if necessary, and finally giving the punishment. Administrators act in accordance with the golden rule and develop empathy.

TABLE 52
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG CARING OF SCHOOL 5

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people look out for each other’s good.	Mostly True	3.63	H
2. The most important concern is the good of all the people in the company.	Mostly True	4.02	H
3. In this company, the major concern is always what is best for the other person.	Somewhat True	3.32	M
4. The most efficient way is always the right way, in this company.	Mostly True	4.14	H
5. Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company.	Mostly True	3.95	H
6. In this company, each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently.	Completely True	4.34	VH
7. It is expected that you will always do what is right for the customer and public.	Completely True	4.29	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.96	H

1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Caring (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Caring (M)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Caring (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Caring (H)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Caring (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Caring (VH)

Table 52 presents the level of ethical climate along caring of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 5, it is somewhat true that the major concern is always what is best for the other person. This implies that the school is moderately caring in this criterion. It is mostly true that: people look out for each other’s good; the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the most efficient way is always the right way; the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently and the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.96 tells us that the ethical climate of School 5 along **caring** is highly caring. This means that the administrators of School 5 live up to the demands of their Catholic identity as witnesses to gospel. In his encyclical *Gaudete et Exultate* (Joy and Hope) Pope Francis exhorts “Catholics are called to be holy by living our lives in love and by bearing witness in everything we do wherever we find ourselves.” Applying this to educational setting, Catholic administrators are urged to connect faith and leadership, valuing people more. Even Ornstein (1991) argued that the leader is more people-oriented than task-oriented. He writes, “When administrators are concerned about people, people tend to put more effort into achieving the goals of the organization.” Horsch, Chen & Nelson (1999) validated their belief of the importance of allocating time at the beginning of the school year to create a safe, caring classroom environment to stimulate learning and community. In his article entitled, “*The Art of Schooling: Places of Authentic Learning and Caring*” Kelehear (2003) put it, “I would also envision a leadership where the teachers and principal work together to form a school culture that is focused on student achievement and engaged citizens.” A caring ethical climate enthrones human dignity and relations of people that are necessary for holistic formation of students that are not only globally competitive but also morally upright citizens.

TABLE 53
THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INSTRUMENTAL OF SCHOOL 5

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are mostly out for themselves.	Somewhat True	2.55	M
2. The major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first.	Mostly True	4.02	H
3. People are expected to do anything to further the company's interests.	Mostly True	3.57	H
4. There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company.	Somewhat True	2.95	M
5. Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests.	Somewhat True	3.06	M
6. In this company, people protect their own interest above other considerations.	Somewhat True	2.73	M
7. People are concerned with the company's interests.	Mostly True	3.54	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Somewhat True	3.20	M

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School's Interest (N)
- 0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School's Interest (VS)
- 1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School's Interest (S)
- 2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School's Interest (M)
- 3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School's Interest (H)
- 4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School's Interest (VH)

Table 53 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 5, it is somewhat true that: people are mostly out for themselves; there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests; and people protect their own interest above other considerations. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first; people are expected to do anything to further the company's interests; and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.20 tells us that the ethical climate of School 5 along **instrumental** is moderately concerned with the school's interest. This means that administrators are not profit-oriented but constant in the pursuit of its educational mission that is molding character of men and women committed to the person and teachings of Jesus Christ. Instrumental climate is basically egoistic. This is supported by the study of Chouaib & Zaddem (2013) who found that the actions and decisions of members of MN & CF companies favor a main expectation that is the exclusive pursuit of self-interest, sometimes to the detriment of the needs and interests of others. The result of this kind of climate is organizational distrust. According to one MN respondents, *"We feel that all that matters for the company is to achieve its profit goals at the least possible cost, and it always comes at the expense of employees' interests"*. In the *Common Good in Education* (1997) it stated that education is about the service of others rather than the service of self. To educate is to serve and to share. Thus, a school administrator who develop instrumental climate is a failure because he/she loses his/her primary vocation that is service. Since the instrumental climate in School 5 is not high it means that they administrators have the proper ideals in school management.

TABLE 54

THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ALONG INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW AND CODE OF SCHOOL 5

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. In this company, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs.	Somewhat True	2.96	M
2. It is very important to follow strictly the company's rules and procedures here.	Completely True	4.27	VH
3. Each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong.	Somewhat True	2.93	M
4. The most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong.	Mostly True	3.40	H
5. The first consideration is whether a decision violates any law.	Mostly True	3.69	H
6. People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations.	Completely True	4.47	VH

7. Everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures.	Completely True	4.20	VH
8. Successful people in this company go by the book.	Somewhat True	2.86	M
9. In this company, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards.	Mostly True	4.11	H
10. In this company, people are guided by their own personal ethics.	Mostly True	3.34	H
11. Successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies.	Mostly True	3.70	H
12. In this company, the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration.	Mostly True	3.83	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Mostly True	3.65	H

- 1.00 – 0.83 Not at all Concerned with School Rules (N)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Concerned with School Rules (VS)
1.67 – 2.49 Slight Concerned with School Rules (S)
2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Concerned with School Rules (M)
3.33 – 4.15 Highly Concerned with School Rules (H)
4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Concerned with School Rules (VH)

Table 54 presents the level of ethical climate along independence, rules, law and code of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

At School 5, it is somewhat true that: in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; and successful people in this company go by the book. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: the most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is completely true that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; and everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures. This implies that people in this school are very highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.65 tells us that the ethical climate of School 5 along **independence, rules, law and code** is highly concerned with the school rules. This means that administrators of School 5 follow rules and school policies. This finding is supported by Karakose (2009) who found that principals must follow codes of ethics and always think of students first in decision making. Smith (1991) recommended that universities, which employ principals, could assist the principal by incorporating followership training along with leadership training, for both are critical. This what Johanson (1994) calls "leadership by example and by involvement."

TABLE 55
THE SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 5

DIMENSION	Grand Weighted Mean	Implication
CARING	3.96	H
INSTRUMENTAL	3.20	M
INDEPENDENCE, RULES, LAW and CODE	3.65	H
Average Grand Weighted Mean	3.60	H

0.00 – 0.83 Not at all Ethical (N)	2.50 – 3.32 Moderately Ethical (M)
0.84 – 1.66 Very Slightly Ethical (VS)	3.33 – 4.15 Highly Ethical (H)
1.67 – 2.49 Slightly Ethical (S)	4.16 – 5.00 Very Highly Ethical (VH)

Table 55 presents the summary of the level of ethical climate of School 5. The table shows the dimension, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The perceptions of employees of School 5 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for **caring** is 3.96 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for **instrumental** is 3.20 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for **independence, rules, law and code** is 3.65 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.39 tells us that the level of ethical climate of School 5 is "highly ethical."

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 5 as perceived by the employees is **caring**. This means that the administrators of School 5 focus more on relationship and connection of the members of the organization over company profits or strict rule-following. The caring climate is not only felt among adults but most especially to the students by whom administrators and teachers have sacred duty to serve. Denig & Quinn (2001) explained that the ethic of care emphasizes concern for both the faculty and the students. The need for schools to be a caring community is supported by the study of Lewis, Schaps & Watson (1995) who said, "we call schools and classrooms in which every child feels connected to others, involved in decision-making, and valued as an individual "caring communities." Bryk, Lee, & Holland (1993) entitled, "*Catholic Schools and the Common Good*" explained that teachers are concerned about the kind of person each student becomes as about how much a student knows. Focusing on the quality of human relations. Teaching values and shaping the lives of young people by their actions and their example was as important as the subject matter presented (Bryk, *et al*, 99). While caring climate positively influences the student academic performance, it also affects the commitment of employees. This is supported by the study of Fu & Deshpande (2014) who found that employees feel more committed to their firm and have a better performance if they feel a sense of shared values with an employer who shows concern for them. So, establishing a caring climate is beneficial to all the members of the organization and the organization itself.

TABLE 56

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION MAKING PRACTICES AND THE SCHOOLS' ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 1

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation <i>r</i> with Ethical Climate		
	Caring	Instrumental	Independence, Rules, Law and Code
Egoism	0.568**	0.804**	0.491*
Benevolence	0.831**	0.762**	0.838**
Principle	0.741**	0.823**	0.687**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.561$ $\alpha = 0.01$ $df = 18$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.444$ $\alpha = 0.01$ $df = 18$

Table 56 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the schools' ethical climate of School 1. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, and the correlation *r* with ethical climate.

The table above revealed that there is a significant relationship between ethical decision-making practice of administrators and school's ethical climate of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated. There is a strong correlation between **egoism** and **instrumental**, and moderate correlations between **egoism** and **caring** and **egoism** and **independence, rules, law and code**. This means that in School 1, egoism criterion will result to instrumental climate.

The strong correlation between egoism and instrumental means that when administrators of School 1 use egoism in their ethical decision making it will result an instrumental climate. This finding is supported by the study of Martin & Cullen (2006) who found that actors perceiving in an instrumental climate see their organization unit as having norms and expectations that encourage ethical decision-making from an egoistic perspective. The result is supported by Victor and Cullen (1987, 1988) who stressed that under egoism, individuals do not care about the well-being of others. Wimbush & Shepard (1994) found that if the firm is characterized by the "instrumental" dimension of ethical climate, then the broker, for her own self-interest, and only in the ethical climate based on an egoistic decision-making criterion would people most likely act in ways to promote their own exclusive self-interest regardless of laws, rules, or the impact their actions have on others. So, administrators using the egoism criterion as the ethical decision-making practice will be able to establish instrumental ethical climate in the organization.

There are strong correlations between **benevolence** and all the climate types. There are also strong correlations between **principle** and all the climate types.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the predictor of a **caring** ethical climate is the **benevolence** ethical decision-making practice. The predictor of an **instrumental** ethical climate is the **egoism** and **principle** ethical decision-making practices. The predictor of an **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climate is the **benevolence** ethical decision-making practice. If the administrators' ethical practice is benevolence then the ethical climate is independence, rules and codes. However, this finding refutes the theory of Victor and Cullen (1987, 1988) who believed that caring climate is the predictor of benevolence criterion, although caring climate which is 0.831 is closer to independence, rules, law & code which is 0.838. This result is supported by the study of Acigil & Parlagumus (2012) who found that care shown to employees seems to go with enforcement of rules. This means that administrators who are benevolent in their decision-making will encourage employees to be faithful to company rules and codes. Eisenberg, Huntington, Hutchison & Sowa (1986) call this "repayment." They write,

“employees who feel a high-level organizational support are more likely to feel obligated to repay the organization back.”

TABLE 57
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS’ ETHICAL DECISION MAKING PRACTICES AND THE SCHOOLS’ ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 2

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation <i>r</i> with Ethical Climate		
	Caring	Instrumental	Independence, Rules, Law and Code
Egoism	0.186	0.393*	0.221
Benevolence	0.454**	0.347*	0.224
Principle	0.502**	0.207	0.499**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.429$ $\alpha = 0.01$ $df = 33$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.334$ $\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 33$

Table 57 presents the relationship between the administrators’ ethical decision-making practices and the schools’ ethical climate of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, and the correlation *r* with ethical climate.

The table above revealed that there is no significant relationship between **egoism** and **caring** and **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climate types but there is a significant relationship between **egoism** and **instrumental**. This means that egoism criterion will naturally yield an instrumental climate.

There is a significant relationship between **benevolence** and **caring** and **instrumental** ethical climate types but there is no significant relationship between **benevolence** and the **independence, rules, law and code**. This means that benevolence criterion will establish caring or instrumental climate, with greater significance with caring with 0.454** value over instrumental with 0.347** value.

There is a significant relationship between **principle** and **caring** and **independence, rules, law and code** but there is no significant relationship between **principle** and **instrumental**. Principle criterion will establish a caring climate with a greater value of 0.502 and independence, rules, law and code climate with a value 0.499. The finding contradicts the study of Victor, Cullen & Parboteeah (2003) who found that ethical criterion principle embodies the application or interpretation of rules, laws and standards in the normative expectations in a social unit.

The strength of correlation between **egoism** and **instrumental** is weak. There is a moderate correlation between **benevolence** and **caring** and a weak correlation between **benevolence** and **instrumental**. There is a moderate correlation between **principle** and **caring** and **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climate types.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the predictor of a **caring** climate are **principle** and **benevolence**. This means that if administrators of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan, Incorporated use principle or benevolence in their ethical decision-making practices this will result to establishing a caring climate. While there is no literature that supports the finding that caring is a predictor of principle, the finding that caring climate is a predictor of benevolence is supported Martin & Cullen (2006) who stressed that the roots of the caring construct are embedded in benevolence theory or, in terms of moral philosophy, utilitarianism.

The **instrumental** climate is manifested by **egoism** practice, and **independence, rules, law and code** climate is apparent in **principle** ethical decision-making practice. Administrators using egoism criterion will not establish a caring and independence, rules, law and code climate.

However, using egoism criterion in ethical decision-making will result to instrumental climate. The finding that there is no significant relationship between egoism and caring means that in the organization when administrators use egoism in their ethical decision-making it will not create a caring climate. This is supported by the theory of Victor and Cullen (1987, 1988) who found that individuals do not care about the well-being of others. Egoism is primarily based on the maximization of self-interest (Cullen et al, 2003). The finding that there is significant relationship between egoism and instrumental means that when administrators are egoistic it will create an instrumental or an ethical climate that is for the interest of the self. This finding corroborated the theory of Victor and Cullen (1987, 1877) who believed that within egoistic criterion of ethical judgement, the individuals' self-interest becomes the expected primary source of moral reasoning when a decision must be made.

TABLE 58
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION MAKING PRACTICES AND THE SCHOOLS' ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 3

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Ethical Climate		
	Caring	Instrumental	Independence, Rules, Law and Code
Egoism	0.038	0.185	0.012
Benevolence	0.271	0.066	0.052
Principle	0.127	0.120	0.159

Critical $r = 0.413$ $\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 21$

Table 58 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the schools' ethical climate of San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, and the correlation r with ethical climate.

The table above revealed no significant relationship between egoism and the ethical climate types, no significant relationship between benevolence and the ethical climate types, and no significant relationship between **independence, rules, law and code** and the ethical climate types.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the schools' ethical climate. This implies that ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated is not significantly related to the school's ethical climate. It implies that the ethical decision-making practices of administrators did not impact the ethical climate of San Estanislao Kostka College, Incorporated.

The result above contradicts the study of Martin & Cullen (2006) who found that the Victor and Cullen framework refers to egoism, benevolence (utilitarianism) and principle (deontology) dimensions. These are the implicit guidelines by which ethical decisions are framed. Research shows that one dominant criterion will emerge in an organization and ultimately define the organization's ethical climate. Ethical decision-making really influences the ethical climate of the organization. Mayer, Kenzi & Greenbaum (2010) stressed that, in essence, by role modeling appropriate behavior, ethical leaders help create a climate in which doing the right thing is valued. Even Stringer (2002) stated that most studies have shown that the single most important determinant of an organization's climate is the day-to day behavior of the leaders of the organization. The result is refuted by the study of Dulay & Karadag (2017) who found that a leader has an important place in the establishment of organizational climate. Although many

literatures contradict to the present finding, this means that ethical climate of the San Estanislao Kostka College is not influenced by the ethical decision-making practices of administrators.

TABLE 59
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES AND THE SCHOOLS' ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 4

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Ethical Climate		
	Caring	Instrumental	Independence, Rules, Law and Code
Egoism	0.283	0.433*	0.503**
Benevolence	0.413*	0.081	0.026
Principle	0.340*	0.291	0.372*

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.436$ $\alpha = 0.01$ $df = 32$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.339$ $\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 32$

Table 59 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the schools' ethical climate of School 3. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, and the correlation r with ethical climate.

The table above revealed that there is no significant relationship between **egoism** and the ethical climate of caring, but there is a significant relationship between egoism and ethical climates of instrumental and independence, rules, law, **and code**. That is, **egoism** practice has no effect on **caring** climate but has a moderate influence on **instrumental** and **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climates. There is a significant relationship between **benevolence** and **caring** but there is no significant relationship between **instrumental** and **independence, rules, law and code**. That is, **benevolence** practice has a moderate influence on a **caring** climate but has no effect on **instrumental** and **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climates. There is a significant relationship between **principle** and **caring** and **independence, rules, law, and code climates**. However, there is no significant relationship between **principle** and **instrumental**. That is, **principle** practice slightly affects **caring** and **independence, rules, law and code** climates but has no influence on **instrumental** climate.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the **benevolence** practice is a predictor of a **caring** climate, and **principle** is a predictor of **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climate. The predictor of **instrumental** climate type is the **egoism** practice. The highest value of relationship is egoism practice and independence, rules, law and code ethical climate with a computed value of 0.503**. This finding is refuted by the study of Randall Upchurch (1998) entitled, "A Conceptual Foundation for Ethical Decision Making: A Stakeholder Perspective in the Lodging Industry (U.S.A.)" who established that the criteria used in ethical reasoning for an egoism climate is maximizing self-interest either at the personal, company, or the societal level. Thus, leaders using egoism is expected to develop an instrumental climate which is self-interest. Simha and Cullen (2012) also further said that egoistic climates, instrumental and self-interest, have a negative association with work and job satisfaction.

TABLE 60

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES AND THE SCHOOLS' ETHICAL CLIMATE OF SCHOOL 5

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation <i>r</i> with Ethical Climate		
	Caring	Instrumental	Independence, Rules, Law and Code
Egoism	0.292**	0.450**	0.472**
Benevolence	0.190	0.119	0.219*
Principle	0.353**	0.171	0.316**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.264$ $\alpha = 0.01$ $df = 92$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) Critical $r = 0.203$ $\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 92$

Table 60 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the schools' ethical climate of St. Vincent's College Incorporated. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, and the correlation *r* with ethical climate.

The table above revealed that there is a significant relationship between **egoism** and the ethical climate types. That is, **egoism** practice has a slight influence on a **caring** climate, and moderate influence on **instrumental** and **independence, rules, law and code** climate types. There is no significant relationship between **benevolence** and **caring** and **instrumental** ethical climate types but there is a significant relationship between **benevolence** and **independence, rules, law and code** climate type. That is, **benevolence** practice has no effect on **caring** and **instrumental** climate types but has a slight influence on **independence, rules, law and code** climate type. There is a significant relationship between **principle** and **caring** and **independence, rules, law and code** climate types, however there is no significant relationship between **principle** and **instrumental** climate type. That is, **principle** practice has a slight influence on **caring** and **independence, rules, law and code** climate types but has no effect on **instrumental** climate type.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the predictor of a **caring** climate is the **principle** practice, and the predictor of an **instrumental** and **independence, rules, law and code** ethical climate types is **egoism** practice. This means that the administrators of St. Vincent's College Incorporated link egoism criterion as the predictor of three ethical climates namely caring, instrumental, and independence, rules, law and code. The independence, rules, law and code climate has the biggest computed *r* value 0.472**. When administrators of St. Vincent's College used egoism criterion of ethical decision-making, the more the people will be encouraged to abide to the policies and guidelines of the school. This finding contradicts the theory of Victor and Cullen (1987, 1988) who believed that the egoism criterion is defined as consideration of the needs and preferences of one's own self (e.g., personal gain, self-defense). Simha and Cullen (2012) argued that egoism refers to the behavior that is concerned with self-interest.

TABLE 61
THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 1

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. I am happy to come to work every morning.	Often	4.05	H
2. I can do my work without fear.	Often	4.15	H
3. I feel secure in my employment.	Often	3.45	M
4. I feel supported, valued and appreciated.	Often	3.70	H
5. I have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision.	Often	3.75	H
6. I know what is expected of me in this job.	Always	4.20	VH
7. I am given adequate training, authority, and resources to do my job effectively.	Often	3.65	H
8. I receive feedback on how I perform my job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/ unsupportive.	Often	3.60	H
9. I am provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally – and is free of harassment.	Often	4.05	H
10. My work gives me a feeling of accomplishment and pride.	Always	4.20	VH
11. I am given sufficient responsibility on my job.	Always	4.25	VH
12. The duties of my position are clearly defined.	Often	4.10	H
13. We are treated equally and with respect.	Sometimes	3.35	M
14. I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between my family and my job.	Often	3.70	H
15. We have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment.	Often	3.50	H

16. I am happy with the pay levels here and believe I am paid well for my job.	Sometimes	3.25	M
17. I am happy with the employee review system.	Sometimes	3.35	M
18. I am involved in decisions affecting my position/work.	Often	3.50	H
19. We all participate in problem-solving.	Sometimes	3.35	M
20. My manager supports me in my professional development.	Often	3.75	H
21. My manager ensures that we are recognized and appreciated for our efforts in making the company grow.	Often	3.40	H
22. I feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company.	Sometimes	3.30	M
23. Workload is fairly allocated among employees.	Sometimes	3.20	M
24. I enjoy my job and believe I have a secure future here.	Often	3.40	H
25. New employees are given a thorough orientation.	Sometimes	3.05	M
26. I am satisfied with the professionalism shown by my fellow peers and leaders.	Often	3.55	H
27. Employee turn-over is reasonable-not high.	Sometimes	3.30	M
28. Senior management is open and honest.	Often	3.50	H
29. The company has a great internal communication system.	Sometimes	3.00	M
30. The company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.	Sometimes	3.35	M
31. The company provides great employee benefits.	Often	3.45	H
32. We enjoy good morale in this company.	Often	3.70	H

33. I am optimistic about the future of the company.	Often	3.60	H
34. Overall, I am happy with my job and place in the company.	Often	3.60	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Often	3.60	H

1.00 – 1.79 Very Low (VL)

1.80 – 2.59 Low (L)

2.60 – 3.39 Moderate (M)

3.40 – 4.19 High (H)

4.20 – 5.00 Very High (VH)

Table 61 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 1. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The condition of the employees' morale is moderate in the sense that: they are treated equally and with respect; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they all participate in problem-solving; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; new employees are given a thorough orientation; employee turnover is reasonable- not high; the company has a great internal communication system; and the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.

The condition of the employees' morale are high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; the duties of their position are clearly defined; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; their senior management is open and honest; the company provides great employee benefits; they enjoy good morale in the school; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they know what is expected of them in their job; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; and they are given sufficient responsibility on their job. This finding is supported by the study entitled, *“Definition and Measurement of Employee Morale”* by Baehr & Renck (1958) who found that the satisfactions associated with doing the job and with the belief that the job is worthwhile and affords opportunities for personal growth and development is relevant in measuring the morale of employees. Even Verma (1987) believed that employees' morale seems to be closely related with job involvement.

The grand weighted mean of 3.60 tells us that the condition of the employees' morale at Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated are high. This means, that since they are satisfied with their pay, relations among colleagues, and how the organization value them as persons and professionals, the employees of Colegio de San Francisco Javier feel that they are at home in the organization, enthusiastic in their work and determined to stay in the organization.

TABLE 62
THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 2

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. I am happy to come to work every morning.	Always	4.26	VH
2. I can do my work without fear.	Always	4.26	VH
3. I feel secure in my employment.	Often	3.63	H
4. I feel supported, valued and appreciated.	Often	3.71	H
5. I have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision.	Often	3.94	H
6. I know what is expected of me in this job.	Often	4.09	H
7. I am given adequate training, authority, and resources to do my job effectively.	Often	3.97	H
8. I receive feedback on how I perform my job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive.	Often	3.66	H
9. I am provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally – and is free of harassment.	Always	4.29	VH
10. My work gives me a feeling of accomplishment and pride.	Always	4.43	VH
11. I am given sufficient responsibility on my job.	Always	4.49	VH
12. The duties of my position are clearly defined.	Always	4.26	VH
13. We are treated equally and with respect.	Often	4.09	H
14. I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between my family and my job.	Always	4.37	VH
15. We have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment.	Often	3.80	H

16. I am happy with the pay levels here and believe I am paid well for my job.	Sometimes	3.03	M
17. I am happy with the employee review system.	Often	3.54	H
18. I am involved in decisions affecting my position/work.	Often	3.60	H
19. We all participate in problem-solving.	Often	3.60	H
20. My manager supports me in my professional development.	Often	4.14	H
21. My manager ensures that we are recognized and appreciated for our efforts in making the company grow.	Often	4.03	H
22. I feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company.	Often	3.66	H
23. Workload is fairly allocated among employees.	Often	3.60	H
24. I enjoy my job and believe I have a secure future here.	Often	3.54	H
25. New employees are given a thorough orientation.	Often	3.89	H
26. I am satisfied with the professionalism shown by my fellow peers and leaders.	Often	3.77	H
27. Employee turn-over is reasonable-not high.	Often	3.71	H
28. Senior management is open and honest.	Often	3.97	H
29. The company has a great internal communication system.	Often	3.49	H
30. The company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.	Often	3.97	H
31. The company provides great employee benefits.	Sometimes	3.03	M
32. We enjoy good morale in this company.	Often	3.86	H

33. I am optimistic about the future of the company.	Often	3.89	H
34. Overall, I am happy with my job and place in the company.	Often	4.03	H
Grand Weighted Mean	Often	3.87	H

1.00 – 1.79 Very Low (VL)

1.80 – 2.59 Low (L)

2.60 – 3.39 Moderate (M)

3.40 – 4.19 High (H)

4.20 – 5.00 Very High (VH)

Table 62 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 2. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The condition of the employees' morale is moderate in the sense that they are happy with the pay levels and believe they are paid well for my job, and the company provides great employee benefits.

The condition of the employees' morale are high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they know what is expected of them in their job; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are treated equally and with respect; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are happy with the employee review system; they all participate in problem-solving; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; new employees are given a thorough orientation; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; they enjoy good morale in the school; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and are free of harassment; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; and they can maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job.

The grand weighted mean of 3.87 tells us that the condition of the employees' morale at Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated are high. This means that the employees of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated are motivated and committed to work because the working environment is safe, specific job description, family factor and are empowered to become more productive in the organization (*has very high weighted mean of 4.49*). This finding is supported by the study entitled "How Employee Empowerment Improves Manufacturing Performance" by Cole (1995), who found that the commitment of employees developed when they are empowered to participate in managerial decision-making and training in group problem-solving. Another empirical support from the study entitled, "*Identifying Factors for Employee Satisfaction*" by Tso, Liu & Li (2015) who found that the job satisfaction score is the highest among all factors for employee satisfaction. Thus, when employees of Rizal Memorial Institute

are satisfied with their job and productivity, these create a sense of fulfillment in the organization as contributing factor in boosting their morale.

TABLE 63
THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 3

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. I am happy to come to work every morning.	Always	4.43	VH
2. I can do my work without fear.	Always	4.30	VH
3. I feel secure in my employment.	Often	4.00	H
4. I feel supported, valued and appreciated.	Often	3.91	H
5. I have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision.	Always	4.26	VH
6. I know what is expected of me in this job.	Always	4.48	VH
7. I am given adequate training, authority, and resources to do my job effectively.	Often	4.26	H
8. I receive feedback on how I perform my job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive.	Often	4.09	H
9. I am provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally – and is free of harassment.	Always	4.65	VH
10. My work gives me a feeling of accomplishment and pride.	Always	4.70	VH
11. I am given sufficient responsibility on my job.	Always	4.61	VH
12. The duties of my position are clearly defined.	Always	4.61	VH
13. We are treated equally and with respect.	Always	4.43	VH
14. I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between my family and my job.	Always	4.52	VH

15. We have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment.	Always	4.35	VH
16. I am happy with the pay levels here and believe I am paid well for my job.	Often	3.96	H
17. I am happy with the employee review system.	Often	4.09	H
18. I am involved in decisions affecting my position/work.	Often	4.00	H
19. We all participate in problem-solving.	Often	3.83	H
20. My manager supports me in my professional development.	Always	4.22	VH
21. My manager ensures that we are recognized and appreciated for our efforts in making the company grow.	Always	4.26	VH
22. I feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company.	Often	3.96	H
23. Workload is fairly allocated among employees.	Often	4.04	H
24. I enjoy my job and believe I have a secure future here.	Always	4.22	VH
25. New employees are given a thorough orientation.	Always	4.39	VH
26. I am satisfied with the professionalism shown by my fellow peers and leaders.	Often	4.04	H
27. Employee turn-over is reasonable-not high.	Often	3.78	H
28. Senior management is open and honest.	Often	3.91	H
29. The company has a great internal communication system.	Often	3.87	H
30. The company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.	Often	3.87	H
31. The company provides great employee benefits.	Often	3.96	H

32. We enjoy good morale in this company.	Often	4.13	H
33. I am optimistic about the future of the company.	Always	4.35	VH
34. Overall, I am happy with my job and place in the company.	Always	4.61	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Always	4.21	VH

1.00 – 1.79 Very Low (VL)

1.80 – 2.59 Low (L)

2.60 – 3.39 Moderate (M)

3.40 – 4.19 High (H)

4.20 – 5.00 Very High (VH)

Table 63 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 3. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The condition of the employees' morale is high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they all participate in problem-solving; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; the company provides great employee benefits; and they enjoy good morale in the school;

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they know what is expected of them in their job; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; they are treated equally and with respect; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; new employees are given a thorough orientation; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The grand weighted mean of 4.21 tells us that the condition of the employees' morale at San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated is very high. The significant indicator is, "My work gives me a feeling of accomplishment and pride," with a weighted value 4.70, very high. This means that when employees are satisfied with their job, they are more motivated with their work. This finding is support by the study entitled, "*Identifying Factors for Employee Satisfaction*" that in identifying factors for employee satisfaction, job satisfaction score is the highest among all factors (Tso, *et al.*, 2015). It means that job satisfaction is important predictor of employee morale. Levin (2008) stressed that retaining good teachers requires giving teachers interesting and challenging work, good working conditions, and respect. There is a great emphasis on

providing them with opportunities to develop their skills. Thus, when employees of San Estanislao Kostka entrusted with work-related task and whose efforts are acknowledged by superiors, they boost their morale.

TABLE 64
THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 4

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. I am happy to come to work every morning.	Always	4.32	VH
2. I can do my work without fear.	Always	4.44	VH
3. I feel secure in my employment.	Often	3.94	H
4. I feel supported, valued and appreciated.	Often	3.74	H
5. I have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision.	Often	4.15	H
6. I know what is expected of me in this job.	Always	4.21	VH
7. I am given adequate training, authority, and resources to do my job effectively.	Often	3.85	H
8. I receive feedback on how I perform my job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive.	Often	3.68	H
9. I am provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally – and is free of harassment.	Always	4.35	VH
10. My work gives me a feeling of accomplishment and pride.	Always	4.35	VH
11. I am given sufficient responsibility on my job.	Always	4.41	VH
12. The duties of my position are clearly defined.	Always	4.29	VH
13. We are treated equally and with respect.	Often	4.00	H

14. I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between my family and my job.	Often	4.06	H
15. We have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment.	Often	3.91	H
16. I am happy with the pay levels here and believe I am paid well for my job.	Often	3.53	H
17. I am happy with the employee review system.	Often	3.50	H
18. I am involved in decisions affecting my position/work.	Often	3.82	H
19. We all participate in problem-solving.	Often	3.65	H
20. My manager supports me in my professional development.	Often	3.94	H
21. My manager ensures that we are recognized and appreciated for our efforts in making the company grow.	Often	3.79	H
22. I feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company.	Often	3.74	H
23. Workload is fairly allocated among employees.	Sometimes	3.32	M
24. I enjoy my job and believe I have a secure future here.	Often	3.68	H
25. New employees are given a thorough orientation.	Sometimes	3.29	M
26. I am satisfied with the professionalism shown by my fellow peers and leaders.	Often	3.79	H
27. Employee turn-over is reasonable-not high.	Often	3.50	H
28. Senior management is open and honest.	Often	3.88	H
29. The company has a great internal communication system.	Often	3.65	H
30. The company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.	Often	4.00	H

31. The company provides great employee benefits.	Sometimes	3.06	M
32. We enjoy good morale in this company.	Often	3.97	H
33. I am optimistic about the future of the company.	Often	4.18	H
34. Overall, I am happy with my job and place in the company.	Always	4.26	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Often	3.89	H

1.00 – 1.79 Very Low (VL)

1.80 – 2.59 Low (L)

2.60 – 3.39 Moderate (M)

3.40 – 4.19 High (H)

4.20 – 5.00 Very High (VH)

Table 64 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 4. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The condition of the employees' morale is moderate in the sense that: the workload is fairly allocated among employees; new employees are given a thorough orientation; and the company provides great employee benefits.

The condition of the employees' morale is high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are treated equally and with respect; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; they all participate in problem-solving; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; they enjoy good morale in the school; and they are optimistic about the future of the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they know what is expected of them in their job; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally – and is free of harassment; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The grand weighted mean of 3.89 us that the condition of the employees' morale at Saint Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated is high. The significant indicator with a weighted mean of 4.44 is, "*I can do my work without fear*" means that when employees of St. Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated work in friendly environment, they are more productive and motivated. This finding is supported by the article entitled, "*The Importance of a Positive Working*

Environment” by Johnny Peters (2013) who held that if people are happy with where they work and the environment they walk into each day, they have been proven to be more productive and make less mistakes (<https://anz.businesschief.com/leadership>). On the other hand, if employees work in a fearful environment, the effect is organizational disaster. In the article, “*The Effects of Fear in a Job Environment*” Kristine Tucker found that when employees experience fear at work and don’t receive positive, encouraging feedback from their supervisors, they might respond with resistance. Resistance might come in the form of reduced productivity, a lack of participation, unwillingness to change and isolation. Fear can also lead to silence in the workplace, forcing subordinates to refrain from expressing their views and opinions to managers and other superiors (www.cron.com). Thus, for employees of St. Joseph College of Sindangan, Incorporated, a friendly and positive work environment is necessary to boost their morale.

TABLE 65
THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES’ MORALE OF SCHOOL 5

CRITERIA	Scale Level	Weighted Mean	Implication
1. I am happy to come to work every morning.	Always	4.29	VH
2. I can do my work without fear.	Always	4.33	VH
3. I feel secure in my employment.	Often	4.02	H
4. I feel supported, valued and appreciated.	Often	3.77	H
5. I have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision.	Often	3.82	H
6. I know what is expected of me in this job.	Always	4.43	VH
7. I am given adequate training, authority, and resources to do my job effectively.	Often	3.76	H
8. I receive feedback on how I perform my job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive.	Often	3.67	H
9. I am provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally – and is free of harassment.	Often	4.06	H
10. My work gives me a feeling of accomplishment and pride.	Always	4.90	VH

11. I am given sufficient responsibility on my job.	Always	4.34	VH
12. The duties of my position are clearly defined.	Always	4.24	VH
13. We are treated equally and with respect.	Often	4.06	H
14. I am able to maintain a reasonable balance between my family and my job.	Often	4.05	H
15. We have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment.	Often	3.59	H
16. I am happy with the pay levels here and believe I am paid well for my job.	Often	3.78	H
17. I am happy with the employee review system.	Often	3.74	H
18. I am involved in decisions affecting my position/work.	Often	3.66	H
19. We all participate in problem-solving.	Often	3.70	H
20. My manager supports me in my professional development.	Often	4.11	H
21. My manager ensures that we are recognized and appreciated for our efforts in making the company grow.	Often	3.87	H
22. I feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company.	Often	3.65	H
23. Workload is fairly allocated among employees.	Often	3.70	H
24. I enjoy my job and believe I have a secure future here.	Often	3.94	H
25. New employees are given a thorough orientation.	Sometimes	3.22	M
26. I am satisfied with the professionalism shown by my fellow peers and leaders.	Often	3.73	H
27. Employee turn-over is reasonable-not high.	Often	3.64	H

28. Senior management is open and honest.	Often	3.81	H
29. The company has a great internal communication system.	Often	3.59	H
30. The company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.	Often	3.90	H
31. The company provides great employee benefits.	Often	3.81	H
32. We enjoy good morale in this company.	Often	3.97	H
33. I am optimistic about the future of the company.	Always	4.26	VH
34. Overall, I am happy with my job and place in the company.	Always	4.34	VH
Grand Weighted Mean	Often	3.93	H

1.00 – 1.79 Very Low (VL)

1.80 – 2.59 Low (L)

2.60 – 3.39 Moderate (M)

3.40 – 4.19 High (H)

4.20 – 5.00 Very High (VH)

Table 65 presents the level of ethical climate along instrumental of School 5. The table shows the criteria, scale level, weighted mean, grand weighted mean, and implication.

The condition of the employees' morale is moderate because the new employees are given a thorough orientation; and the company provides great employee benefits.

The condition of the employees' morale are high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; they are treated equally and with respect; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; they all participate in problem-solving; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; the employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; the company provides great employee benefits; and they enjoy good morale in the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they know what is expected of

them in their job; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The grand weighted mean of 3.93 us that the condition of the employees' morale at School 5 are high. The two highest indicators are job-related namely, "*I know what is expected of me in this job*" with 4.43 weighted mean and "*I am give sufficient responsibility on my job*" with a weighted mean of 4. 34. This finding is supported by an article entitled, "*Employees Meet Only Expectations When They Know What is Expected*" by Heather Huhman (2015) who indicated that employees who don't know what their manager expects of them can't be engaged or successful in the workplace. She recommended open lines of communication for administrators by letting employees know that their role plays a significant part for the success of the organization (<https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/252734>).

TABLE 66
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 1 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(6, 13)	1.053	2.915	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 18)	0.079	4.414	Not Significant
Length of Service	(4, 15)	2.913	3.056	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(2, 17)	1.541	3.592	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 66 presents the difference in the level of employees' morale at School 1 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value 1.053 for "Age" is not significant against the critical *F* value 2.915 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of age. The computed *F* value 0.079 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical *F* value 4.414 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of sex. The computed *F* value 2.913 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical *F* value 3.056 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of length of service. The computed *F* value 1.541 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical *F* value 3.592 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of educational attainment.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the level of employees' morale of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment do not influence School 1 employees' morale. This finding is supported by the study entitled, "*Staff Perceptions of Work-Environment Factors Affecting Morale in Southeastern Registrar's Offices,*" by Rheanna Plemons (2014, p. 124), who found

that when it comes to gender, females typically create friendships based on personal similarities. In contrast, men may find the development of friendships to be a challenge in this female-dominated field. With regard to age, age showed no significance on morale, motivators, or leadership styles (p.125). But the study entitled, “*The Aging Workforce Raises New Talent Management Issues for Employers,*” by Rappaport, Bancroft & Okum (2003) contradict the present finding who reported on low morale among older workers who were financially unable to retire. Robert Baker (1980) found that in relation to correctional facility officers as respondents, age tends to influence job satisfaction more than education among older officers. With regards to length of service, years of service had no significance based on the Fisher’s Exact Test. However, individual results showed those with fewer years of experience were more likely to retain high morale through a change. Those with more experience in the office perceived those with fewer years accepted this change because they were naïve. Those with more years of experience perceived they were able to accept change with high morale, because they had been through more changes than younger employees (p. 126). About educational attainment and employee morale, Ivar Berg (1971) refuted the finding by declaring that when an individual's educational attainment level is well aligned with his or her job skill requirements, the individual's job satisfaction level will tend to be high.

TABLE 67
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES’ MORALE SCHOOL 2 WHEN
GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(8, 26)	2.357	2.320	Significant
Sex	(1, 33)	0.609	4.139	Not Significant
Length of Service	(5, 29)	3.261	2.545	Significant
Educational Attainment	(3, 31)	0.513	2.911	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 67 presents the difference in the level of employees’ morale of School 2 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value of 2.357 for “Age” is significant against the critical *F* value of 2.320 at a 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed *F* value 0.609 for “Sex” is not significant against the critical *F* value 4.139 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees’ morale in terms of sex. The computed *F* value 3.261 for “Length of Service” is significant against the critical *F* value 2.545 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed *F* value of 0.513 for “Educational Attainment” is not significant against the critical *F* value of 2.911 at a 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in employees’ morale in terms of educational attainment.

Of the four profile variables, we found enough evidence that “Age” and “Length of Service” affect School 2 employees' morale. That is, their age and length of service influence the spirit of the employees that would make them want to succeed. This means that employees’ morale in School 2 is influenced by age and length of service. Concerning age as related to employee

morale, this finding is supported by the study entitled “*Employee Attitudes as a Function of Age and Length of Service: A Reconceptualization*” by Gibson & Klein (1970), who found that there is a positive relationship between age and overall satisfaction (morale); satisfaction with pay, job, supervisor. An article entitled, *Factor Affecting Morale*, indicated that, while younger workers are more dissatisfied with higher expectations than their elders, older employees have more stability which comes with maturity, a severe attitude towards the job, more reliability, less absenteeism, proven steady work habits, a sense of responsibility and loyalty and less tendency to be distracted by outside interest as influences (https://ebrary.net/2848/management/factors_affecting_morale). However, Vollmer & Kinney (1955) found that younger employees were likelier to report job satisfaction than older employees.

About the length of service as related to employee morale, the finding contradicted the study of Gibson and Klein (1970), who found that there is no significant relationship between tenure and satisfaction (morale) for three reasons: disconfirmed expectations of relatively hopeful, naïve new employees, acculturation into a we-they value system occurs, and perceptions of favoritism occur as other people in the system are promoted.

TABLE 68
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES’ MORALE OF SCHOOL 3 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(7,15)	2.011	2.707	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 21)	0.043	4.325	Not Significant
Length of Service	(3, 19)	2.321	3.127	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(3, 20)	0.473	3.493	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 68 presents the difference in the level of employees’ morale of School 3 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value 2.011 for “Age” is not significant against the critical *F* value 2.707 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in employees’ morale in terms of age. The computed *F* value of 0.043 for “Sex” is not significant against the critical *F* value of 4.325 at a 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees’ morale in terms of sex. The computed *F* value 2.321 for “Length of Service” is not significant against the critical *F* value 3.127 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in employees’ morale in terms of length of service. The computed *F* value 0.473 for “Educational Attainment” is not significant against the critical *F* value of 3.493 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference in employees’ morale in terms of educational attainment.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the level of employee’ morale at School 3 when grouped according to

profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment does not influence the morale of employees of School 3.

This finding is supported by the study entitled, “*Staff Perceptions of Work-Environment Factors Affecting Morale in Southeastern Registrar’s Offices*,” by Rheanna Plemons (2014, p. 124) who found that when it comes to gender, females typically create friendships based on personal similarities, whereas men may find the development of friendships to be a challenge in this female-dominated field. About age, age showed no significance on morale, motivators, or leadership styles (p.125). But the study entitled, “*The Aging Workforce Raises New Talent Management Issues for Employers*,” by Rappaport, Bancroft & Okum (2003) contradict the present finding who reported on low morale among older workers who were financially unable to retire. Robert Baker (1980) found that in relation to prison officers as respondents, age tends to influence job satisfaction more than education among the older officers. With regards to length of service, years of service had no significance based on the Fisher’s Exact Test. However, individual results showed those with fewer years of experience were more likely to retain high morale through a change. Those with more experience in the office perceived those with fewer years accepted this change because they were naïve. Those with more years of experience perceived they were able to accept change with high morale, because they had been through more changes than younger employees (p. 126). With regard to educational attainment and employee morale, this finding is refuted by the study, “*Employee Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism and Turnover*” by Mowday, Porter & Steers (1982) who pointed out "that this inverse relationship may result from the fact that more educated individuals have higher expectations that the organization may be unable to meet" (p. 30). Because more educated employees have a greater number of job options, they would be less likely to stay with the organization (Obeng and Ugboro, 2003) who cannot afford to give in to their demands.

TABLE 69
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES’ MORALE OF SCHOOL 4 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(5, 28)	1.579	2.558	Not Significant
Sex	(1, 32)	0.877	4.149	Not Significant
Length of Service	(3, 30)	0.451	2.922	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	(3, 30)	0.822	2.922	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 69 presents the difference in the level of employees’ morale of School 4 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F-value, critical F-value, and interpretation.

The computed *F* value 1.579 for “Age” is not significant against the critical *F* value 2.558 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees’ morale in terms of age. The computed *F* value 0.877 for “Sex” is not significant against the critical *F* value 4.149 at

0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of sex. The computed F value 0.451 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 2.922 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of length of service. The computed F value 0.822 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 2.922 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of educational attainment.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the level of employees' morale of School 4 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment does not affect the psychological well-being of the employees as they perform their jobs. This finding is supported by the study entitled, "*Staff Perceptions of Work-Environment Factors Affecting Morale in Southeastern Registrar's Offices*," by Rheanna Plemons (2014, p. 124) who found that when it comes to gender, females typically create friendships based on personal similarities, whereas men may find the development of friendships to be a challenge in this female dominated field. With regard to age, age showed no significance on morale, motivators, or leadership styles (p.125). But the study entitled, "*The Aging Workforce Raises New Talent Management Issues for Employers*," by Rappaport, Bancroft & Okum (2003) contradict the present finding who reported on low morale among older workers who were financially unable to retire. Robert Baker (1980) found that in relation to correctional facility officers as respondents, age tends to influence job satisfaction more than education among the older officers. The study of Ilagan & Javier (2014) refuted the finding who found that age is related to morale among employees of Banco de Oro.

With regards to length of service, it had no significance based on the Fisher's Exact Test. However, individual results showed those with fewer years of experience were more likely to retain high morale through a change. Those with more experience in the office perceived those with fewer years accepted this change because they were naïve. Those with more years of experience perceived they were able to accept change with high morale, because they had been through more changes than younger employees (p. 126). With regard to the relationship between educational attainment and employee morale, this finding is supported by the study of Judge & Hulin (1993) who found a negative association between job satisfaction and educational level, wage, alternative employment opportunities, hours worked. But Ivar Berg (1971) refuted the finding by affirming that when an individual's educational attainment level is well aligned with his or her job skill requirements, the individual's job satisfaction level will tend to be high.

TABLE 70
THE DIFFERENCE IN THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 5 WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO PROFILE

PROFILE	Degrees of Freedom	Computed F-value	Critical F-value	Interpretation
Age	(8, 85)	3.361	2.049	Significant
Sex	(1, 92)	3.661	3.945	Not Significant
Length of Service	(6, 87)	2.957	2.205	Significant
Educational Attainment	(4, 89)	0.740	2.474	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 70 presents the difference in the level of employees' morale of School 5 when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, degrees of freedom, computed F -value, critical F -value, and interpretation.

The computed F value 3.361 for "Age" is significant against the critical F value 2.049 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 3.661 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 3.945 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of sex. The computed F value 2.957 for "Length of Service" is significant against the critical F value 2.205 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.740 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 2.474 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. That is, they have no difference of employees' morale in terms of educational attainment.

Of the four profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Age" and "Length of Service" affect the employees' morale of School 5. That is, the spirit of the employees that would make them want to succeed is influenced by their age and length of service. This means that employees' morale in Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan, Incorporated is influenced by age and length of service. With regard to age as related to employee morale, this finding is supported by the study entitled, "*Employee Attitudes as a Function of Age and Length of Service: A Reconceptualization*" by Gibson & Klein (1970) who found that there is a positive relationship between age and overall satisfaction (morale); satisfaction with pay, job, supervisor. An article entitled, Factor Affecting Morale, indicated that, while younger workers are more dissatisfied with higher expectations than their elders, older employees have more stability which comes with maturity, a serious attitude towards job, more reliability, less absenteeism, proven steady work habits, a sense of responsibility and loyalty and less tendency to be distracted by outside interest as influences (https://ebrary.net/2848/management/factors_affecting_morale). Vollmer & Kinney (1955) found that younger employees were found to be more likely to report job satisfaction than older employees.

With regard to the length of service as related to employee morale, the finding is corroborated with the study of Ilagan and Javier (2014) who found that, in terms of placement and promotion, length of service is significantly related to employees' morale. However, it contradicted the study of Gibson and Klein (1970) who found that there is no significant relationship between tenure and satisfaction (morale) for three reasons: disconfirmed expectations of relatively hopeful, naïve new employees, acculturation into a we-they value system occurs, and perceptions of favoritism occur as other people in the system are promoted. The study entitled "*Supervision and other Determinants of Employee Morale: The Case of Banco De Oro Branches in Batangas City and Bauan, Philippines*" of Ilagan and Javier (2014) indicated that, in terms of bank style supervision, the respondents' nature of work is affected by their age, highest educational attainment and their monthly income. It supports the present finding that age is significantly related to morale while refutes the finding that educational attainment is not related to morale. But the study entitled, "*Effects of Ethical Climate and Ethical Leadership on Employee Attitudes: Bosnian Case*" by Dinc & Aydemir (2014) indicated that educational level of employees were positively related to their job satisfaction.

TABLE 71
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION MAKING PRACTICES AND THE EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 1

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Employees' Morale	Critical r
Egoism	0.466*	0.427
Benevolence	0.697**	0.561
Principle	0.647**	0.561

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) $df = 18$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 71 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 1. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, the correlation r with employees' morale, and critical r .

The computed Pearson r values, 0.466, 0.697, and 0.647 are significant against the critical r values 0.427 and 0.561 with 18 degrees of freedom at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of uncertainty. We do have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is a significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.466 is interpreted as moderate correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **egoism** is moderately related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.697 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **benevolence** is highly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.647 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **principle** is highly related to the employees' morale.

The result revealed that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly affect the employees' morale of School 1. With the highest computed value of 0.697** this means that administrators in School 1 who use benevolent criterion in ethical decision-making will boost the motivation and commitment of the employees. This finding is supported by the study entitled, "*The Role of Leadership in Creating Virtuous and Compassionate Organizations: Narratives of Benevolent Leadership in an Anatolian Tiger*" by Karakas & Sarigullo (2013) found that using benevolent leadership framework, leaders can create supportive team and work environments for employees centered on ethical sensitivity, spiritual depth, positive engagement, and community responsiveness.

TABLE 72
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES AND THE EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 2

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Employees' Morale	Critical r
Egoism	-0.165	0.334
Benevolence	0.016	0.334
Principle	0.217	0.334

$\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 33$

Table 72 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 2. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, the correlation r with employees' morale, and critical r .

The computed Pearson r values, -0.165, 0.016, and 0.217, are not significant against the critical r value 0.334 with 33 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices do not affect employee morale. This finding is supported by the study entitled "The Effects of Ethical Climate and Ethical Leadership on Employee Attitudes: Bosnian Case" by Dinc & Aydemir, who found that ethical leadership has no positive influence on employees' job satisfaction at private universities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

However, few researchers believe that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices impact employees' morale. The study entitled "The Effect of Ethical Leadership on Employees' Job Satisfaction: A Study on Municipalities in Konya" by Attar, Cagliyan, & Ajdarovski (2017) showed that ethical leadership positively affects job satisfaction levels of administrative personnel in Konya municipalities. The study entitled "The Virtuous Influence of Ethical Leadership Behavior: Evidence from the Field," Neubert, Carlson, Kacmar & Chonko (2009) demonstrated that leaders' ethical behavior has a direct and an indirect impact on followers' job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

TABLE 73

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION-MAKING PRACTICES AND THE EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 3

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Employees' Morale	Critical r
Egoism	0.459*	0.413
Benevolence	0.583**	0.526
Principle	0.568**	0.526

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) $df = 21$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 73 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 3. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, the correlation r with employees' morale, and critical r .

The computed Pearson r values, 0.459, 0.583, and 0.568, are significant against the critical r values 0.413 and 0.526, with 21 degrees of freedom at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of uncertainty. We do have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, a significant relationship exists between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.459 is interpreted as a moderate correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **egoism** is moderately related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.583 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **benevolence** is highly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.568 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **principle** are highly related to the employees' morale.

The result revealed that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly affect employees' morale in School 3. With the highest computed value of 0.583** benevolent

ethical decision-making practices impact employees' morale. This finding is supported by Karakas & Sarigullo (2013) who found that benevolent leadership entails discovering and embracing employees and team members as whole persons, acknowledging not only their cognitive faculties but also their social, emotional, and spiritual faculties, to engage their hearts, spirits, and minds.

TABLE 74
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION MAKING PRACTICES AND THE EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 4

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Employees' Morale	Critical r
Egoism	0.156	0.339
Benevolence	0.258	0.339
Principle	0.233	0.339

$\alpha = 0.05$ $df = 32$

Table 74 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 4. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, the correlation r with employees' morale, and critical r .

The computed Pearson r values, 0.156, 0.258, and 0.233 are not significant against the critical r value 0.339 with 32 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 4. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices have no impact to the employees' morale. However, a certain entitled, "*Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment – A Study in the Construction Sector in India*" by Nidadhavolu (2018) study does not support the present finding. The study indicated that leadership styles have a significant impact on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

TABLE 75
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ADMINISTRATORS' ETHICAL DECISION MAKING PRACTICES AND THE EMPLOYEES' MORALE OF SCHOOL 5

Ethical Decision-Making Practice	Correlation r with Employees' Morale	Critical r
Egoism	0.249*	0.203
Benevolence	0.296**	0.264
Principle	0.234*	0.203

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) $df = 92$

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 75 presents the relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 5. The table shows the ethical decision-making practice, the correlation r with employees' morale, and critical r .

The computed Pearson r values, 0.249, 0.296, and 0.234 are significant against the critical r values 0.203 and 0.264 with 92 degrees of freedom at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of uncertainty. We do have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is a significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale. The correlation coefficients of 0.249 is interpreted as low correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **egoism** is slightly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.296 is interpreted as low correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **benevolence** is slightly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.234 is interpreted as low correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along **principle** is slightly related to the employees' morale.

The result revealed that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly affect employees' morale in St. Vincent's College Incorporated. With the highest computed value of 0.296**, administrators using benevolent ethical decision-making practices impact the morale of employees. This finding is supported by the study of Atar, Cagliyan & Ajdarovska (2017) entitled, "*The Effect of Ethical Leadership on Employees' Job Satisfaction: A study on Municipalities in Konya,*" who found that managers who have ethical and moral values, do the right thing, worry about others and choose to be open are expected to create an ethical climate and this will in turn make the employees more satisfied by emphasizing the fairness at the work place. Blau (1964), using principles of reciprocity, said that individuals feel obligated to return when they see fair and good behaviours toward them. Naturally, employees feel indebted to ethical leaders due to their trustworthy and fair behaviors and thus, they reciprocate with beneficial work behaviors like citizenship behaviors (Brown and Mitchell, 2010) and even avoid from unethical behavior like absenteeism.

DISCUSSION

The following are the findings of the study presented by each school of five Catholic diocesan schools. The order of the findings begins with the *profile of administrators, profile of employees, level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices, school's ethical climate, relationship between administrators' ethical decision-making practices and school's ethical climate* and *administrators' ethical decision-making practices and their relationship with employees' morale*.

SCHOOL 1

1. On the **profile of the administrators** of School 1 in terms of **Age**. One (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 26 – 30 years old, no administrator is between 31 – 35 years old, three (3) or 37.5% of the administrators are between 36 – 40 years old, one (1) or 12.5% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 51 – 55 years old, no administrator is between 56 – 60 years old, and one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is 61 years old or over.

2. Sex. One (1) or 12.5% of the administrator is a male and seven (7) or 87.5% are females.

3. Length of service. Two (2) or 25.0% of the administrators have less than 3 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 3 – 7 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 8 – 12 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 13 – 17 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and one (1) or 12.5% has 28 or over years of service.

4 Educational attainments. One (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is a college graduate, two (2) or 25.0% of them have master's degree units, two (2) or 25.0% have master's degree, one (1) or 12.5% has doctorate units, and two (2) or 25.0% have a doctorate degree.

5. Seminars/ trainings attended. Three (3) or 42.9% of the administrators have not attended seminars on ethical decision making and four (4) or 57.1% have attended seminars on ethical decision making.

6. On the **profile of the employees** of School 1 in terms of **Age**. Five (5) or 25.0% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, seven (7) or 37.5% are between 26 – 30 years old, three (3) or 15.0% are between 31 – 35 years old, two (2) or 10.0% are between 36 – 40 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 46 – 50 years old, no employee is between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 56 – 60 years old, and no employee is 61 years old or over.

7. Sex. Six (6) or 30.0% of the employees are males and fourteen (14) or 70.0% are females.

8. Length of service. Five (5) or 25.0% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, eleven (11) or 55.0% have between 3 – 7 years of service, one (1) or 5.0% has between 8 – 12 years of service, two (2) or 10.0% have between 13 – 17 years of service, one (1) or 5.0% has between 18 – 22 years of service, no employee has between 23 – 27 years of service, and no employee has 28 or over years of service.

9. Educational attainment. Thirteen (13) or 65.0% of the employees are college graduate, six (6) or 30.0% of them have master's degree units, one (1) or 5.0% has master's degree, no employee has doctorate units, and no employee has a doctorate degree.

10. On the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** of School 1 along **Egoism**. The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits". The administrators sometimes practiced that "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". However, the administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments" and People should work for the success of the company".

The grand weighted mean of 5.73 tells us that the administrators of School 1 usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the school and welfare of everybody.

11. Benevolence. The administrators almost always practiced that “The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization”, “One should never psychologically or physically harm another person”, and “to help others without seeking a reward or recognition.” The administrators usually practiced that “One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual”, “People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all”, and “One considers people in their decision-making practices.”

The grand weighted mean of 6.29 tells us that the administrators of School 1 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence.

12. Principle. The administrators usually practiced that “In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness”. The administrators almost always practiced that “Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community”, “Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization”, “Employees should strictly obey company policies”, “Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules”, “Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization”, “Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees”, and “Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines”.

The grand weighted mean of 6.67 tells us that the administrators of School 1 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The administrators of School 1 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.73 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.29 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.67 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.23 tells us that level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 1 is “usually practiced”.

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 1 is in the context of principle.

13. On the significant difference in the ***level of administrators’ ethical decision making practices*** of School 1 ***when grouped according to profile***. The computed F value 0.099 for “Age” is not significant against the critical F value 19.296 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 87.417 for “Sex” is significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 9.019 for “Length of Service” is not significant against the critical F value 233.986 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.746 for “Educational Attainment” is not significant against the critical F value 9.117 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.052 for “Seminars/ Training

Attended” is not significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. Of the five profile variables, we found enough evidence that “Sex” has to do with the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 1. That is, their ethical decision-making practices vary as to their sex.

14. On the level of ethical climate of School 1 along **Caring**. At School 1, it is mostly true that: people look out for each other’s good; the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the major concern is always what is best for the other person, the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company; and each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criteria.

In this school also, it is completely true that the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criteria. The grand weighted mean of 3.81 tells us that the ethical climate of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated along caring is highly caring.

15. Instrumental. At School 1, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school’s interest in this criteria. It is somewhat true in this school that: the people are expected to do anything to further the company’s interests; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company’s interests; and people are concerned with the company’s interests. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school’s interest in this criteria. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first and there is no room for one’s own personal morals or ethics in this company. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school’s interest in this criteria.

The grand weighted mean of 3.05 tells us that the ethical climate of School 1 along instrumental is moderately concerned with the school’s interest.

16. Independence, rules, law and code. At School 1, it is somewhat false that in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school rules in this criteria. It is somewhat true in this school that: each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person’s sense of right and wrong; successful people in this company go by the book; and people are guided by their own personal ethics. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criteria. However, it is mostly true that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.32 tells us that the ethical climate of School 1 along independence, rules, law and code is moderately concerned with the school rules.

The perceptions of employees of School 1 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for caring is 3.81 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for instrumental is 3.05 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for independence, rules, law and code is 3.32 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.39 tells us that the level of ethical climate of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated is "highly ethical".

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 1 as perceived by the employees is **caring**.

17. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the level of schools' ethical climate** of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated. The table above revealed that there is a significant relationship between ethical decision-making practice of administrators and school's ethical climate of School 1. There is a strong correlation between egoism and caring, and moderate correlations between egoism and instrumental and egoism and independence, rules, law and code.

There are strong correlations between egoism and caring and instrumental ethical climates and a moderate correlation between egoism and independence, rules, law and code. There are strong correlations between benevolence and all of the climate types. There are also strong correlations between principle and all the climate types.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the predictor of a caring ethical climate is the benevolence ethical decision-making practice. The predictor of an instrumental ethical climate is the egoism and principle ethical decision-making practices. The predictor of an independence, rules, law and code ethical climate is the benevolence ethical decision-making practice.

18. On the **level of employees' morale** of School 1. The condition of the employees' morale are moderate in the sense that: they are treated equally and with respect; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they all participate in problem-solving; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; new employees are given a thorough orientation; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; the company has a great internal communication system; and the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership.

The condition of the employees' morale are high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they feel supported,

valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; the duties of their position are clearly defined; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; their senior management is open and honest; the company provides great employee benefits; they enjoy good morale in the school; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they know what is expected of them in their job; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; and they are given sufficient responsibility on their job. The grand weighted mean of 3.60 tells us that the condition of the employees' morale at School 1 are high.

19. On the significant difference in the **level of employees' morale** of School 1 **when grouped according to profile**. The computed F value 1.053 for "Age" is not significant against the critical F value 2.915 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.079 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 4.414 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 2.913 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 3.056 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 1.541 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 3.592 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the level of employees' morale of School 1 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment do not influence the morale of employees of Colegio de San Francisco Javier Incorporated.

20. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the level of employees' morale** School 1. The computed Pearson r values, 0.466, 0.697, and 0.647 are significant against the critical r values 0.427 and 0.561 with 18 degrees of freedom at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of uncertainty. We do have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is a significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.466 is interpreted as moderate correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism is moderately related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.697 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along benevolence is highly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.647 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that

the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along principle is highly related to the employees' morale.

The result revealed that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly affect the employees' morale of School 1.

SCHOOL 2

1. On the **profile of the administrators** of School 2 in terms of **age**. No administrator is between 26 – 30 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 31 – 35 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 36 – 40 years old, no administrator is between 41 – 45 years old, two (2) or 25.0% of the administrators is between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrators is between 51 – 55 years old, no administrator is between 56 – 60 years old, and three (3) or 37.5% of the administrators are 61 years old or over.

2 Sex. Three (3) or 37.5% of the administrators are males and five (5) or 62.5% of them are females.

3. Length of service. One (1) or 12.5% of the administrators has less than 3 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% of the administrator has between 3 – 7 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% of has between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator has between 13 – 17 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 12.5% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and three (3) or 37.5% have 28 or over years of service.

4. Educational attainment. Two (2) or 25.0% of the administrators are college graduate, three (3) or 37.5% of them have master's degree units, three (3) or 37.5% have master's degree, no administrator has doctorate units, and no administrator has doctorate degree.

5. Seminars / trainings attended. Six (6) or 75.0% of the administrators have not attended seminars on ethical decision making and two (2) or 25.0% have attended seminars on ethical decision making.

6. On the **profile of the employees** of School 2 in terms of **age**. Eleven (11) or 31.4% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, six (6) or 17.1% are between 26 – 30 years old, four (4) or 11.4% are between 31 – 35 years old, two (2) or 5.7% are between 36 – 40 years old, two (2) or 5.7% are between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 5.0% is between 46 – 50 years old, six (6) or 17.1% are between 51 – 55 years old, two (2) or 5.7% are between 56 – 60 years old, and one (1) or 2.9% is 61 years old or over.

7. Sex. Fifteen (15) or 42.9% of the employees are males and twenty (20) or 57.1% are females.

8. Length of service. Fourteen (14) or 40.0% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, seven (7) or 20.0% have between 3 – 7 years of service, three (3) or 8.6%

have between 8 – 12 years of service, four (4) or 11.4% have between 13 – 17 years of service, two (2) or 5.7% have between 18 – 22 years of service, five (5) or 14.3% are between 23 – 27 years of service, and no employee has 28 or over years of service.

9. Educational attainments. Twenty four (24) or 68.6% of the employees are college graduate, nine (9) or 25.7% of them have master's degree units, one (1) or 2.9% has master's degree, no employee has doctorate units, and one (1) or 2.9% has a doctorate degree.

10. On the *level of administrators' ethical decision making practices* of School 2 along **egoism**. The administrators often practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations", "People should do well in the organization for rewards", and "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators usually practiced that "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits." However, the administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments" and "People should work for the success of the company".

The grand weighted mean of 5.59 tells us that the administrators of Rizal Memorial Institute of Dapitan Incorporated usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the school and welfare of everybody.

11. Benevolence. The administrators almost always practiced that "The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization", "One should never psychologically or physically harm another person", "People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all", "to help others without seeking a reward or recognition", and "One considers people in their decision-making practices." The administrators usually practiced that "One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual".

The grand weighted mean of 6.54 tells us that the administrators of School 2 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence.

12. Principle. The administrators usually practiced that "In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness". The administrators almost always practiced that "Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community", "Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization", "Employees should strictly obey company policies", "Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules", and "Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees". The administrators always practiced that "Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization", and "Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines".

The grand weighted mean of 6.94 tells us that the administrators of School 2 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The administrators of School 2 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.59 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.54 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.94 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.47 tells us that level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 2 is "almost always practiced".

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 2 is **principle**.

13. On the significant difference in the ***level of administrators' ethical decision making practices*** of School 2 ***when grouped according to profile;***

The computed F value 0.425 for "Age" is not significant against the critical F value 9.117 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.734 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.360 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 19.296 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.307 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 5.786 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 9.311 for "Seminars/ Training Attended" is significant against the critical F value 5.987 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. Of the five profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Seminars/Training Attended" has to do with the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 2. That is, their approach to problems or situations are influenced by the seminars/training on ethical decision-making they had attended.

14. On the ***level of ethical climate*** of School 2 along ***caring***. At School 2, it is mostly true that: people look out for each other's good; the major concern is always what is best for the other person; the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criteria.

In this school also, it is completely true that: the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently; and the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criteria.

The grand weighted mean of 3.81 tells us that the ethical climate of School 2 along caring is highly caring.

15. Instrumental. At School 2, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in these criteria. It is somewhat true in this school that: there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests; people protect their own interest above other considerations; and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that

people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in these criteria. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first and the people are expected to do anything to further the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in these criteria.

The grand weighted mean of 3.05 tells us that the ethical climate of School 2 along instrumental is moderately concerned with the school's interest.

16. Independence, rules, law and code. At School 2, it is somewhat true that in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in these criteria. It is mostly true in this school that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; successful people in this company go by the book; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in these criteria.

The grand weighted mean of 3.72 tells us that the ethical climate of School 2 along independence, rules, law and code is highly concerned with the school rules.

The perceptions of employees of School 2 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for caring is 3.96 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for instrumental is 3.10 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for independence, rules, law and code is 3.72 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.59 tells us that the level of ethical climate of School 2 is "highly ethical".

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 2 as perceived by the employees is **caring**.

17. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** and the **level of schools' ethical climate** of School 2 between egoism and caring and independence, rules, law and code ethical climate types but there is a significant relationship between egoism and instrumental. There is a significant relationship between benevolence and caring and instrumental ethical climate types but

there is no significant relationship between benevolence and the independence, rules, law and code. There is a significant relationship between principle and caring and independence, rules, law and code but there is no significant relationship between principle and instrumental.

The strength of correlation between egoism and instrumental is weak. There is a moderate correlation between benevolence and caring and a weak correlation between benevolence and instrumental. There is a moderate correlation between principle and caring and independence, rules, law and code ethical climate types.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the predictor of a caring climate are principle and benevolence. The instrumental climate is manifested by egoism practice, and independence, rules, law and code climate is **principle** ethical decision-making practice.

18. On the *level of employees' morale* of School 2.

The condition of the employees' morale is moderate in the sense that: they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; and the company provides great employee benefits.

The condition of the employees' morale is high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they know what is expected of them in their job; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are treated equally and with respect; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are happy with the employee review system; they all participate in problem-solving; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; new employees are given a thorough orientation; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; they enjoy good morale in the school; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; and they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job.

The grand weighted mean of 3.87 tells us that the condition of the employees' morale at School 2 is **high**.

19. On the significant difference in the **level of employees' morale** of School 2 **when grouped according to profile**

The computed F value 2.357 for "Age" is significant against the critical F value 2.320 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.609 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 4.139 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 3.261 for "Length of Service" is significant against the critical F value 2.545 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.513 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 2.911 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. Of the four profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Age" and "Length of Service" affect the employees' morale of School 2. That is, the spirit of the employees that would make them want to succeed is influenced by their age and length of service.

20. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** and the **level of employees' morale** School 2. The computed Pearson r values, -0.165, 0.016, and 0.217 are not significant against the critical r value 0.334 with 33 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 2. This infers that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices has no impact to the employees' morale.

SCHOOL 3

1. On the **profile of the administrators** of School 3 in terms of **age**. No administrator is below 31, one (1) or 20.0% of the administrator is between 31 - 35 years old, two (2) or 40.0% is between 36 – 40 years old and one (1) or 20.0% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 20.0% is between 46 – 50 years old and no administrator is above 50 years old.

2. **Sex**. Three (3) or 60.0% of the administrators are males and two (2) or 40.0% of are females.

3. **Length of service**. Of the five administrators, three (3) or 60.0% have between 8 – 12 years of service and two (2) or 40.0% have between 23 – 27 years of service.

4. **Educational attainment**. No administrator is a college graduate, two (2) or 40.0% have master's degree units, two (2) or 40.0% have master's degree, one (1) or 20.0% has doctorate units, and no administrator has a doctorate degree.

5. **Seminars/ trainings attended**. Of the five administrators, four (4) or 80.0% have not attended seminars on ethical decision making and one (1) or 20.0% has attended seminars on ethical decision making.

6. On the **profile of the employees** of San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated in terms of **age**. Six (6) or 26.1% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, three (3) or 13.0% are between 26 – 30 years old, one (1) or 4.3% are between 31 – 35 years old, five (5) or 21.7% are between 36 – 40 years old, four (4) or 17.4% are between 41 – 45 years old, no administrator is between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 4.3% are between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 4.3% are between 56 – 60 years old, and two (2) or 8.7% is 61 years old or over.

7. **Sex.** Eight (8) or 34.8% of the employees are males and fifteen (15) or 65.2% are females.

8. **Length of service.** Six (6) or 26.1% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, eleven (11) or 47.8% have between 3 – 7 years of service, four (4) or 17.4% have between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator have between 13 – 22 years of service, two (2) or 8.7% are between 23 – 27 years of service, and no employee has 28 or over years of service.

9. **Educational attainment.** Twelve (12) or 52.2% of the employees are college graduate, seven (7) or 30.4% of them have master's degree units, four (4) or 17.4% has master's degree, no employee has doctorate units, and no employee has a doctorate degree.

10. On the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** of School 3 along **egoism**. The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits." The administrators sometimes practiced that "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments". The administrators also always practiced that "People should work for the success of the company".

The grand weighted mean of 5.61 tells us that the administrators of San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the school and welfare of everybody.

11. **Benevolence.** The administrators almost always practiced that "One should never psychologically or physically harm another person", "People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all", and "One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual". The administrators always practiced that "The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization", "to help others without seeking a reward or recognition", and "One considers people in their decision-making practices." The grand weighted mean of 6.99 tells us that the administrators of School 3 almost always practiced benevolence criterion in ethical decision-making.

12. **Principle.** The administrators usually practiced that "In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness". The administrators almost always

practiced that “Employees should strictly obey company policies”, “Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules”, and “Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization”. The administrators always practiced that “Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community”, “Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization”, “Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees”, and “Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines”.

The grand weighted mean of 6.82 tells us that the administrators of School 3 almost always practiced principle criterion in ethical decision-making.

The administrators of School 3 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.61 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.99 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.82 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.47 tells us that level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 3 is “almost always practiced”.

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 3 is **benevolence**.

13. On the significant difference in the **level of administrators’ ethical decision making practices** of School 3 **when grouped according to profile**. The computed F value 0.224 for “Age” is not significant against the critical F value 215.707 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 1.883 for “Sex” is not significant against the critical F value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 1.883 for “Length of Service” is not significant against the critical F value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 2.671 for “Educational Attainment” is not significant against the critical F value 19.000 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.900 for “Seminars/ Training Attended” is significant against the critical F value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 3 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, educational attainment and seminars/ training attended in ethical decision making do not influence the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 3.

14. On the **level of ethical climate** of School 3 along **caring**. At School 3, it is somewhat true that people look out for each other’s good. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion. It is mostly true that: the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the major concern is always what is best for the other person; the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company; and each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.74 tells us that the ethical climate of School 3 along caring is highly caring.

15. Instrumental. At School 3, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves and there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. It is somewhat true in this school that: the people are expected to do anything to further the company's interests; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests; and people protect their own interest above other considerations. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 2.94 tells us that the ethical climate of School 3 along instrumental is moderately concerned with the school's interest.

16. Independence, rules, law and code. At School 3, it is somewhat true that: in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; successful people in this company go by the book. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.46 tells us that the ethical climate of School 3 along independence, rules, law and code is highly concerned with the school rules.

The perceptions of employees of School 3 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for caring is 3.74 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for instrumental is 2.94 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for independence, rules, law and code is 3.46 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.38 tells us that the level of ethical climate of San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated is “highly ethical”.

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 3 as perceived by the employees is **caring**.

17. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators’ ethical decision making practices** and the **level of schools’ ethical climate** of School 3 .The table above revealed that one, there is no significant relationship between egoism and the ethical climate types; two, that there is no significant relationship between benevolence; and third, that the ethical climate types; and fourth, that there is no significant relationship between independence, rules, law and code and the ethical climate types.

We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant relationship between the administrators’ ethical decision-making practices and the schools’ ethical climate. This implies that ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 3 is not significantly related to the school’s ethical climate.

18. On the **level of employees’ morale** of School 3. The condition of the employees’ morale are high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they all participate in problem-solving; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; the company provides great employee benefits; and they enjoy good morale in the school;

The condition of the employees’ morale are very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they know what is expected of them in their job; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; they are treated equally and with respect; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; new employees are given a thorough orientation; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school. The grand weighted mean of 4.21 tells us that the condition of the employees’ morale at School 3 is **very high**.

19. On the significant difference in the **level of employees' morale** of School 3 **when grouped according to profile**. The computed F value 2.011 for "Age" is not significant against the critical F value 2.707 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.043 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 4.325 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 2.321 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 3.127 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.473 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 3.493 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the level of employees' morale of School 3 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment do not influence the morale of employees of School 3

20. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** and the **level of employees' morale** San Estanislao Kostka College Incorporated. The computed Pearson r values, 0.459, 0.583, and 0.568 are significant against the critical r values 0.413 and 0.526 with 21 degrees of freedom at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of uncertainty. We do have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is a significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.459 is interpreted as moderate correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism is moderately related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.583 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along benevolence is highly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.568 is interpreted as strong correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along principle is highly related to the employees' morale.

The result revealed that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly impact employees' morale of School 3.

SCHOOL 4

1. On the profile of the administrators of School 4 in terms of **age**. No administrator is below 36 years old, one (1) or 20.0% of them is 36 – 40 years old, one (1) or 20.% is between 41 – 45 years old, one (1) or 20.0% is between 46 – 50 years old and one (1) or 20.0% is between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 20.0% is between 56 – 60 years old, and no administrator is 61 years old or above.

2. **Sex**. All administrators are males.

3. **Length of service**. No administrator has less than 8 years of service, two (2) or 40.0% has between 8 – 12 years of service, two (2) or 40.0% has between 13 – 17 years of service, no administrator has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 20.0% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and no administrator has 28 or above years of service.

4. **Educational attainment**. Three (3) or 60.0% of the administrators have a master's degree, and two (2) or 40.0% have a doctorate degree.

5. Seminars/ trainings attended. No administrator has attended seminars or trainings in ethical decision-making.

6. On the profile of employees of School 4 in terms of age. Fifteen (15) or 44.1% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, ten (10) or 29.4% are between 26 – 30 years old, two (2) or 5.9% are between 31 – 35 years old, two (2) or 5.9% are between 36 – 40 years old, three (3) or 8.8% are between 41 – 45 years old, two (2) or 5.9% are between 46 – 50 years old, and no administrator has 51 years old or over.

7. **Sex.** Eleven (11) or 32.4% of the employees are males and twenty-three (23) or 67.6% are females.

8. **Length of service.** Eleven (11) or 32.4% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, seventeen (17) or 50.0% have between 3 – 7 years of service, three (3) or 8.8% have between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator have between 13 – 17 years of service, three (3) or 8.8% have between 18 – 22 years of service, and no employee has 23 or over years of service.

9. **Educational attainment.** Eleven (11) or 32.4% of the employees are college graduate, thirteen (13) or 38.2% of them have master's degree units, nine (9) or 26.5% has master's degree, one (1) or 2.9% has employee has doctorate units, and no employee has a doctorate degree.

10. On the **level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices** of School 4 along **egoism**. The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits." The administrators sometimes practiced that "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments". The administrators also always practiced that "People should work for the success of the company".

The grand weighted mean of 5.70 tells us that the administrators of School 4 usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the school and welfare of everybody.

11. **Benevolence.** The administrators always practiced that "The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization", "One should never psychologically or physically harm another person", and "to help others without seeking a reward or recognition". The administrators almost always practiced that "One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual". The administrators also usually practiced "People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all".

The grand weighted mean of 7.03 tells us that the administrators of School 4 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence.

12. **Principle.** The administrators usually practiced that "In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness". The administrators almost always

practiced that “Employees should strictly obey company policies”, “Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules”, “Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization”, and “Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees”. The administrators always practiced that “Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community”, “Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization”, and “Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines”.

The grand weighted mean of 6.88 tells us that the administrators of School 4 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The administrators of School 4 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.70 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 7.03 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 6.88 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.54 tells us that level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 4 is “almost always practiced”. However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 4 is **benevolence**.

13. On the significant difference in the **level of administrators’ ethical decision making practices** of School 4 **when grouped according to profile**. The computed F value 2.217 for “Age” is not significant against the critical F value 215.707 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. No F statistic can be computed for the difference in ethical decision-making practices in terms of sex since all of the administrators are males. The computed F value 5.800 for “Length of Service” is not significant against the critical F value 19.000 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 2.536 for “Educational Attainment” is not significant against the critical F value 12.128 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. No F statistic can be computed for the difference in ethical decision-making practices in terms of seminars/training attended since all of the administrators have not attended that kind of seminar or training. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 4 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment does not influence the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 4.

14. On the **level of ethical climate** of Saint Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated along **caring**. At School 4, it is mostly true that: people look out for each other’s good; the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the major concern is always what is best for the other person; the most efficient way is always the right way; in this school, the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently and the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.92 tells us that the ethical climate of School 4 along caring is highly caring.

15. Instrumental. At School 4, it is somewhat false that people are mostly out for themselves. This implies that people in this school are slightly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. It is somewhat true in this school that: there is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this company; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company's interests; and people protect their own interest above other considerations. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school's interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first; and people are concerned with the company's interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school's interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.11 tells us that the ethical climate of School 4 along instrumental is moderately concerned with the school's interest.

16. Independence, rules, law and code. At School 4, it is somewhat true that: in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; the most important consideration in this company is each person's sense of right and wrong; and successful people in this company go by the book. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.49 tells us that the ethical climate of School 4 along independence, rules, law, and code is highly concerned with the school rules.

The perceptions of employees of School 4 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for caring is 3.92 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for instrumental is 3.11 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for independence, rules, law, and code is 3.49 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.51 tells us that the level of ethical climate of School 4 “highly ethical”.

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 4 as perceived by the employees is **caring**.

17. On the significant relationship between **the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices** and the **level of schools’ ethical climate** of School 4. The table above revealed that there is no significant relationship between egoism and the ethical climate caring but there is a significant relationship between egoism and ethical climates instrumental and independence, rules, law and code. There is no significant relationship between benevolence and the ethical climate types. There is a significant relationship between principle and caring and independence, rules, law and code, however there is no significant relationship between principle and instrumental.

The correlation coefficients 0.433 and 0.503 between egoism and instrumental and independence, rules, law and code respectively indicates moderate correlation. There is a low correlation between principle and the climate types caring and independence, rules, law, and code.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the principal practice is a predictor of caring, and independence, rules, law and code ethical climate types. The predictor of instrumental climate type is **egoism**.

18. On the **level of employees’ morale** of School 4. The condition of the employees’ morale are moderate in the sense that: the workload is fairly allocated among employees; new employees are given a thorough orientation; and the company provides great employee benefits.

The condition of the employees’ morale are high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are treated equally and with respect; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; they all participate in problem-solving; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; they enjoy good morale in the school; and they are optimistic about the future of the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they know what is expected of them in their job; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The grand weighted mean of 3.89 tells us that the condition of the employees' morale at School 4 is **high**.

19. On the significant difference in the **level of employees' morale** of School 4 **when grouped according to profile**. The computed F value 1.579 for "Age" is not significant against the critical F value 2.558 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.877 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 4.149 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.451 for "Length of Service" is not significant against the critical F value 2.922 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.822 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 2.922 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant difference in the level of employees' morale School 4 when grouped according to profile. This means that age, sex, length of service, and educational attainment does not affect the psychological well-being of the employees as they perform their jobs.

20. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices** and the **level of employees' morale** of School 4. The computed Pearson r values, 0.156, 0.258, and 0.233 are not significant against the critical r value 0.339 with 32 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of uncertainty. We do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale of School 4. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices has no impact to the employees' morale.

SCHOOL 5

1. On the **profile of the administrators** of School 5 in terms of **age**. No administrator is between 26 – 30 years old, no administrator is between 31 – 35 years old, no administrator is between 36 – 40 years old, two (2) or 20.0% of the administrators are between 41 – 45 years old, two (2) or 20.0% of them are between 46 – 50 years old, one (1) or 10.0% is between 51 – 55 years old, one (1) or 10.0% is between 56 – 60 years old, and four (4) or 40.0% are 61 years old or over.

2. **Sex**. Seven (7) or 70.0% of the administrators are males and three (3) or 30.0% of them are females.

3. **Length of service**. One (1) or 10.0% of the administrators has less than 3 years of service, two (2) or 20.0% of the administrator have between 3 – 7 years of service, no

administrator has between 8 – 12 years of service, no administrator has between 13 – 17 years of service, no administrator has between 18 – 22 years of service, one (1) or 10.0% has between 23 – 27 years of service, and six (6) or 60.0% have 28 or over years of service.

4. Educational attainment. No administrator is a college graduate, one (1) or 10.0% of them has master's degree units, three (3) or 30.0% have master's degree, four (4) or 40.0% of the administrators have doctorate units, and two (2) or 20.0% of the administrators have doctorate degree.

5. Seminars/ trainings attended. Four (4) or 40.0% of the administrators have not attended seminars on ethical decision making and six (6) or 60.0% have attended seminars on ethical decision making.

6. On the **profile of employees** St. Vincent's College Incorporated in terms of **age**. Twenty-seven (27) or 28.7% of the employees are between 21 – 25 years old, fourteen (14) or 14.9% are between 26 – 30 years old, seven (7) or 7.4% are between 31 – 35 years old, seven (7) or 7.4% are between 36 – 40 years old, eleven (11) or 11.7% are between 41 – 45 years old, twelve (12) or 12.8% are between 46 – 50 years old, seven (7) or 7.4% are between 51 – 55 years old, five (5) or 5.3% are between 56 – 60 years old, and four (4) or 4.3% is 61 years old or over.

7. Sex. Thirty-eight (38) or 40.4% of the employees are males and fifty-six (56) or 59.6% are females.

8. Length of service. Twenty-five (25) or 26.6% of the employees have less than 3 years of service, twenty five (25) or 26.6% have between 3 – 7 years of service, fifteen (15) or 16.0% have between 8 – 12 years of service, four (4) or 4.3% have between 13 – 17 years of service, nine (9) or 9.6% have between 18 – 22 years of service, six (6) or 6.4% are between 23 – 27 years of service, and ten (10) or 10.6% have 28 or over years of service.

9. Educational attainment. Twenty-seven (27) or 28.7% of the employees are college graduate, twenty-four (24) or 25.5% of them have master's degree units, thirty seven (37) or 39.4% have master's degree, five (5) or 5.3% have doctorate units, and one (1) or 1.1% has a doctorate degree.

10. On the **level of administrators' ethical decision-making practices** of School 5 along **egoism**. The administrators usually practiced that "People should protect their own interest above other considerations". The administrators often practiced that "People should do well in the organization for rewards" and "All decision-making practices should promote company interest even if these sacrifice employee benefits", and "Lying in the organization is justifiable if it is for personal benefit or for the benefit of the company". The administrators almost always practiced that "People should not perform any act that would result to punishments". The administrators also always practiced that "People should work for the success of the company".

The grand weighted mean of 5.73 tells us that the administrators of School 5 usually practiced to get the people in the organization to consider its interest and to work for the benefit of the school and welfare of everybody.

11. Benevolence. The administrators almost always practiced that “The dignity and welfare of the people should be the most important concern in the organization”, “One should not perform an action which might in any way threaten the dignity and welfare of another individual”, “People are willing to sacrifice for the benefit of all”, and “One considers people in their decision-making practices”. The administrators always practiced that “One should never psychologically or physically harm another person”, and “to help others without seeking a reward or recognition”.

The grand weighted mean of 6.97 tells us that the administrators of School 5 almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence.

12. Principle. The administrators often practiced that “In all decisions, company rules should be given importance over empathy / kindness”. The administrators almost always practiced that “Conflicts should be resolved by policies and rules”. The administrators always practiced that “Company decisions should also consider the code of ethics of the community”, “Everyone should familiarize all the policies of the organization”, “Employees should strictly obey company policies”, “Decision-making relies on the policies and guidelines set by the organization”, “Civil codes must be observed in making decision that would affect employees”, and “Leaders should be faithful to rules and guidelines”.

The grand weighted mean of 7.10 tells us that the administrators of St. Vincent’s College Incorporated almost always practiced ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The administrators of School 5 used mix practices for ethical decision-making. The grand weighted mean for egoism is 5.73 which means that they usually practiced ethical decision-making in the context of egoism. The grand weighted mean for benevolence is 6.97 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of benevolence. The grand weighted mean for principle is 7.10 which means that they almost always practice ethical decision-making in the context of principle.

The average grand weighted mean 6.60 tells us that level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 5 is “almost always practiced”.

However, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of St. Vincent’s College Incorporated is **principle**.

13. On the significant difference in the level of administrators’ ethical decision-making practices of School 5 when grouped according to profile. The computed F value 0.568 for “Age” is not significant against the critical F value 5.192 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 1.177 for “Sex” is significant against the critical F value 5.318 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 14.070 for “Length of Service” is not significant against the critical F value 4.757 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F

value 1.971 for “Educational Attainment” is not significant against the critical F value 4.757 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 2.715 for “Seminars/ Training Attended” is not significant against the critical F value 5.318 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. Of the five profile variables, we found enough evidence that “Length of Service” has to do with the ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of St. Vincent’s College Incorporated. That is, their ethical decision-making practices vary according to their length of service.

14. On the **level of ethical climate** of St. Vincent’s College Incorporated along **caring**. At School 5, it is somewhat true that the major concern is always what is best for the other person. This implies that the school is moderately caring in this criterion. It is mostly true that: people look out for each other’s good; the most important concern is the good of all the people in the company; the most efficient way is always the right way; the major consideration is what is best for everyone in the company. This implies that the school is highly caring in this criterion.

In this school also, it is completely true that each person is expected, above all, to work efficiently and the school expects that employees will always do what is right for the customer and public. This implies that the school is very highly caring in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.96 means that the ethical climate of School 5 along caring is highly caring.

15. Instrumental. At School 5, it is somewhat true that: people are mostly out for themselves; there is no room for one’s own personal morals or ethics in this company; work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the company’s interests; and people protect their own interest above other considerations. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school’s interest in this criterion. However, it is mostly true that: the major responsibility for people in this company is to consider efficiency first; people are expected to do anything to further the company’s interests; and people are concerned with the company’s interests. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school’s interest in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.20 tells us that the ethical climate of School 5 along instrumental is moderately concerned with the school’s interest.

16. Independence, rules, law and code. At School 5, it is somewhat true that: in this school, people are expected to follow their own personal and moral beliefs; each person in this company decides for himself what is right and wrong; and successful people in this company go by the book. This implies that people in this school are moderately concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is mostly true in this school that: the most important consideration in this company is each person’s sense of right and wrong; the first consideration is whether a decision violates any law; people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards; people are guided by their own personal ethics; successful people in this company strictly obey the company policies; and the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration. This implies that people in this school are highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion. It is completely true

that: it is very important to follow strictly the school rules and procedures; people are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations; and everyone is expected to stick by company rules and procedures. This implies that people in this school are very highly concerned with the school rules in this criterion.

The grand weighted mean of 3.65 tells us that the ethical climate of School 5 along independence, rules, law, and code is highly concerned with the school rules.

The perceptions of employees of School 5 on how ethical issues vary according to situations. The grand weighted mean for caring is 3.96 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly caring. The grand weighted mean for instrumental is 3.20 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are moderately concerned with school's interest. The grand weighted mean for independence, rules, law and code is 3.65 which means that the perceptions of employees of the school's ethical climate are highly concerned with the school rules.

The average grand weighted mean 3.39 tells us that the level of ethical climate of St. Vincent's College Incorporated is "highly ethical".

However, the most dominant ethical climate of School 5 as perceived by the employees is **caring**.

17. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** and the **level of schools' ethical climate** of School 5. The table above revealed that there is a significant relationship between egoism and the ethical climate types. There is no significant relationship between benevolence and the caring and instrumental ethical climate types but there is a significant relationship between benevolence and independence, rules, law and code. There is a significant relationship between principle and caring and independence, rules, law and code, however there is no significant relationship between principle and instrumental.

The correlation coefficient 0.342 between egoism and caring indicates low correlation and the correlation coefficients 0.450 and 0.472 between egoism and instrumental and independence, rules, law and code respectively indicate moderate correlation. There is a low correlation between principle and the climate types caring and independence, rules, law and code.

By using the values of correlation coefficients, the predictor of caring, and instrumental and independence, rules, law and code ethical climate types is **egoism**.

18. On the **level of employees' morale** of School 5. The condition of the employees' morale is moderate in the sense that the new employees are given a thorough orientation; and the company provides great employee benefits. The condition of the employees' morale is high in the sense that: they feel secure in their employment; they feel supported, valued and appreciated; they have access to managers/supervisors when I need a decision; they are given adequate training, authority, and resources to do their job effectively; they receive feedback on how they perform their job that is helpful and not

disadvantageous/unsupportive; they are provided with a safe working environment – physically and mentally –and is free of harassment; they are treated equally and with respect; they are able to maintain a reasonable balance between their family and their job; they have a fair and equal opportunity to air grievances in a safe environment; they are happy with the pay levels and believe they paid well for my job; they are happy with the employee review system; they are involved in decisions affecting their position/work; they all participate in problem-solving; their manager supports them in their professional development; their manager ensures that they are recognized and appreciated for their efforts in making the company grow; they feel there is a fair opportunity for advancement in the company; the workload is fairly allocated among employees; they enjoy their job and believe they have a secure future in the school; they are satisfied with the professionalism shown by their fellow peers and leaders; the employee turn-over is reasonable- not high; their senior management is open and honest; the company has a great internal communication system; the company is managed well, and we trust the leadership; the company provides great employee benefits; and they enjoy good morale in the school.

The condition of the employees' morale is very high in the sense that: they are happy to come to work every morning; they can do their work without fear; they know what is expected of them in their job; their work gives them a feeling of accomplishment and pride; they are given sufficient responsibility on their job; the duties of their position are clearly defined; they are optimistic about the future of the school; and overall, they are happy with their job and place in the school.

The grand weighted mean of 3.93 means that the condition of the employees' morale at School 5 is **high**.

19. On the significant difference in the **level of employees' morale** of School 5 **when grouped according to profile**. The computed F value 3.361 for "Age" is significant against the critical F value 2.049 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 3.661 for "Sex" is not significant against the critical F value 3.945 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 2.957 for "Length of Service" is significant against the critical F value 2.205 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. The computed F value 0.740 for "Educational Attainment" is not significant against the critical F value 2.474 at 0.05 level of uncertainty. Of the four profile variables, we found enough evidence that "Age" and "Length of Service" affect the employees' morale of School 5. That is, the spirit of the employees that would make them want to succeed is influenced by their age and length of service.

20. On the significant relationship between the **level of administrators' ethical decision making practices** and the **level of employees' morale** School 5. The computed Pearson r values, 0.249, 0.296, and 0.234 are significant against the critical r values 0.203 and 0.264 with 92 degrees of freedom at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of uncertainty. We do have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. That is, there is a significant relationship between the administrators' ethical decision-making practices and the employees' morale. The correlation coefficients of 0.249 is interpreted as low correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along egoism are slightly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.296 is

interpreted as low correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along benevolence is slightly related to the employees' morale. The correlation coefficient of 0.234 is interpreted as low correlation. This implies that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices along principle are slightly related to the employees' morale.

The result revealed that the administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly impact the employees' morale of School 5.

Figure 2 Respondent Schools and Its Corresponding Ethical Decision-making Practice, Ethical Climate, and Employees' Morale

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: Generally, the prevalent ethical decision-making practices of Catholic diocesan schools' administrators' are benevolence and principle that create a caring ethical environment and which contribute to a confident and enthusiastic workforce. The administrators' ethical decision-making practice moderately influence a school ethical climate that offers support in career development and other opportunities for employees.

Specific conclusions about the administrators' level of ethical decision-making practice, level of school's ethical climate, and level of employees' morale are:

SCHOOL 1

Generally, the administrators usually practiced ethical decision-making that moderately influence the school's ethical climate and highly affects employees' morale.

SCHOOL 2

Generally, the administrators almost always practiced ethical decision-making that moderately influence the school's ethical climate but has no effect on employees' morale.

SCHOOL 3

Generally, the administrators almost always practiced ethical decision-making but has no influence on the school's ethical climate and moderately affects employees' morale.

SCHOOL 4

Generally, the administrators almost always practiced ethical decision-making that moderately influence the school's ethical climate but has no effect on employees' morale.

SCHOOL 5

Generally, the administrators almost always practiced ethical decision-making that slightly influence the school's ethical climate and slightly affects the employees' morale.

SPECIFIC CONCLUSIONS

SCHOOL 1

Among the three criteria for ethical decision-making practices, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 1 is principle. The most dominant ethical climate of School 1 as perceived by the employees is caring. The condition of the employees' morale at School 1 is high. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly impact the employees' morale of School 1. Thus, the researcher concludes that principle practice of administrators' ethical decision-making creates a caring ethical climate of the organization and responsible for boosting the morale of employees.

SCHOOL 2

Among the three criteria of ethical decision-making, the most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 2 is principle. The most dominant ethical climate of School 2 as perceived by the employees is caring. The condition of employees' morale at School 2 is high. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 2 has no impact on the employees' morale. Thus, the researcher concludes that principle practice of ethical decision-making forms a caring ethical climate of the organization but is not responsible for the high morale of employees.

SCHOOL 3

Among the three criteria of ethical decision making practices, most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 3 is benevolence. The most dominant ethical climate of School 3 as perceived by employees is caring. The ethical decision-making practices of the administrators of School 3 is not significantly related to the school's ethical climate. The condition of the employees' morale at School 3 is very high. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly affect the employees' morale of School 3. Thus, the researcher concludes that benevolence practice of administrators' ethical decision-making is not responsible for the formation of caring ethical climate in School 3, although it influences the high morale of employees.

SCHOOL 4

The most dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 4 is benevolence. The most dominant ethical climate of School 4 as perceived by the employees is caring. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices impact the school's ethical climate. The condition of the employees' morale at School 4 is high. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices of School 4 has no effect on employees' morale. Thus, the researcher concludes that benevolence criterion impacts school's caring climate but no effect on the high morale of employees.

SCHOOL 5

The dominant ethical decision-making practice of the administrators of School 5 is principle. The most dominant ethical climate of School 5 as perceived by the employees is caring. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices impact the school's ethical climate. The condition of the employees' morale at School 5 is high. The administrators' ethical decision-making practices significantly affect the employees' morale of School 5. Thus, the researcher concludes that principle practice of administrators' ethical decision-making is responsible for the formation of a caring climate and high morale of employees.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are based upon the above findings and conclusions for the administrators to embrace the best ethical decision-making practices so to establish the moral atmosphere of the work environment and the level of ethics practiced within the school that facilitates a positive ethical environment that can make employees more productive and even happier:

SCHOOL 1

1. School administrators (*top level & middle level management*) should familiarize the dominant ethical climate of school to assess their ethical leadership style so as to shape an ethical culture unique of its own.
2. New employees should be inducted to the ethical climate of the organization so that they can easily adopt the ethical dynamics of the school.
3. Administrators should devise policies and practices that enhance the ethical climate of the organization.
4. Institutions can provide leadership development programs and trainings to administrators to harness their ethical decision-making practices.
5. Establish an Ethical Committee in every school in the Catholic diocesan schools that is linked to quality, safety and excellence in education.
6. Schools' ethical climate should be felt by students integrating it in the lesson plan/syllabus.
7. For future researchers, another subject worth for investigating is if there is any relationship between ethical climate and employees' morale of the school

SCHOOL 2

1. Administrators should be familiar with the dominant ethical climate the organization has in order to assess their ethical leadership style so as to shape an ethical culture unique of its own.
2. New employees should be inducted to the ethical climate of the organization so that they can easily adopt the ethical dynamics of the school
3. Administrators should devise policies and practices that enhance the ethical climate of the organization
4. Institutions can provide leadership development programs and trainings to administrators to harness their ethical decision-making practices.
5. Administrators should find out the reason why their ethical decision-making practices has no impact on employees, morale.
6. Dominant ethical climate of the school should be incorporated in the school's community extension services and outreach programs so that the ethical culture of the school will be felt by the least fortunate and underprivileged.
7. For future researchers, another subject worth investigating for is if there is any relationship between ethical leadership and employee misconduct.

SCHOOL 3

1. Administrators should be familiar with the dominant ethical climate the organization has in order to assess their ethical leadership style so as to shape an ethical culture unique of its own.
2. New employees should be inducted to the ethical climate of the organization so that they can easily adopt the ethical dynamics of the school
3. Administrators should devise policies and practices that enhance the ethical climate of the organization
4. Institutions can provide leadership development programs and trainings to administrators to harness their ethical decision-making practices.
5. Establish an Ethical Committee in every school in the Catholic diocesan schools that is linked to quality, safety and excellence in education.
6. Administrators should find out the reason why their ethical decision-making practices do not affect the school's ethical climate.
7. Administrators should discover why their ethical decision-making practices has a low influence on employees' morale.
8. For future researchers, another subject worth investigating for is if there is any relationship between existing school ethical climate affect administrators' ethical decision-making practices.

SCHOOL 4

1. Administrators should be familiar with the dominant ethical climate the organization has in order to assess their ethical leadership style so as to shape an ethical culture unique of its own.
2. New employees should be inducted to the ethical climate of the organization so that they can easily adopt the ethical dynamics of the school
3. Administrators should devise policies and practices that enhance the ethical climate of the organization
4. Institutions can provide leadership development programs and trainings to administrators to harness their ethical decision-making practices.
5. Establish an Ethical Committee in every school in the Catholic diocesan schools that is linked to quality, safety and excellence in education.
6. Administrators should find out why their ethical decision-making practices has no impact on the morale of employees.
7. For future researchers, another subject worth investigating for is if there is any relationship between ethical decision-making and employees' job satisfaction.

SCHOOL 5

1. Administrators should be familiar with the dominant ethical climate the organization has in order to assess their ethical leadership style so as to shape an ethical culture unique of its own.
2. New employees should be inducted to the ethical climate of the organization so that they can easily adopt the ethical dynamics of the school

3. Administrators should devise policies and practices that enhance the ethical climate of the organization
 4. Institutions can provide leadership development programs and trainings to administrators to harness their ethical decision-making practices.
 5. Administrators should improve their ethical decision-making practices so that it can greatly affect the school's ethical climate and employees' morale.
 6. Administrators should evaluate if the present ethical climate does not overlap the core values of the schools.
 7. Establish an Ethical Committee in every school that is linked to quality, safety and excellence in education.
 8. For future researchers, another subject worth investigating for is if there is any relationship between ethical decision-making practices and organizational commitment of employees.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

This research adheres to the highest ethical standards and principles, ensuring the protection of participants' rights, confidentiality, and integrity throughout the study. The following ethical considerations were meticulously addressed and implemented:

Institutional Review Board (IRB) Approval

Prior to the commencement of this research, ethical clearance and approval were obtained from the Institutional Review Board. This approval ensures that the study aligns with established ethical guidelines and safeguards the welfare of participants.

Informed Consent

Participants were provided with comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Informed consent was obtained from all participants,

emphasizing their voluntary participation, the right to withdraw at any time without repercussions, and assurance of anonymity and confidentiality.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

Stringent measures were implemented to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of participants. All data collected was anonymized and stored securely, accessible only to authorized personnel involved directly in the research.

Minimization of Risks

Efforts were made to minimize any potential risks associated with the study. Participants' physical, emotional, and psychological well-being were prioritized throughout the research process. Necessary measures were taken to mitigate any foreseeable risks to participants.

Conflict of Interest

There were no conflicts of interest that could potentially influence the objectivity or integrity of this research. Any affiliations or relationships that could present a conflict of interest have been disclosed transparently.

Continuous Ethical Oversight

Continuous monitoring and ethical oversight were maintained throughout the research process. Any emerging ethical concerns were promptly addressed, and necessary actions were taken to uphold ethical standards.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank the anonymous reviewers and editors for their kind feedback and help with this manuscript.

REFERENCES

BOOKS

- Aquinas, T. (1993). *Commentary on Aristotle's Nicomachean Ethics*. USA: Dumb Ox Books
- Aureada, J.A. (2009). *Thesis Writing for Theology Students: A Primer*. Manila: UST Publishing House.
- Kohlberg, L. (1981). *Essays on Moral Development: The Psychology of Moral Development*. Vol.II, New York: Harper and Row
- Pope, S. (Ed.). (2002) *The Ethics of Aquinas*. USA: Georgetown University Press

PRINTED JOURNAL ARTICLES

- Amorado, R. (2013). Corruption of Education, Education in Corruption. *Boletin Eclesiastico de Filipinas*. Vol. 89, (900), 637-647.
- Laguda, Ricardo. (2013). Religious Education: Teaching and Learning in a Digital World. *Boletin Eclesiastico de Filipinas*. Vol. 89, (898), 659- 663.

ONLINE JOURNAL ARTICLES

- Aşçıgil, S., & Parlakgümüş, A. (2012). Ethical Work Climate as an Antecedent of Trust in Co-Workers. *Business & Professional Ethics Journal*, 31(3/4), 399-417. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/41705493>
- Badawy, M. K. How Women Managers View their Role in the Organization. *The Personnel Administrator*, 23(21:60-68, 197.
- Baldamus, W., & Behrend, H. (1951). Variations in Absenteeism during the Week: An Index of Employee Morale. *Operational Research Quarterly (1950-1952)*, 2(1), 13-14. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/3006362>
- Bartels, L., Harrick, E., Martell, K., & Strickland, D. (1998). The Relationship between Ethical Climate and Ethical Problems within Human Resource Management. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 17(7), 799-804. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25073124>
- Basten, C., (2006). A Feminised Profession: Women in the Teaching Profession. *Educational Studies*. Vol. 23, (1) 55-62. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305569970230104>
- Beck, L. (1992). Meeting the Challenge of the Future: The Place of a Caring Ethic in Educational Administration. *American Journal of Education*, Vol. 100, (4) The University of Chicago Press, 454-496. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1085818>
- Blome, C., & Paulraj, A. (2013). Ethical Climate and Purchasing Social Responsibility: A Benevolence Focus. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 116(3), 567-585. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/42001942>
- Chau, L., & Siu, W. (2000). Ethical Decision-Making in Corporate Entrepreneurial Organizations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 23(4), 365-375. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25074252>
- Chen, A., Sawyers, R., & Williams, P. (1997). Reinforcing Ethical Decision Making through Corporate Culture. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 16(8), 855-865. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25072949>
- Currie, J., & Ryan, M., (2014). Complementing Traditional Leadership: The Value of Followership. *Reference & User Services Quarterly* , Vol. 54, (2), 15-18.
- David M. Mayer, Maribeth Kuenzi and Rebecca L. Greenbaum (2010) Examining the Link Between Ethical Leadership and Employee Misconduct: The Mediating Role of Ethical Climate. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 95, Supplement 1: Regulating Ethical Failures: *Insights From Psychology* (2010), pp. 7-16 Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/29789709> Accessed: 27-11-2018 23:21
- Dawson, L. (1997). Ethical Differences between Men and Women in the Sales Profession. *Journal of Business Ethics* Vol.16 (No.11), 1143-1152. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25072979>
- Karadag, E & Bektas, F (2014). Women Administrators in Education: Leadership Behavior Assessment According to Teachers' Perceptions. *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 32-40. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317719630>

- Kelehear, Z. (2003). The Art of Schooling: Places of Authentic Learning and Caring. *Education and Culture*. Vol. 9 (2), 28-30. Indiana: Purdue University Press. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/42922722>
- Knouse, S., & Giacalone, R. (1992). Ethical Decision-Making in Business: Behavioral Issues and Concerns. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 11(5/6), 369-377. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25072286>
- Lehnert, K., Park, Y., & Singh, N. (2015). Research Note and Review of the Empirical Ethical Decision-Making Literature: Boundary Conditions and Extensions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 129(1), 195-219. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/24702894>
- Leung, A. S. M. (2008). Matching Ethical work climate to in-role and extra-role behaviors in a collectivist work setting. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 79, 43-55.
- Lewis, C., Schaps, E., & Watson, M. (1995) Beyond the Pendulum: Creating Challenging and Caring Schools. *Phi Delta Kappan*, Vol. 76, No.7, 547-554. Phi Delta Kappa International. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20405394>
- Libby, B., & Agnello, V. (2000). Ethical Decision Making and the Law. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 26(3), 223-232. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25074342>
- McKnight, D., Ahmad S., & Schroeder, R. (2001) When Do Feedback, Incentive Control, And Autonomy Improve Morale? The Importance Of Employee-Management Relationship Closeness. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, Vol. 13, No. 4 (Winter 2001), pp. 466-482. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40604365>
- Martin, K. and Cullen, J. (2006). Continuities and Extensions of Ethical Climate Theory: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 69, No. 2, 175-194. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25123946>
- Raile, E. (2013). Building Ethical Capital: Perceptions of Ethical Climate in the Public Sector. *Public Administration Review*, 73(2), 253-262. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/23355469>
- Robison, W. (1984). Management and Ethical Decision-Making. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 3(4), 287-291. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25071455>
- Shafer, W. (2015). Ethical Climate, Social Responsibility, and Earnings Management. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 126(1), 43-60. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/24702302>
- Shin, Y. (2012). CEO Ethical Leadership, Ethical Climate, Climate Strength, and Collective Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 108 (3), 299-312. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41476296>.
- Smith, R. (1991). Principals Need to be Good Followers. *High School Journal*. Vol. 5 (7), 24-27. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40364806>
- Speroff, B. (1955). Job Satisfaction and Interpersonal Desirability Values. *Sociometry*, 18(1), 69-72. doi:10.2307/2785829
- Srivastava, A., & Sinha, M. (1975). Morale of the Blue-Collar Workers in Relation to Different Degrees of Job Anxiety. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 10(3), 371-378. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/27765468>
- Starratt, R. (1991) "Building an Ethical School: A Theory for Practice in Educational Leadership." *Educational Administration Quarterly* 27, 185-202. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1085818>
- Staudinger, U. (1999) Older and Wiser? Integrating Results on the Relationship between Age and Wisdom-Related Performance. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*. Retrieved from <http://jbd.sagepub.com/content/23/3/641>

- Street, M., Robertson, C., & Geiger, S. (1997). Ethical Decision Making: The Effects of Escalating Commitment. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 16(11), 1153-1161. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/25072980>
- Torois, K., Cherop F.J., Kibet, S., Kipngetich, T.J., (2014) Ethical Leadership: The Effect on Employees. *Developing Country Studies*. 4 (25) www.iiste.org
- Tucker, Janice (2013). Graduate Programs in Education: Impact On Teachers' Careers. *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, Issue No.148, 1-26. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1017213.pdf>
- Tucker, Kristine. (n.d.). The Effects of Fear in a Job Environment. *Work - Chron.com*. Retrieved from <http://work.chron.com/effects-fear-job-environment-7989.html>
- Tyler, Tom., Blader, Stever. (2005). Can Businesses Effectively Regulate Employee Conduct? The Antecedents of Rule following in Work Settings. *The Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 48, (6), 1143-1158. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20159734>
- Victor, B., Cullen, J. (1988). The Organizational Bases of Ethical Work Climates. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 33. (1).pp. 101-125. Sage Publications. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2392857>
- Vogel, L. (2012). Leading with Hearts and Minds: Ethical Orientations of Educational Leadership On Doctoral Students. *Values and Ethics in Educational Administration*.10 (1), Retrieved from <http://3fl71l2qoj4l3y6ep2tqpwra.wpengine.netdna-cdn.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/VEEA-Vol10-No1.pdf>
- Wimbush, J., & Shepard, J. (1994) Toward an Understanding of Ethical Climate: Its Relationship to Ethical Behavior and Supervisory Influence. *Journal Business of Ethics*. Vol. 13 (8): 637-647. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25072570>
- Wimbush, J., Shepard, J., & Markhan, S. (1997). An Empirical Examination of the Multi-Dimensionality of Ethical Climate in Organizations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 16, (1), 67-77. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25072870>
- Yau-De Wang, & Hsieh, H. (2012). Toward a Better Understanding of the Link Between Ethical Climate and Job Satisfaction: A Multilevel Analysis. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 105(4), 535-545. Retrieved from <http://0-www.jstor.org.ustlib.ust.edu.ph/stable/41413236>

PUBLISHED THESES / DISSERTATION

- Dubazane, X,N. (2015) "The Impact of Ethical Climate on Organizational Commitment." 2015.
- Fitch, W. (2009) "A Study of Relationships Between Ethical Decision Making, Leadership Styles, and Demographics in Pennsylvania Superintendents." Theses and Dissertations. Retrieved from <http://knowledge.library.iup.edu/etd/868>
- Fichter, R. D. (2017). Exploring Ethical Decision-Making in Financial Institutions. Theses and Dissertations.
- Kim, S.Y (2011). Exploring The Linkages Among Employee Communication, Relational Trust, And Ethical Organizational Climates In Employee- Organizational Relationships. Theses and Dissertations.

BOOK REVIEW

- Johanson, W. (1994). Military Leadership: In Pursuit of Excellence by Robert L. Taylor and William E. Rosenbach. *Naval War College Review*. Vol.47, (4), 149-151. USA: Naval US College Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44642723>